

D4.1 Identifying enablers of successful DV policy and its implementation

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Executive Summary

The present report provides policymakers in the field of domestic violence with a support tool for developing and implementing measures against domestic violence. Based on the review and analysis of 18 best practices interventions in areas such as law enforcement, social work or health care from five EU countries, the report summarises the key factors for designing high-quality measures to combat domestic violence, as well as criteria that enable and accelerate the implementation of such measures. The solutions presented in this report were selected by members of the IMPROVE consortium in five countries: Austria, Finland, France, Germany and Spain. The selection of the analysed measures was based on their relevance in the context of the different national sets of measures against domestic violence. A measure was included in the analysis either because of its widespread practical use, its high degree of innovation or because it closed critical gaps in the overall strategy.

The solutions included in this report can be grouped according to their specific sectors. The social sector solutions include Women Shelters in Austria and Spain, Austrian Violence Protection Centres, Finish Cultural Interpreters, as well as the German Violence Against Women Support Hotline and the so-called StoP-Project. Measures focusing on the police are the Austrian Approach and Entry Ban system, the Finish Anchor Teams, the French Embedded Social Workers, and the Spanish GAMA police unit. The judicial sector is represented by the Austrian Court Assistances and the French Judicial Task Force. Health sector solutions are the Finnish Tools for screening risks of domestic violence and FGM in health care as well as the German Round Table Berlin. The analysis carried out for this report also included multi-sectorial solutions: the MARACs presented in the Finnish report, the Marburg Model from Germany, as well as the Spanish Gipuzkoa's Provincial Council Social Services' Attention Model for Gender-Based Violence and the Specialised Training for various professionals provided.

The analysis of these measures resulted in the identification of nine “critical enablers” for successful implementation, as well as nine critical enablers for the assessment of successful performance of a domestic violence (DV) policy measure. The critical enablers for successful implementation can be further divided into external and internal factors. External factors, i.e., factors that are not specifically introduced as part of the DV policy solution, include an existing legal framework, political and civil-society support, funding and funding regulations, as well as a feminist perspective and the existence of bottom-up activism. Internal factors driving

successful implementation are those factors under the immediate purview of the solution. These include a comprehensive pilot phase, the integration of the intervention into the existing (support) structures and communities, regular training, as well as peer-to-peer delivery and a bottom-up approach. Lastly, continuous assessment and evaluation by users and providers of services, in addition to internal data collection were deemed beneficial internal factors.

Critical enablers for successful performance of victim protection measures can also be divided into two categories: impact-related and design-related factors. The former focus on factors to assess and measure the performance of a solution. They consist of empirical evidence on uptake, usage and quality of a service, measurements of the trust of authorities and funding providers, as well as the cross-national transferability of a solution. In contrast, design factors look at specific qualities of a solution. The reports highlighted the following qualities as beneficial: cross-organisational and One-Stop-Shop approaches, pro-active approaches, the clear division of labour and responsibilities, low-threshold service accessibility, as well as a victim-centred and holistic design. On the basis of the analysis of these critical enablers, the so-called SISPO (Societal Foundation, Implementation Pathways, Service Design, Practical Environment and Ongoing Development) framework was developed for the conception and analysis of interventions. The framework serves as a comprehensive checklist for the design of victim protection measures. Thus, it is intended to support policy makers, practitioners and researchers in the conceptual development and assessment of state-of-the-art victim protection measures. The report concludes with a brief instruction on how to apply the SISPO framework.

1. Introduction

Victims of domestic violence continue to face barriers in access to protection services and interventions often fail to comprehensively address their needs. One reason for this is that the successful implementation of DV policies is challenging, as a multitude of legal, political, cultural, organisational and individual factors influence the success of an intervention. To improve victim protection one important question is thus what the key factors are for designing high-quality measures and what enables and accelerates their implementation. In order to answer this question, the present report highlights:

- The key factors that characterise the successful and sustainable **implementation** of DV policies and measures.
- The key factors behind the **effectiveness and success** of DV policies and measures.

To answer these two questions, victim protection strategies and the sets of DV measures that are in place in Austria, Finland, France, Germany and Spain were analysed. We examined solutions that fulfilled at least one of the following criteria: they were frequently used, well established among different interest groups, particularly innovative, and/or best suited to reach previously under-served victim groups. Except for France, in each country four measures were analysed. The reason why only two measures were analysed in France is that one of the examined interventions, namely the “Judicial Task Forces to Combat Family Violence” (see Appendix 2, Section 2.3), is a very broad and comprehensive DV policy measure that combines a number of adjunct innovations, each worth analysing in its own right.

This analysis resulted in a final list of **18 critical enablers**. Critical enablers are characteristics of good practice DV interventions that policy makers and practitioners may want to consider when designing, implementing and executing DV policies in the future. In the analysis we distinguished between critical enablers for the successful implementation of DV policies and intervention and critical enablers for the successful performance, i.e., the practical effectiveness of interventions. Both types of critical enablers can be further divided. Critical enabler for the implementation can be categorised into external and internal factors. The former are characteristics that are not part of the development and design of the specific intervention, but often exist prior to its introduction. A typical example of this is the existence of strong civil society engagement against domestic violence. Internal factors in turn are

characteristics that are specific to a certain (type of) intervention and are part of its design, for example that a DV training measure is delivered on a peer-to-peer basis. Critical enablers for successful performance of victim protection measures can be divided into impact-related and design-related factors. The former are factors that assess and measure the performance of a solution, for example statistical evidence of an intervention's usage. Design factors refer to the specific qualities of a solution, like the low-threshold design of a DV intervention.

The aim and purpose of this report is to provide policy makers and practitioners from the various sectors involved in victim protection with an easy-to-use guide for the development, implementation and delivery of victim protection measures. Therefore, the present report is structured and written in the form of a catalogue of criteria. Consequently, the main part of the report refrains from comprehensive descriptions and analytic dissections of the 18 analysed victim protection measures in favour of simple and quick access to the essential content. Only the different 'critical enablers' are presented, and their content is illustrated by reference to a few carefully selected examples from the analyses. Readers interested in the details of the various measures, or the methodology of the report are referred to the appendix. The report is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a brief overview of the various analysed measures. Section 3 and section 4 then present the critical enablers for the successful implementation of DV policies and intervention, as well as the critical enablers that are used to assess the practical successfulness of DV policies respectively. Section 5 presents the SISPO Framework, which summarises the findings, by presenting a matrix of critical enablers. The conclusion in Section 6 offers suggestions to policymakers and practitioners on how the presented results can be used in the design, development, implementation and evaluation of measures to combat violence against women.

2. Summary of analysed DV measures

2.1 Austria

Measure 1 – Approach and Entry Ban

The Approach and Entry Ban is stipulated in § 38a of the Security Police Act (SPG), and can be considered the most important police intervention for addressing domestic violence in Austria. The imposition of the measure prohibits the perpetrator from entering or approaching the home of the victim for a period of two weeks. This applies regardless of whether the perpetrator or the victim is the owner or main tenant of the home. § 38a SPG obliges police officers to issue a ban in case of “dangerous situation”. Police can define a situation to be dangerous based on the likelihood of an act of violence to occur. Following the issuing of the ban the police must notify the regional violence protection centre, providing victim information to facilitate proactive outreach. The police also have to inform victims about restraining order options. Additionally, perpetrators are required to engage in violence prevention counselling within 14 days. The incident is recorded in the Central Violence Protection Register for three years.

Measure 2 – Women’s Shelters

Austria has 33 women’s shelters, of which 16 are linked to the Association of Autonomous Austrian Women’s Shelters. These shelters provide critical services for women and children affected by violence, including accommodation, legal advice, psycho-social support, and assistance with authorities and courts. Core support activities include creating safety plans, aiding in legal claims, and providing parenting or separation guidance. Depending on the financial situation of the women seeking help, access and the stay may be free of charge or require a small fee. Shelters often extend support beyond the victim’s stay, offering follow-up care and social reintegration. They operate on a victim-centred approach, ensuring all measures have the victim’s consent. Additionally, they contribute to societal awareness through workshops, campaigns, and educational events. Staff typically have backgrounds in psychology, social work, or law, coupled with specialised training to support victims effectively.

Measure 3 – Violence Protection Centres

Violence protection centres (GSZ) are federally mandated and organised at the state level, focusing on comprehensive support for victims, such as navigating legal processes, finding

housing, and facilitating police reporting. GSZ also have mobile units and local offices to ensure accessibility, particularly in rural areas. GSZ provide victims with short- as well as long term support. Initial support typically involves addressing immediate security needs. This can include a preliminary risk assessment and the drafting of a security plan. More immediate actions include supporting victims when filing police reports and accompanying them to the police. A large part of the work of GSZ personal is providing judicial and long-term support, primarily in the form of psycho-social court assistance.

Measure 4 – Court Assistance for Victims

Psycho-Social Court Assistance (PSCA) and Legal Court Assistance (LCA) are two interventions aimed at supporting victims during (criminal) trial. The PSCA provides social and emotional support by preparing victims for legal proceedings. The main aim is to prevent re-traumatisation, as well as to help victims to feel confident and secure during their court testimony and hearing. The PSCA includes direct accompaniment during trials and extends to civil trial arising from criminal proceedings, such as custody or alimony disputes. The LCA provides legal representation to safeguard victims' rights and ensure procedural fairness. Both forms of assistance are free of charge and available for victims of violent crimes, dangerous threats, sexual offenses, and related cases, underscoring Austria's commitment to victim protection.

2.2 Finland

Measure 1 – Multi-agency risk assessment conference

The Multi-agency risk assessment conference (MARAC) is a two-stage risk assessment method for repeated intimate partner violence. The method was developed in the UK. The purpose of the method is to systemically and multi-professionally improve victim's safety by information sharing, safety coordinating, and action planning that links with other relevant agencies. The method has been used in Finland for over ten years. A one-year pilot of the MARAC method was launched in Finland in 2010 and Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) was responsible for coordinating and evaluating the project. It was later continued as a project and since then developed into a permanent approach.

Measure 2 – Anchor Teams

The Anchor Teams project was launched in 2004. After successful pilot phases Anchor Teams are implemented nationwide with almost 40 locations. The purpose of the Anchor team model is to promote the well-being of children, adolescents, and families at an early

stage and to prevent crime. Locally, Anchor teams can also work on DV cases. Anchor work is done in multi-professional teams consisting of professionals from the police, social services, healthcare, and youth. The main task of Anchor Teams is the early intervention in the criminal behaviour of minors, comprehensive investigation of young persons' life situation and their need for help, referral to the right help and support, quick intervention in cases of DV, and increasing internal security through multi-professional cooperation. In recent years, the Finnish government has directed Anchor teams to focus increasingly on combating youth crime and radicalisation. The intervention in cases of DV is now limited to cases that involve minors who are in need of multi-professional support due to a difficult family situation.

Measure 3 – Medical risk screening tool for domestic violence and female genital mutilation

In order to strengthen the health care sectors capacity in detecting DV the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) recommends using a special questionnaire to detect domestic violence during pregnancy and early parenthood at maternity and child health clinics. These clinics, which are universal, free, and voluntary, are visited by nearly all expecting couples and families with young children, making them ideal for early intervention. The questionnaire is typically administered around mid-pregnancy, allowing parents to address topics beyond the initial excitement of having a baby. At this stage, public health nurses and/or midwives are more familiar with the families, fostering a supportive environment for discussions. THL also advises addressing female genital mutilation (FGM) in these clinics, particularly for families from cultures where FGM is practiced. Preventive measures begin during pregnancy by assessing the mother's FGM status, discussing parental attitudes, and evaluating risks to their daughters using a specialised threat assessment form. THL provides municipalities with detailed guidelines, including clinical pathways for addressing domestic violence and FGM. However, regional differences exist in how consistently these recommendations are implemented across clinics.

Measure 4 – Cultural Interpreter

In order to better address challenges arising from immigration Finland has implemented cultural interpreters. The aim of the cultural interpreter model is to help bridge cultural and language gaps, allowing vulnerable victims to access support services. Cultural interpreters are often NGO workers or volunteers, who themselves have a migration background and therefore possess the cultural knowledge and language skills that raise trust of victims with migration background and can help to reduce barriers for victims to disclose abuse. This kind

of peer-to-peer support for victims with a migration background aims at improving victims' capabilities to navigate DV support systems, strengthen the cooperation with authorities, educate victims that violence is a crime and encourage them to seek justice.

2.3 France

Measure 1 – Intervenants Sociaux en Commissariat et Gendarmerie

The initial role of French police social workers (ISCGs) was to ensure that information gathered by police officers concerning situations of social distress was effectively communicated to, and utilised by, social services. Embedding social workers within police stations appeared to be the only efficient method to facilitate the swift transfer of information to social services. The establishment of embedded social workers marked the first instance of collaboration between the law enforcement sector and the social sector in France—two professional spheres that historically harboured mutual distrust. The main tasks currently assigned to ISCGs are the identification of situations of social distress and to prevent their deterioration and escalation. Moreover, ISCGs are tasked with facilitating help-seeking behaviour and providing social support for victims when the victims report abuse, file a complaint, are granted protection, and when criminal investigations are initiated. They also inform victims of their rights and social assistance entitlements, and refer them to appropriate support services, shelters, and victim support associations. ISCGs also aim to establish a network of contacts within various local support services to facilitate emergency responses for victims in need.

Measure 2 – Judicial Task Forces to Combat Family Violence and Related Innovations

The Judicial Task Forces to Combat Family Violence was only recently introduced into the French judicial system and aims, via a range of specific measure, to combat high-impact domestic violence and improve victim protection. The most significant innovation, which forms the foundation for all others, is the establishment of judicial task forces dedicated to domestic and family violence (FV) within all courts and public prosecutors' offices. These FV Task Forces, along with the innovations they bring, are significantly transforming the philosophy and operational principles of the French judicial system. As their implementation began only in 2019, it is still too early to definitively assess their effectiveness in preventing high-impact domestic violence or protecting victims. However, they are already widely utilised across France, and some of their positive and negative impacts are becoming evident.

2.4 Germany

Measure 1 – The Violence Against Women Support Hotline

The Violence Against Women Support Hotline was launched in 2013. It is set up as an initial advice and referral service on the basis of the Support Hotline Act, which defines the framework conditions and tasks of the Support Hotline. It is the first nationwide counselling service in Germany that can be reached confidentially and free of charge (24/7 on 365 days). The Support Hotline is aimed at women affected by violence and offers them psychosocial counselling and crisis intervention. The hotline can also connect victims with local support facilities and provides help and information to anyone wishing to help a women affected by violence, such as relatives, friends, acquaintances, or neighbours. Moreover, professionals (health care workers, social worker, psychotherapists, police, youth welfare, etc.) can also contact the hotline to receive information on all topics relating to DV, from intervention planning and dealing with overwhelming emotions, to talking about experiences and answering questions about local support services.

Measure 2 – The Round Table Berlin

The “Round Table Berlin – health care for domestic and sexual violence” is a committee of the Berlin Senate Department for Health and Long-Term Care and is chaired by the Berlin Senator for Health. The project is designed, developed, and coordinated by S.I.G.N.A.L. e. V. It is committed to the implementation of the evidence-based WHO guidelines ‘Dealing with violence in couple relationships and sexual violence against women’ and their structural anchoring in hospitals, doctors’ surgeries and public health services. The main aims are to improve healthcare and support for those affected by domestic and sexualised violence, to strengthen the confidence of healthcare professionals in dealing with those affected and to promote and expand cross-sectoral, interdisciplinary cooperation. Therefore, the RTB seeks to improve the provision of first-line support (e.g., asking about intimate partner violence, information and further help, increasing safety and follow-up-care), develops DV guidelines for the various health care sectors, settings and professions and promotes the training of health care professional and the integration of DV programmes into curricula of healthcare professions. Furthermore, the RTB undertakes public relations works, undertakes research and data collection to review the implementation of the guidelines and assess the impact of measures to further develop health care services.

Measure 3 – The Marburg Model

The Marburg Model is an innovative approach to combating DV. It aims to improve outcomes of DV interventions by accelerating court proceedings and promoting coordinated efforts among stakeholders. It centres on close cooperation between law enforcement agencies, public prosecutors, courts, perpetrator intervention programmes and victim support organisations. The main goal of the Marburg Model is to establish a fast and effective cooperation between all stakeholder involved in cases of domestic violence in order to expedite court proceedings. Regular meetings and networking between police, prosecutors, and support services are essential components, ensuring a respectful and trusting environment. A key innovation is the role of the court assistant, who intervenes within five days of an incident and makes direct contact with the parties involved. Court assistants, thus take a proactive approach to support both victims and perpetrators. Their tasks include providing information, offering social and educational counselling, and working with all parties to develop solutions.

Measure 4 – The ‘StoP - neighbourhoods without partner violence’ project

"StoP - Neighbourhoods without Partner Violence" stands for a community-oriented concept for prevention and intervention in the area of partner violence. It is a network of district-based projects in various cities that are active under this name. It aims to strengthen people affected by DV and social networks in urban areas so that partner violence is no longer endured, kept secret, ignored or tolerated. The "StoP" project has a dual objective: first, to systematically develop and expand the willingness of people affected by violence and perpetrators of violence to come forward, and second to systematically develop and foster civil courage to intervene in DV cases in participating local community. In addition to removing the taboos surrounding partner violence and direct forms of support and intervention, increasing the willingness to intervene also includes strengthening the ability of community residents to engage with the issue in a wider social and socio-political context and to develop collective forms of action.

2.5 Spain

Measure 1 – Specialised training in gender-based violence for professionals

Spain has a solid legislative and public policy framework for the elimination of gender-based violence, which includes the obligation of public authorities to provide specialised and high-quality trainings for professionals. The aim of this legal framework is to provide qualified

training to professionals from various disciplines, including the legal, social, health, education and media sector, to intervene, in a coordinated and multidisciplinary manner, in the field of violence against women. Such specialised training courses have been implemented mainly through university postgraduate programs and ongoing training programs offered by public and private institutions, as well as professional associations. These programs intend to provide professionals with the necessary skills to design, plan, manage, implement and assess support, psychosocial, educational, socio-sanitary and/or legal interventions, from a holistic view which considers the multiple factors that affect the needs of women and their context.

Measure 2 – The Women's Houses movement

The Women's Houses emerged from the collaboration between public institutions and citizens. Women's Houses have been established and developed at the municipal or county level through locally driven participatory processes, tailored to the specific needs and characteristics of each municipality. Unlike other municipal facilities, citizens have been actively involved in defining all aspects of these projects, including the objectives, values, principles, characteristics, and management models of the houses. This approach has fostered future collaboration and set a clear precedent for implementing public policies effectively. Women's Houses aim to empower women and promote gender equality through various initiatives. They enhance feminist awareness, implement feminist actions, and deepen the understanding of gender-based violence. These centres provide specific guidance to help women overcome such situations and encourage their active participation in socio-political spheres. By fostering gender equality, they create inclusive spaces for individuals, groups, and associations advocating for equality. Women's Houses serve as hubs for support, education, and advocacy, ensuring women have the tools and opportunities to address challenges and contribute meaningfully to society while advancing the principles of equality and inclusion.

Measure 3 – Gipuzkoa's Provincial Council Social Services' Attention Model for Gender-Based Violence

The Provincial Councils of the Basque Country—Bizkaia, Araba, and Gipuzkoa—are administrative boards coordinated by the autonomous Basque Government and operating under the Statutes of Gernika. In this framework, social services and the promotion of social welfare are competencies transferred to both City and Provincial Councils. This structure

supports proximity, personalisation of care, and the decentralisation of resources and services. The Gipuzkoa Provincial Council has taken significant steps to improve the response to gender-based violence against women. A key initiative was the creation of AMUUM, a working group led by the Social Inclusion and Attention to Women Victims of Gender-Based Violence Service. The AMUUM reviewed DV intervention models and practices to develop recommendations for enhancing services. These recommendations align with gender-perspective principles drawn from international, national, and regional gender-based violence frameworks. The aim is to standardise quality across services and ensure a coherent, value-driven response to victims' needs. The guidelines focus on translating these principles into actionable practices, promoting micro-level service improvements, and steering services toward excellence. Ultimately, the measure seeks to provide consistent, high-quality support for victims of gender-based violence.

Measure 4 – GAMA (Abuse Care Group) of the Valencia Local Police (PLV)

The GAMA is a police intervention group that was developed to act exclusively for the protection of victims of gender and domestic violence. The implementation of the GAMA marked a turning point in DV police interventions, both in terms of the quantitative results of the work carried out by the team, as well as a qualitative leap that has led to a substantial improvement in the quality, effectiveness and efficiency of the service provided to victims under protection. Over the years, GAMA has developed into a specialised unit dedicated to offering comprehensive assistance to victims. Operating within a collaborative network of support services, the unit works closely with various organisations and institutions. This ensures that victims are provided with timely and effective support.

3. Critical Enablers of DV policy implementation

The following section describes the factors identified as crucial for the successful implementation of DV policies. As mentioned above, these factors can be categorised as either external or internal. External factors delineate the framework conditions that must be in place for the implementation of a measure to succeed. These include, in particular, a legal basis, but also political or civil society support. Internal factors, in contrast, describe how the measure must be ‘designed’ in order to be effectively implemented.

3.1 External factors

Overall, the analysis shows that one of the most important factors driving the implementation of DV measures is to establish a legal basis. Almost all of the measures presented in the national reports are based on legal provisions. Such provisions can be *(1) narrow and specifically defined*, as is the case for the German DV Helpline, which was established by a dedicated legal act. In just 8 paragraphs and less than 500 words, this legal act regulates the central tasks, the group of addressees, availability as well as questions of public relations and the evaluation of the hotline. Certain details, such as the qualifications required of hotline staff, are left to the practical assessment of the operator. Besides such specific laws, legal regulations can also set out *(2) comprehensive principles that frame the conditions for a range of various measures across different institutions and settings*. This is, for example, the case with the Spanish legislation on the elimination of gender-based violence, which across several different acts also regulates public authorities’ responsibilities to provide specialised and high-quality trainings for professionals¹. In contrast to the legal definition of specific services, the focus here is on formulating framework conditions, such as by defining general objectives, the target audience, assigning responsibility for implementation, setting a time frame and resolving financing aspects. Other legal measures, such as the Judicial Task Forces to Combat Family Violence in France, represent a *(3) combination, involving both the establishment of specific procedures and the prescription of general principles*.

When developing measures for the protection of victims, political decision-makers can choose between these three forms of legal regulation. A particular advantage of very narrow on concrete legal stipulations, like in the case of the German support hotline, is that the

¹ Organic Law 1/2004 on Comprehensive Protection Measures against Gender-Based Violence; the Organic Law 3/2007 for the Effective Equality of Women and Men; Law 14/2011 on Science, Technology and Innovation; Royal Decree 1393/2007; Organic Law 2/2023 on the University System.

envisaged measure is comparatively easy to implement (e.g., because further legal interpretation is hardly to be expected) and to evaluate. The successful adoption of comprehensive legal frameworks to improve protection against violence is particularly advisable when systemic and structural changes are the goal. However, the successful implementation of comprehensive measures, such as the legally required specialised training in the field of gender-based violence at Spanish universities, can heavily depend on another external factor, namely the *existence of a corresponding socio-political orientation*. As the Spanish example shows, the successful implementation of legally stipulation training was significantly driven by academic feminism, which has a 50-year tradition in Spanish universities. Finally, it is crucial to recognise that in all three cases. (i.e., task-specific legal regulations, general legal frameworks and the combination of both) the respective legalisation leaves the “fine-tuning” of the practical implementation and execution of the legal requirement to the responsible actors. Ideally these responsible actors are closely involved in the design and development of the regulation.

The second external factor for the successful implementation of DV policies is that of *political support*. While political support for a particular issue may often be expressed by introducing legal measures, it is not always necessary or advantageous to aim for the comparatively high standard of legal regulations. Instead, political support can be expressed symbolically and/or via policy efforts. One example of this comes from the development of women's shelters in Austria. Their historical development shows the great importance of political support in two ways. First, *political allies were needed to raise the project to the level of public-political discourse and to keep it there*. Second, the project required *political representation*, which can be achieved, for example, by political actors taking on representative functions in the project. In the case of the founding of the first women's shelter in Austria, this was accomplished by filling the shelter association's supervisory board, with ‘honourable personalities’ from politics and society. In addition to its representative function, political support is an important factor for the successful implementation of victim protection measures because it can *facilitate the acquisition of funding*. In contrast to legal regulations, political support also allows for a continuous balancing of the various perspectives. While the enactment of laws can mark the preliminary end of political attention, endeavours and efforts (after all, implementation is usually the responsibility of executive bodies such as authorities and not the legislature), ongoing participation of political actors can *strengthen collaboration between all stakeholders* and foster acceptance and effectiveness among various groups.

Equally effective, however, can be the *support and recognition of an intervention by non-governmental public institutions* (e.g., universities) *and civil society actors*, like NGOs. Indeed, it may even be advantageous for an intervention to be primarily associated with private and civil society initiatives, because state institutions do not always enjoy the full trust of those affected. Examples of this are again the women's shelter movements in Spain and Austria, which, although partly supported by public authorities or political actors, were mainly driven by grassroots feminist movements. In these cases, the success in implementation is based on the fact that women who themselves were affected by violence worked on the implementation of the measure. Such engagement is typically associated with a high degree of intrinsic motivation, while economic or political motives, for example, are of little importance.

Both factors, i.e., legal foundations and political or civil support, are also important because they are closely linked to the third external factor for successful implementation, namely *sufficient and clearly regulated funding*. While the aspect of sufficient funding is self-explanatory as an important implementation factor, the second point requires further explanation. A clear financing regulation includes the unambiguous determination of who provides how much money, for how long, on what basis (e.g., legally stipulated or as a donation), how this money is to be used, what happens to surplus funds, what documentation requirements exist, and whether certain other conditions (e.g., from whom else money can be obtained) are associated with it. Such clarifications are particularly necessary for sustainable implementation.

At least as important as the factors mentioned above is the fact that many of the measures mentioned in the country reports emerged from *feminist-motivated, bottom-up efforts*. These measures thus predate political or legal endorsement and are closely linked to civil society support for violence protection measures. The importance of a feminist orientation and perspective for the development and implementation of victim protection measures can hardly be overestimated. Some of the most important measures, such as women's shelters, violence protection laws and comprehensive counselling services, were initiated, driven and/or implemented by groups of women who opposed the sexist and patriarchal structures of societies. These include, for example, the Women's Shelter in Austria, the Women's Houses in Spain, and the StoP project in Germany and Austria. Without these feminist principles, which are shared by many practitioners, be it in social work, legal or health-related

victim support, it would hardly be possible to implement a variety of measures. As a result, the state would not be able to adequately fulfil its duty to protect people, especially women from violence. Therefore, policy makers should be more receptive to initiatives and projects that demonstrate such a critical attitude and have emerged from bottom-up efforts.

3.2 Internal factors

In addition to these external factors that drive the implementation of measures, there are a number of internal factors that need to be considered when designing the content and structure of any measure. Before a comprehensive introduction of a DV-policy measure takes place, it is important to *plan an extended pilot phase* that ideally involves all affected stakeholders. The added value of such a step can be seen, for example, in the MARACs in Finland, the “StoP” project from Germany or the violence protection centres in Austria, which all included (scientifically) monitored pilot phase. Such piloting phases enable the refinement of strategies and adaptation to the needs of practitioners and victims. Moreover, they can help identify potential risks and vulnerabilities that are difficult to foresee, allowing negative consequences to be addressed and minimised early on. This is especially important to ensure that a programme is both effective and safe, when working with vulnerable populations. In addition, such a pilot phase provides information on the scalability of a measure by gaining initial insights into existing demand and associated resource requirements.

Whether *measures are designed to be integrable into existing (victim protection and/or social) structures*, constitutes another positive factor for a successful implementation. While this may not be possible or necessary for all measures, the experiences from France with the integration of social workers into the police force or the Finnish Anchor Teams show the benefits of such an approach. In both cases, the integration of social work and police structures lowers the threshold for contact and mutual support beyond the core tasks of the stakeholders. Particularly, such integration reduces the threshold for mutual exchange if both organisational and local integration is achieved, i.e., the participating actors share office space, for example. For the exchange of information and the development of a trusting-relationship face-to-face exchange is typically preferred over telephone or email exchange. Integration of different stakeholders directly involved in the measure is thus conducive to the implementation of victim protection measures. Measures should also be embedded within local communities, for example by establishing contact with local associations, religious groups or social services provided by NGOs. In this way, the targeted measures can be

tailored to fit local conditions and needs. A prime example of this is certainly the 'StoP' project, which aims to build and embed violence and victim protection in local-community structures. Consequently, policy makers should consider the diversity of different social settings when developing interventions. For example, it can make a significant difference whether community-based interventions are to be implemented in urban neighbourhoods that tend to be characterised by anonymity, or in rural communities where it may be necessary to provide opportunities for anonymity.

Another factor that drives the implementation of measures is the *peer-to-peer communication of concepts and content*. In fields like medicine, police work, and social work, trust in the skills and training of professionals from other sectors is not always automatic. This lack of trust may sometimes stem from prejudice but can also be to the understandable perception that people outside a profession lack the same level of knowledge and practical experience in a given field as those within it. Therefore, a peer-to-peer approach is better suited for creating accessible and effective collaboration. The Round Table Berlin (RTB), for example, which is working on the implementation of victim protection measures in the medical field, shows how important such a conceptual structure is for successful implementation. The RTB involves various medical professions in the overall development of their concepts and trainings, which improves the implementation of these guidelines and training offers, because they are tailored to the needs and practices of the various medical specialities. Consequently, it is more likely that results will be accepted by the respective disciplines and organisations. In addition to specific professional contexts, peer-to-peer development, support and training are also essential for victim support and counselling programmes. This is evident in the development of women's shelters, as described in the Spanish and Austrian contexts. In both cases, it was coalitions of women that created spaces for the protection and the empowerment of women. Whilst in both cases, initiatives were dependent on the support of political or public partners, they were essentially bottom-up and peer-to-peer endeavours, distinct from state interventions against domestic violence. Thus, their success stems from their bottom-up and peer-to-peer approach.

Finally, two further important factors should be mentioned, even if they are general. First, *measures should always include the continuous assessment and evaluation of the needs and experiences of service users and providers*, e.g., through dedicated surveys or scientific evaluation. Such continuous assessments provide the information basis for the ongoing

improvement of measures, as well as, in the case of changes in the field, their rapid adaptation to the changing needs of victims and practitioners. Closely related to this is the collection of data on the organisation's own activities. The importance of this was highlighted in almost all of the analysed measures (e.g., keeping records of the services provided, such as the number of counselling sessions), as well as effective information management and information processing. This is especially necessary and beneficial for multi-agency interventions, as their success heavily depends upon the ability to share information about a specific case. Second, *measures should always be combined with regular training and education programmes on the topic of protection against violence*. This is crucial because it is an effective way to keep staff up to date in the face of today's complex intervention systems and to ensure that the latest research findings on domestic violence can be integrated into the measures. This way, the sustainable operation of intervention can be supported.

4. Critical Enablers for the assessment of the success of victim protection measures

When analysing the factors that can be employed to assess and evaluate the effectiveness of victim protection measures, it is also possible to distinguish between two categories. First, those criteria that provide information about the impact of the measure, for example, the extent to which a victim protection measure is utilised over time. Second, we have identified criteria that can help to assess the quality of the measure in terms of content. This includes, for example, whether the measure involves networking several front-line responders.

4.1 Impact related assessment criteria

One of the most important criteria for assessing the effectiveness of victim protection measures is the *availability of 'empirical evidence'*. Almost all measures analysed by the partners refer to empirical evidence as an essential indicator for assessing the effectiveness of a DV policy measure. There are two sources of empirical evidence' policy makers and practitioner can draw on to assess the impact of a measure. First, *data provided in activity reports and work documentation of front-line responders* that, for example, show a continuous increase over the years in the usage or application of a measure. This can, for example, include the number of counselling sessions offered by hotlines and victim protection organisations or the number of undertaken/requested victim protection measures, such as restraining orders or MARACs. As these figures present the utilisation of a measure, they provide a solid basis for mapping developments in the 'demand' for certain support or protection interventions. Furthermore, higher rates of utilisation can be considered as an increase in public awareness. However, a disadvantage is the fact that such 'bare figures' only provide limited information about the quality of a measure. Likewise, such figures by themselves do not provide an explanation as to why, for example, there is an increase or decrease in requests for counselling. The second type of empirical evidence that can be drawn on to assess a DV policy measures addresses this gap: It includes *scientific publications or evaluations of measures/activities* commissioned by international organisations, public authorities, NGOs or even the organisations implementing the measures. For policy and other decision-makers, this means that one important way to determine the effectiveness of an intervention is to monitor or commission the collection of its utilisation rates or impact. Here the focus can be on assessing the individual uptake rates of an intervention, as well as user and practitioner experience with the measure. The most

important dimension of such impact-evaluation is the feedback from the target group of the measure, i.e., whether for example victims of domestic violence report an improvement in their situation and/or the stakeholders involved in the measure consider that the intended effect of the measure has been achieved. Only in this way can the possible relation between the measure and its goal be estimated.

Another factor in analysing the performance of a policy measure is the degree to which a measure has gained *the trust of public authorities and/or third-party organisations* over the course of its implementation. Here, two indicators stand out in particular. The first is whether and to what extent measures have a legal basis and are experiencing continuous expansion and further development. The second is the extent to which such measures receive long-term funding. Both indicators suggest that the legislator and/or funding bodies recognise the necessity and benefit of the measure and acknowledge its long-term use. Among the measures analysed by the partners, and standing out in the context, are the Austrian entry and approach ban, the French model of 'Embedded Social Workers' (ISCG) and the Finnish Anchor Teams. All three measures are long-term and comprehensive victim protection measures that have been expanded over the course of their implementation and enjoy a high level of public confidence in containing domestic violence. For policy makers aiming to implement a comparable intervention, this is a particularly useful criterion for evaluating measures in other countries.

The *possibility of low-threshold national transferability and its implementation in different national contexts* is another indicator to assess the potential of measures. One example is the StoP violence protection project. StoP is a bottom-up community project which was developed in Germany. It has already been expanded to Austria and is currently being evaluated for implementation in France, Belgium, the Czech Republic and Romania. Other examples of such measures are the MARAC interventions, and the cultural interpreter analysed in the Finnish report. The decisive factor for considering transnational transferability and implementation as an evaluation criterion is that this awards the measure a high degree of flexibility and adaptability, both of which are also central aspects of the successful implementation of measures.

4.2 Design-related assessment criteria

One of the most important design-related criteria is that measures take a *cross-organisational and cross-agency approach*, i.e., a so-called 'one-stop shop' model. Examples of this are the

Marburg Model in Germany, the Anchor Teams in Finland, the ISCG in France, the Abuse Care Group (GAMA) of the Local Police in Valencia or the violence protection centres in Austria. Such networked approaches offer advantages for victims as well as for the participating organisations and authorities. For the latter, for example, 'operational effectiveness' is improved through the exchange of information. Likewise, the introduction of different expert perspectives and the consolidation of information from various sources increases the effectiveness of the response. Moreover, networked measures enable a more precise assessment of a case, since a concrete threat and the appropriate set of measures for a victim can often be best provided through a multi-perspective analysis. For example, while the police are very effective at ensuring immediate safety in dangerous situations, victim support organisations are better equipped to provide psycho-social support to victims. Similarly, medical or social service partners are able to identify medical or material/financial risks, respectively. Such long-term networked collaboration can also lead to a mutual recognition of organisational responsibilities and perspectives. In this way, a network-approach can help to overcome professional and organisational knowledge silos, and therefore bridge differences in perspectives. For the involved organisations, such an approach can contribute to mutual reassurance, advice and guidance in relation to the various areas of expertise. For victims, such a model can make it easier to get in touch with the various organisations, which reduces their overall burden and increases the likelihood of them remaining in the support system. It also makes it easier to support victims who suffer from a combination of problems, such as domestic violence, drug abuse and mental illness. It is therefore generally advisable for policy makers to consider a co-operative, multi-agency framework when developing DP measures. Not all possible organisations working on victim protection need to be involved in every measure, as this can increase bureaucratic work (e.g. due to changing information obligations) and reduce the effectiveness of cooperation and intervention. To determine who should ultimately collaborate as part of an intervention, an extensive pilot phase is advisable

The practical effectiveness of many of the cited interventions also stems from the proactive approach. In Austria, for example, if the police impose an entry and approach ban, they will inform the regionally responsible violence protection centre. The centre then actively contacts the victim by telephone. This way, victims who would otherwise not contact victim protection organisations are reached. Even more wide-reaching are the various forms of screening tools that can be used in the health sector (see the corresponding analysis in the Finnish report).

These contribute to the implementation of DV policies by reaching a very broad segment of the population, especially when they are used in the context of care and treatment in maternity and child health clinics. Second, they also reach those groups and individuals who otherwise hardly come into contact with DV support and counselling services.

Another criterion, which is also closely linked to the concept of the network approach, is that measures, such as the ‘cultural translator’ in Finland or the FV Task Forces in France, rely on a *strict division of labour to effectively relieve the burden on involved stakeholders* and practitioners. Regarding the relieving of workload, the judicial assistants employed in the context of the FV Task Forces in France, for example, can support judges at the family court by preparing certain judicial documents like protection order requests or criminal settlement orders. Judicial assistants employed at the prosecutor’s office in turn can compensate for the lack of time magistrates often have to conduct in-depth examinations of cases involving DV. In order to effectively fulfil such roles, the areas of work, tasks and responsibilities must be organised in such a way that duplication, overlap or even competing work are avoided. Therefore, it is necessary that each actor’s role within a given DV measure is tailored to fulfil clearly defined functions, such as acting as a point of contact for initial advice and referral, or as a provider of long-term support. An example of such a clear division is provided by the ISCG in France. There, one important factor in the success of the programme is the strict delineation of work between police officers and social workers. The latter are prohibited from interfering in police activities, particularly criminal investigations. Instead, they provide social support to victims, allowing police officers to focus entirely on indispensable police work.

For measures that are aimed directly at victims there are also a number of criteria that characterise effective and successful victim protection measures. Generally, measures that aim to support victims of domestic violence are particularly effective if they have a low threshold for access. This includes that the measure should be free of charge, or, as is the case with emergency accommodation or women’s shelters in Austria, only involve very low costs depending on the financial situation of the victims. For (initial) counselling services, it is also important that these should be anonymous, confidential and without any documentation of personal information being requirement. These services should also have multiple forms of access, e.g., face-to-face, telephone, live-chat or email counselling. It is also essential that counselling services are multilingual, and ideally, as the example of the helpline from Germany and that of Cultural Interpreters from Finland show, make sure that counsellors

from different ethnic and cultural backgrounds are available. The operating and availability times of counselling services should be guaranteed around the clock. If this is not possible, these times should be spread out over the week and daytime. This ensures that opening times are compatible with people's various work or caregiving obligations. An example that illustrates this necessity particularly well comes from the German helpline, where an analysis of the use of the counselling service shows that 40 percent of requests come in between 6 p.m. and 8 a.m., when other institutions are generally not available.

Intervention measures initiated by authorities, public institutions or victim protection organisations are most effective if they are *administered fast, early* (e.g. via appropriate screening procedures in clinics, as described in the Finnish report) *and include a coordinated approach between different front-line responders*. This is the case with the Austrian entry and approach ban, the GAMA unit in Spain, the Finnish Anchor Teams or the French FTV Task Force. Such interventions usually take a holistic approach, targeting both the offender, for example by ordering participation in an offender programme, and the victim, by initiating protective measures while providing psychosocial interventions. The French FV Task Force for example include the instalment of judicial assistants who support court magistrates, personalised victim assessments (EVVI), improved risk detection tools, Anti-Approach Bracelets (BAR), emergency tracks within jurisdictions, and a feedback process (RETEX) for evaluating systemic failures following DV related homicides. Another important criterion is that such measures have a high degree of individualisation. They should be adaptable to the respective situation, by taking into account the different social and economic circumstances of the victims, as well as diverse cultural and ethnic backgrounds. They must also offer appropriate support when children are involved or when victims suffer from addictions or mental disorders.

The most important criterion therefore is that DV interventions follow a victim-centred-approach. Measures aimed at victims must be voluntary in principle, and the needs and wishes of victims must take priority. Otherwise, there is a risk that the interventions will be perceived as paternalistic. This can lead to victims being discouraged and diminish trust in the system. To be effective and successful, interventions should instead be designed to expand victims' options for action and decision-making, increase their self-efficacy and give them back control over their own lives.

5. Developing the SISPO-Framework

So far, the present report summarised the factors characterising successful and sustainable implementation as well as the factors characterising successful DV policies and measures. Based on the comparison of a total of 18 DV policy measures from five different countries, we identified for both, implementation and performance of DV measures, nine critical enablers each.

Table 1 shows the critical enablers for the successful implementation of DV measures, and Table 2 provides an overview of the critical enablers for successful performance. Some of these critical enablers identified are of a general nature, i.e., they are factors that are also, but not specifically, important and related to the implementation of victim protection measures. These include, for example, the establishment of a legal framework, political/civil society support or the provision of sufficient funding. Similarly, among the critical enablers for assessing successful performance of DV intervention we found factors, that can be considered general indicators for measuring the effectiveness of a policy measure. This includes the evidence-based-monitoring, long-term investments or the clear division of labour and responsibilities. However, the analysis also highlights some critical enablers that are specifically related to and highly important for victim protection measures. These include the adaptation of a feminist perspective, the victim-centred perspective, a proactive and holistic approach, peer-to-peer delivery, the low threshold service accessibility and the ‘one-stop shop’ concept. It is also important to emphasise that some factors are closely linked to each other, e.g., the factors “Legal Framework”, “Funding and Funding Guidelines” and “Political/Civil Society Support” or the “One-Stop-Shop” concept and the “Victim-Centred Approach”. This is important to consider when analysing, planning and designing victim protection measures, because the full effect of an intervention may only unfold when certain factors are combined. Yet, for a measure to be successfully implemented and to be effective in practice, not all ‘critical enablers’ have to be met. However, this still poses the question of which of these ‘critical enablers’ policy makers and practitioners, but also scientific analyses of DV intervention, should pay attention to. To this end, we have systematised our findings in the SISPO Concept Framework. SISPO stands for **S**ocietal Foundation, **I**mplementation Pathways, **S**ervice Design, **P**ractical Environment and **O**ngoing Development. These are also the five central cornerstones that every DIV intervention should address. Table 3 represent the conceptual framework.

Table 1. Critical Enablers for Successful Implementation

Critical Enablers of DV Policy Implementation		
Category	Factor	Description
External Factors	Legal Basis	Measures should have a clear legal foundation, either through highly task-specific regulations, general legal frameworks, or a combination of both.
	Political/Civil Society Support	Sustained political support ensures resources, representation, and continuous collaboration among stakeholders and engagement of NGOs and grassroots initiatives bring intrinsic motivation and foster trust among stakeholders and target group.
	Adequate and Clear Funding	Explicit financing regulations covering sources, allocation, duration, and conditions.
	Feminist Perspective	Shared principle among many stakeholders and attitudinal/motivational prerequisite for many victim protection measures
Internal Factors	Pilot Programs	Testing measures through pilot phases helps refine strategies, identify risks, and assess scalability.
	Integration of Services	Embedding measures into existing local structures or creating cross-sector collaboration (e.g., police-social work integration) enhances effectiveness.
	Peer-to-Peer Delivery	Trust-building and knowledge-sharing between professionals and stakeholders foster higher acceptance and impact.
	Continuous assessment	Regular evaluations of the measures provide indicators for the continuous user-related adaptation of measures.
	Continuous Training	Ensures that staff stay up to date regarding the changing best practices, legal regulations etc

Table 2. Critical Enablers for Successful Performance

Critical Enablers for the Assessment of Victim Protection Measures		
Category	Factor	Description
Impact-Factors	Evidence-Based Monitoring	Data collection on service use and outcomes is vital for assessing effectiveness and informing improvements.
	Long-term Investments	Continuous expansion, funding and legal development signal public trust in a measure.
	Cross-National Transferability	Signals high degree of flexibility and adaptability.
Design Factors	One-Stop-Shop Design	Bridges organisational knowledge silos, fosters cross-organisation trust and understanding and increases the likelihood of victims remaining in the support system.
	Proactive Approach	Increases the chances of reaching and engaging victims, especially 'hard-to-reach' groups.
	Clear Division of Labour and Responsibilities	Avoids duplication of work, overlaps or even competing activities and enables the different actors in the cooperation network to concentrate on their main areas of responsibility.
	Low-Threshold Service Accessibility	Increases first-time response rate and reduces negative support seeking experience
	Victim-Centred Approach	Encourages victims, increases trust in system, keeps victims in support network
	Holistic Intervention Design	Victims and perpetrators must be included, and rapid protective measures and long-term support measures as well as involvement of different stakeholders (police, social workers, medical services, judicial services etc)

At the present stage, the SISPO framework is still in a conceptual phase, as it has not yet been scientifically evaluated. However, it is planned to submit the concept as a paper to peer-reviewed journals and present it at scientific conferences. Consequently, the following descriptions are preliminary and subject to change. Column 1 of the SISPO Framework lists the conceptual cornerstones that must be considered when planning or analysing any DV intervention. Each of these cornerstones consists of several ‘critical enablers’ that we identified in the previous analysis. These are listed in column two under ‘considerable factors’. Column three lists a series of key questions that arise in connection with the respective ‘considerable factor’. This list is demonstrative and can be further expanded.

The cornerstone “**Societal Foundation**” includes the legal, political, and financial prerequisites for domestic violence interventions. The ‘considerable factors’ summarised here are particularly important to regard when implementing DV interventions. Measures that do not include any of the four listed factors may be difficult to implement, especially in the long term. The ‘considerable factor’ ‘feminist perspective’ represents a cross-cutting factor. Regardless of any underlying legal regulations, political/civil society support or financing structure, it seems to be advantageous for measures to include or draw on such a perspective. The main reason for this is that many victim protection measures are carried out by people, especially women, who have a feminist stance. The second cornerstone “**Implementation Pathways**” focuses on practical strategies for the actual implementation of interventions. It emphasises the benefits of structured pilot programs, the integration of a new intervention into existing service structures and the peer-to-peer delivery of interventions. Particularly relevant here is the integration of a new measure into existing structures. This not only allows existing expertise and resources (e.g., infrastructure) to be utilised, but also ensures that a measure is integrated into an already operating system. Thereby, the measure can become known more quickly and receive a certain amount of trust in advance. The cornerstone “**Service Design**” encompasses the factors that were identified as being highly important for the effective design of a measure. These include, in particular, a victim-centred, low-threshold and proactive approach, with these three factors being closely linked. Also, the one-stop-shop principle and the holistic design of the measures are essential and conceptually interconnected factors. Depending on the main objective of an intervention, one of these two combinations, i.e., a victim-centred, low-threshold and proactive approach or a holistically designed one-stop-shop concept should form the core of any intervention. Depending on the sector and objective of the intervention, it is necessary to prioritise one of

these two combinations. For example, a holistic and one-stop-shop intervention design is appropriate for measures that primarily aim to intervene and quickly stop violence, such as the entry and approach ban in Austria, which combines police intervention, violence prevention sessions with the perpetrator and the active approach to the victim by violence protection centres. Longer-term follow-up measures, in contrast, which aim to empower victims, enable them to permanently separate from their violent partner and/or to take legal action, must be designed to be primarily victim-centred and easily accessible (for example, by being easily compatible with the professional and social circumstances of victims). Ideally, however, interventions are designed in such a way that a combination of all five factors is achieved. The fourth cornerstone, “**Practical Environment**”, summarises factors that serve to assess the feasibility of an intervention with regard to practical circumstances. Particular attention should be paid to whether an intervention that is being considered for expansion, for example, has a high level of trust. These aspects can be analysed relatively easily, even in the cases where measures implemented in other countries are considered. In this regard, it is also valuable to consider how many other countries have implemented the same measure, and what similarities and differences can be observed. The final cornerstone, “**Ongoing Development**”, emphasises the importance of data-based monitoring and ongoing adaptation of interventions, as well as the need for professional capacity building and knowledge sharing. Thus, the factors summarised under this cornerstone are important to consider in order to verify whether interventions are designed in such a way that they can adapt to changing challenges, incorporate the latest scientific insights and therefore contribute to the long-term provision of care for victims and the prevention of domestic violence.

Table 3. SISPO Framework for DV Interventions

SISPO – A Conceptual Framework for Domestic Violence Interventions		
Conceptual Cornerstones	Considerable Factors	Related Decision-Making Questions
Societal Foundation	Legal Basis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is there a substantive reason for a measure to be implemented without a legal basis? - What is the scope of the legal issues being regulated (small scale vs. structural solution)? - Can the measure be included in / or linked to existing legislation?
	Political/Civil Society Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What roles can/should political actors play? - What role can/should civil society support play? - Is representative or involved support required, or both?
	Adequate and Clear Funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Who is responsible for funding? - What activities will be funded? - How long are the funding periods? - What happens to surplus funds? - What are the documentation requirements?
	Feminist Perspective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the measure comply with feminist principles? - Does the measure include intersectional dimensions? - Are there any feminist grassroots projects that the intervention could build on?
Implementation Pathways	Pilot Programs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the measure target vulnerable or hard to reach groups? - What risks or challenges should be tested during pilot phases? - What are the indicators of a successful pilot phase?
	Integration of Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can a planned service be integrated into existing structures? - Which stakeholder need to be involved in the service integration? - Is there a reason for the intervention to be a "stand-alone" measure?
	Peer-to-Peer Delivery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which professional actors are involved in the implementation of the measure? - Which modes of training already exist in this field? - What does the trainer culture in this field look like?
Service Design	One-Stop-Shop Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can victims access all potential support services via a single point of contact? - How are public agencies and civil society/independent support services linked?
	Proactive Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the measure provide for automatic contact with the victim? - Does the measure provide for automatic obligations for offenders? - Is active information sharing between stakeholders planned?
	Clear Division of Labour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What mechanisms can prevent duplication of effort or conflict between stakeholders? - Are roles and responsibilities clearly defined among all service providers and stakeholders?
	Low-Threshold Service Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the key aspects concerning accessibility and availability of the planned service (e.g. regional availability, opening hours)? - Who is the target group, and which psychological/economic/cultural/social circumstances should be taken into account? - In addition to the primary access option (e.g. telephone support), are other options (e.g. email or live chat) also provided?
	Victim-Centred Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are victim needs included in the design of the measure? - Are there mechanisms to obtain and incorporate feedback from victims? - Does the measure contain aspects that involve obligations directly/indirectly affecting the victim? - Is the measure designed to empower victims and respecting their autonomy?
	Holistic Intervention Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is the measure aimed at victims and offenders? - Does the intervention include immediate and long-term support? - Are different sectors (police, health services, victim support, etc.) involved? - Are legal, psychological and social measures integrated into the intervention alongside security police measures?
Practical Environment	Trusted Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How long does the intervention exist? - Has the measure been continuously developed? - Has the intervention been continuously funded? - Is there a legal basis? - Is there political or civil society support?
	Cross-National Transferability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has the measure been implemented internationally? - Has the measure been implemented in different countries in a relatively consistent or very inconsistent manner? - Are there other countries planning to introduce the intervention?
Ongoing Development	Continuous Assessment and Evidence-Based Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are there activity reports by the responsible organisations? - Is there scientific evidence regarding the success of the measure? - Has quantitative and qualitative evidence been gathered?
	Continuous Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are there up-to-date training programmes related to the measure? - Are there mandatory or only voluntary training/further education programmes? - Are training and further education part of the employment conditions?

6. Conclusion

The findings of this report can be used as a basis for the (further) development and design, but also for the evaluation of victim protection measures. It should be noted that the report focuses on the design of victim-centred measures. Perpetrator-focused measures are not covered. The following approach is recommended for the practical application of the SISPO framework. As a first step, the SISPO framework can be used as a kind of checklist when developing a measure, by going through the individual conceptual cornerstones and the considerable factors summarised under them. In doing so, the measure in question should address each of the five cornerstones by including at least one of the considerable factors. For the cornerstones Implementation Pathway and Service Design, we recommend including at least two of the considerable factors. This way, it can be ensured that a given measure conceptually fulfils the minimum requirements for an implementable and conceptually feasible intervention. The example questions in column three can be used as a stimulus for brainstorming and discussion. If additional guidance and clarification is needed or desired for certain considerable factors, their detailed descriptions in sections 3 and 4 can be consulted. If, beyond that, specific practical examples are needed, for example to better understand how a holistic approach is realised in an already implemented intervention, the 200-page detailed analysis of 18 measures in the appendix is highly recommended.

Finally, it should be noted that the SISPO framework developed here is a conceptual tool. It is therefore neither intended nor possible to actually predict the success of an intervention in practice. Ultimately, such a prediction depends on factors that cannot be meaningfully included in a conceptual framework for developing or analysing measures, such as the motivation of those applying a measure, the behaviour of victims/perpetrators or the way in which domestic violence is dealt with in society as a whole (e.g., whether the topic is highly taboo or publicly discussed). The reason such factors were not included in the framework is that, while they all affect the success and feasible form of an intervention, they have very different impacts depending on the type of intervention (e.g., police interventions, even if well designed, are likely to have little impact in a society where domestic violence is seen as a private matter, while anonymous counselling or women's shelters may be more effective). It is therefore difficult to generalise the factors in terms of design.

Appendix

Appendix 1. Methodology

Overall methodology

The aim of Task 4.1 is to identify those factors (termed critical policy enablers) that extend across specific nationally successful or innovative victim services (termed solutions) and enable the implementation of DV policy-measures and characterise their effective design and structure. Therefore, the following methodological guideline was developed.

At first, **contributing partners were asked to identify and describe solutions** which have proven to be “the most relevant” in preventing or protecting victims from violence. Relevance was constructed along five questions:

- What are the most widely employed solutions?
- What are the most established solutions across different stakeholder groups?
- What are the most recently developed or novel solutions?
- What are the best solutions for reaching new victim groups?
- What are the most effective solutions?

To justify the choice of solutions, in addition to their own expertise in the respective national context, the selection and descriptions were based on empirical findings from previous IMPRODOVA and IMPROVE research activities and additional, specifically conducted desk research.

In a second step, **partners were tasked to justify their selections** and in doing so, to identify factors which contribute to the relevance of a given solutions. While it was important to the analysis that justifications were open ended, guidance was given to ensure that justifications followed a similar structure, in order for the comparative analysis to be carried out. Hence, five guiding questions were formulated:

- What were the conditions and decisive factors for the **successful implementation** of the solution?
- How relevant is the solution in practice? This included **how effective** the solution is in prohibiting or protecting against domestic violence.
- What **evidence or data** supports the relevance of the solutions?
- Did the solution align with, or complement, existing policies, regulations, strategies, or the practice of actors in the field?

- Are there **unintended consequences** or risks associated with implementing the solution?

The third methodological step was the comparative analysis of all national reports provided by the partners, both the descriptions and, more importantly, the justifications. The comparative analysis was dedicated to the two questions described in the introduction two this report, namely which factors lead to the successful implementation of DV policy measures and how can the success of the measure be assessed? To answer these questions the comparative analysis drew in particularly on the empirical evidence provided for the success of the measure contained in the national reports (e.g. the development of case numbers by victim support organisations) as well as on the findings of partners' own research activities, like interviews with professionals from the field. A detailed description of the analytical approach is provided in chapter 4 of the analysis.

The comparative contrasting was carried out by VICESSE, the task leader responsible for organising and guiding the task. Guidance included regular calls with all contributing partners, as well as situational bilateral calls to support partners in their research and writing activities. Furthermore, partners were sent two Guidelines for T4.1, one for this deliverable, as well as one for the acquisition of data needed for T4.2 "Designing Method for Identifying Change Accelerators (MICA)" and T4.3 "Developing a Decision Support Toolkit for FLR managers (DST)".

Appendix 2. Country Analysis of Policy-Enabler

2.1 Austria

The Austrian report expands on the research conducted in IMPRODOVA and IMPROVE. To this end, it uses previously collected interview material from T1.2, T1.3 and T1.4, as well as research from IMPRODOVA. This data is updated with new desk research. For this report, we have identified four different solutions that work in tandem to support victims, as well as intervene in and prevent DV.

The first solution is the Entry and Approach Ban (AV/BV), which at its core is a police intervention. However, due to its expansion of the course of more than 20 years, it now represents DV policy measures that address victims and offenders and involves several stakeholders. Combined these measures provide an effective, low-threshold and rapidly deployed method for preventing the immediate continuation of violence. They also serve as a starting point for further intervention. The second solution are the Austrian Women's Shelters which were among the first suitable victim protection measures available for female victims of DV. Women's Shelters not only provide immediate shelter to female victim-survivors of DV, but also offer out-client consultation among the most important interest groups working to improve the protection of women from domestic violence. The third solution are Violence Protection Centres which further expand the available support offer, by providing a generalised support infrastructure specialised on the counselling of victims. A special aspect of their work is their legally regulated cooperation with other front-line responders, in particular the police or violence prevention counselling services for offenders. The fourth solution are two distinct forms of court assistance available to victims of domestic violence in Austria. Legal court assistance, which provides legal consultation and representation, and psycho-social support which aims at lowering the burden of the support process and court proceedings.

2.1.1 Solution I: The Entry and Approach ban

Background and Aim

Among the police intervention measures used to address domestic violence, the entry and approach ban is the most important tool. Regulated in § 38a of the Security Police Act (SPG), the legal text obliges the police to impose an approach and trespassing ban if the necessary

requirements are met. The decisive reason for imposing such a ban is whether a “dangerous situation” exists, i.e. whether the police officers can assume from the situation at the scene that a person will commit a dangerous attack on the life, health or freedom of another person. To do so, officers must perform a risk prognosis § 38a SPG itself does not define the facts that are constitutive for a dangerous situation. According to case law and the academic literature, this may include: a potential previous assault, the statement of the endangered person, their appearance (e.g. swollen face, frightened impression), the behaviour of the endangering person, previous relevant incidents and official actions, cries for help heard from the home, previous convictions and visible injuries, traces at the scene (e.g. damaged door, broken objects) and/or statements from other persons present (Mayrhofer, 2023). If the intervening officers arrive at the conclusion that a dangerous situation exists, they must impose an entry and approach ban, which has numerous consequences. Firstly, for a period of two weeks, the perpetrator may no longer enter the premises (irrespective of property rights), including the area within a radius of one hundred metres of the location for which the AV/BV was issued. The ban on entry is accompanied by a ban on approaching which prohibits the perpetrator to approach the victims within a radius of one hundred metres. Moreover, the perpetrator has to hand over, all keys to the premises to the police. However, there are other consequences associated with the AV/BV. First, the police are obliged to report the AV/BV to the regionally responsible violence protection centre and to transmit the victim's data so that the violence protection centre can proactively contact the victim. The victim must be informed about this procedure. Furthermore, the victim must be informed about the possibility of applying to the court for a restraining order. There are three variants, namely the restraining order for protection against domestic violence, § 382b, for general protection against violence § 382c and for protection against “stalking” 382d. If the victim applies for such a restraining order, the AV/BV will first be extended by two weeks. Second, the perpetrator must contact a counselling centre for violence prevention within five days of the order of the AV/BV to arrange violence prevention counselling (§ 25 para. 4) and take part in the counselling. The counselling must take place within 14 days of contact being made. If the perpetrator does not make contact or does not take part in violence prevention counselling, they must be subpoenaed to the security authority for the purpose of carrying out violence prevention counselling. Thirdly, the imposition of an AV/BV results in an entry into the Central Violence Protection Register (“Zentrale Gewaltschutzdatei”), where the personal data of the perpetrator and information on the incident are stored for 3 years.

Implementation of the measure

The decisive driving force behind the original introduction of the entry ban as part of the First Protection Against Violence Act in 1997 was the socio-political atmosphere. With Europe as a whole experiencing a positive momentum also human rights and women's rights movements calling for the protection of women's fundamental rights were gaining political ground.

Justification

A key characteristic of the importance and success of the measure in practice is that since the introduction of the entry ban as part of the first Protection against Violence Act in 1997, the number of issued AV/BV has steadily risen. Although it is difficult to find exact and uniform figures for the last 26 years (e.g. violence protection centres and the police sometimes report different figures), all available sources show a steady increase. While in 1997, the first year that Section 38a (i.e. the possibility and duty of issuing an entry ban) came into force, the violence protection centres reported only 170 cases of entry bans. This figure rose to 4,672 cases by 2004 (Hengerer and Ullmann, 2005; Mayrhofer and Schwarz-Schlöglmann, 2017). For the same period, experts from the Federal Criminal Police Office reported 1,365 entry bans (BVs) for 1997 and 4,764 cases for 2004 (ibid.). In addition to the increase, an alignment of the figures can also be observed. In 2016, 8,637 cases were reported to the violence protection centres (Mayrhofer and Schwarz-Schlöglmann, 2017). The figures continued to rise with the third Protection against Violence Act, although the comparability is limited due to a new counting method. According to the 2020-2022 Violence Protection Report, the number of ordered AV/BV rose from 11,652 cases in 2020 to 13,690 cases in 2021 and 14,643 cases in 2022 (Bundeskriminalamt, 2023). This steady increase can be interpreted as an increase in the social and individual awareness of DV and the measure itself.

Experts from science, the police and violence protection organisation attribute this steady increase to several reasons. First, they note an increase in social awareness of the problem. This concerns both the problem of domestic violence in general and the willingness to defend oneself against it. Second, the awareness of the need for a professional approach to domestic violence has also increased in the security sector and, according to police experts, the entry and approach ban is among one the best trained measures by the police. The background to this development lies in the low threshold, immediacy, and effectiveness.

The low threshold is primarily based on the fact that the measure is imposed directly by the intervening officers. This means that no judicial or prosecutorial intervention is required. It has an immediate effect because the imposition directly breaks through the violent situation, in multiple dimensions. First, it provides immediate security, as the perpetrator has to leave the premises immediately, has to hand over all keys, maybe even taken to police station for questioning. Moreover, the police monitors compliance with the order within the first three days. In addition to these security measure, the AV/BV also intervenes at the social and psychological level, as the victim will be pro-actively contacted by a violence protection centre and the perpetrator is obliged to attend violence prevention counselling. Thus, the AV/BV is also designed by law to connect different front-line responder organisation and foster the information exchange between those stakeholders.

The effectiveness of the measure is achieved not only through the comprehensive training specialising on protection against violence, which police officers undergo as part of their basic training, but also through additional police measures that are structurally linked to the AV/BV. In almost every police station in Austria there is a specially trained officer to whom colleagues can turn, depending on availability, even during a police operation due to domestic violence. The police also offer victims counselling sessions, e.g. regarding further legal steps such as a restraining order. Moreover, the data on violations of the AV/BV demonstrate its effectiveness. According to the report of the Austrian Court of Audit (Österreichischer Rechnungshof), the proportion of violations of the AV/BV in relation to the total number of impositions in the period 2018-2021 was between 10% and a maximum of 14%. Finally, the measure is also highlighted by the “GREVIO Baseline Evaluation Report” for Austria for being an international role model in terms of police and legal interventions².

Overall, according to our analysis, several factors are decisive for the positive assessment of the AV/BV and its high level of effectiveness in practice:

- Clear legal anchoring with practical guidelines for intervening security authorities.
- An approach to victim protection that goes beyond police/security measures, but also included social and psychological support and intervention.

² For more details, see: https://www.aof.at/images/03_gesetze/3-5_istanbulkonvention/Official_GREVIO-Report_Austria_Web.pdf.

- The fact that the police have to inform violence protection centres who then proactively approach victims relieves victims of the pressure or possible anxiety to find a suitable support centre on their own.
- Since the imposition of the AV/BV also obliges the perpetrator to attend violence prevention counselling sessions, the AV/BV increasingly holds the perpetrators accountable.
- Extensive police education and training with the involvement of trainers from violence protection organisations.
- Increasing organisational specialisation within the police (e.g. introduction of specially trained officers for violence in the private sphere)
- Due to the provisions of the Security Police Act and its improvements over the course of three violence protection acts, cooperation between the various actors, i.e. the police, the violence protection centres for victims and the violence prevention centres for perpetrators, is structurally anchored in the law.
- Ongoing political reform and willingness to improve the AV/BV with the inclusion of expertise from the field.
- Violence protection centres receive extensive resources so that they can contact endangered persons after the imposition of an AV/BV.

Unintended consequences

At present, there seem to be only a few issues or areas for improvement in connection with the AV/BV. The main weakness is that the approach ban is not an independent measure, but can only be imposed in conjunction with an entry ban. This is a disadvantage in cases in which the offender does not know the victim's address. In such cases, it is better for the protection of the victim not to impose an AV/BV (in which the offender would have to be informed of the location to which the no-entry order applies). Another weakness is that the perpetrator's consent is required for the exchange of data between the police, the violence protection centre and the violence prevention centre, which makes cooperation more difficult. In the future, automatic data exchange should be made possible.

2.1.2 Solution II: Austrian Women's Shelter

Background and Aim

There are currently 33 women's shelters in Austria. Sixteen of these shelters are members of the "Autonome Österreichische Frauenhäuser" (Association of Autonomous Austrian Women's Shelters) association. This association is also home to the "Informationsstelle gegen Gewalt" (Information Centre against Violence), the "Frauenhelpline gegen Gewalt" (women's helpline against violence), the online "HelpChat - Halt der Gewalt" (Helpchat- Stop the Violence), the project "StoP - Stadteile ohne Partnergewalt" (StoP - Neighborhoods without partner violence) and Zentrum BAKHTI für EmPOWERment für Mädchen* und junge Frauen* (BAKHTI centre for empowerment for girls* and young women*). The majority of the actual organisations that operate the women's shelters are non-profit associations that receive funding from public institutions, such as ministries, municipalities or federal states, in addition to donations and volunteer work. A few women's shelters are operated by private or state-owned service providers.

In addition to providing accommodation for women and their children affected by violence, the main tasks also include legal advice and psycho-social support for women. This specifically includes developing a safety plan, support in dealing with authorities and courts (reporting an offence, divorce, custody, etc.) or for the enforcement of legal claims such as social welfare, support in finding accommodation and or parenting advice, as well as separation from the violent partner. Many shelters also offer accompaniment to the police, authorities, or made available. Shelters may also provide follow-up care and longer-term assistance that extends beyond the stay at the shelter. Core principle of the work is a victim-centred approach, whereby measures are only implemented with the consent of the victim.

In addition to these core tasks, women's health centres also play an important role in raising social awareness and educating people about violence against women. Their activities range from training courses, workshops and larger events, such as specialist conferences or public advertising campaigns.

Staff working in women's shelters often have a background in psychology and social work. However, many women's shelters also have employees with pedagogical or legal expertise as well as medical training. Typically, employees also have completed specialised training on how to support victims.

Implementation of the measure

In Austria the first women shelter was opened in Vienna in 1978. The foundation and opening of this and the other first women shelters was realised bottom-up by a handful of highly

motivated and politically engaged women (Karlsson, 1988). One important driving force behind this development was the international rise of a feminist perspective, which recognised and demanded that the 'private' must be perceived as public and political (Haller, 2002). This perspective challenged the strict separation between private and public spheres and highlighted how the private sphere is socially conditioned. It also challenged the state's self-image as a provider of first and foremost public security (ibid.). A particular challenge in establishing these first women's shelters, which still exist today, is funding. In addition to donations, extensive voluntary commitment and state support are typically required. Even in the early stages of development of the women shelters, there was a risk of political influence (Karlsson, 1988).

Besides the protection and empowerment of women, probably the most important contribution of the women's shelter movement was its feminist activism, which called attention to violence against women and male violence and demanded the right of women and girls to physical integrity and sexual self-determination (Dearing et al., 2000). Thus, in many ways, the women's shelter movement still is one of the most important driving forces for improvements in the protection against violence, the recognition of victims, and the public and political discourse on the subject.

In the years that followed, women's shelters were founded throughout Austria as projects by an association of committed women. In 1988, these individual women's shelters joined forces to form the 'Aktionsgemeinschaft österreichischer Frauenhäuser' (Action Group of Austrian Women's Shelters) (Brem 2008). While these first pilot projects were still founded in the spirit of feminist, grassroots democratic and autonomous principles, many women's shelters had to be restructured over time as the organisational structures and demands grew, but also in part due to the requirements of financial donors. As a result, women's shelters slowly changed from feminist-activist and egalitarian community projects to social institutions with clear hierarchies, working and funding structures. However, their feminist working principles remained unaffected by this change (ibid.). This development went hand in hand with a professionalisation of the work, but at the same time new demands were increasingly placed on women's shelters. Professionalisation was achieved to the extent that, especially in the initial phase, there were hardly any guidelines or specific training, but employees had to acquire knowledge and skills independently in practice. In the course of the more than 40-years-long history of women's shelters, many new requirements have arisen. Beside securing

funding, one particular challenge was that an increasing number of women with a migration background have sought out women's shelters (Brückner, 2008). This has confronted staff with language and cultural communication problems. Today, however, women's shelters are well-equipped in supporting different vulnerable groups which can be seen in the multilingual websites and multi-lingual composition of the teams, increasingly barrier free buildings or the multitude of counselling formats.

Another important step in the implementation and work of women's shelters continues to be the cooperation with other support organisations like violence protection centres, with social services (e.g. child and youth welfare bureaus or public housing services), as well as with police and the judiciary. Today, this cooperation has become increasingly more important, as women's shelters are now one of a variety of support organisations, albeit an enormously important one. Thus, in order to provide comprehensive support to women, whose average length of stay has also tended to be shorter, cooperation with other institutions is required. In addition, the second objective of the women's shelter movement, namely awareness raising and promotion of women rights, can be realised more broadly through such cooperation. Finally in 2023 the Austrian federal government with the nine states introduced a new funding scheme, the *Frauen-Schutzunterkunfts-Vereinbarung* (Women's Shelter agreement). This provides for the payment of a total of 12 million euros over the period 2023 to 2026. Eligibility for this payment is determined by the requirements and tasks to be fulfilled by the funding recipients, which are specified in the law.

All in all, the following points were crucial for sustainable implementation:

- Bottom-up development by highly motivated groups of feminist activists.
- Networking between the staff of women's shelters.
- Cooperation with political actors, also to secure funding.
- Feminist activism, primarily through political public relations work that focuses on the concerns and problems of women and promotes social change.
- Professionalisation and restructuring of women's shelter work.
- Establishing cooperation with other organisations dedicated to tackling domestic violence.

Justification

The importance of women's shelters and the women's shelter movement in the fight against violence against women and the protection of victims and their children can hardly be overestimated. In Austria women's shelters were the first comprehensive institutions to protect women from male violence and paved the way for today's protection system. The relevance of women's shelters can be recognised by the fact that today women's shelters are available in all EU countries, even if there are not enough places and funding is often inadequate. Nevertheless, women's shelters represent a transnational concept that can be implemented at a comparatively low threshold due to the extensive international experience. Moreover, the occupancy and support figures show that women's shelters in Austria are an indispensable pillar of victim protection³.

Overall, the numbers of women and children who received shelter have remained relatively constant over the years⁴. According to the AÖF reports, 3,502 people, including 1,735 women and 1,767 children, received support in 2012. Similar figures can also be found in the following years for the 26 women's shelters that contributed data to the various reports. For example, 3,232 persons were supported in 2013; 3,257 persons in 2014; 3,331 persons in 2015, 3,261 persons in 2016; 3,341 persons in 2017; 3,284 persons in 2018; and in 2019 3,310 children and women received shelter. The emergence of the Covid crisis in 2020 caused a decline in admission rates, with 2,994 women and children finding refuge in a women's shelter. This corresponds to a decline of just under 10% compared to 2019. Due to the lockdown related restrictions it was impossible for many women to flee from their violent partner. Although the figures for 2021 and 2022 rose again to just over 3,000, these figures are not comparable with previous years due to structural changes in the women's refuge landscape. The same applies to 2022, when 3,578 people found refuge in a women's refuge. While Covid has led to a decline in admission rates, there has been an increase in the number of days spent in shelters. For example, the women's shelters that are part of the AÖF reported a significant increase in 2020, with 83,561 days of stay compared to 2019, where 71,179 days of stay were reported. This figure decreased again in the following years to 74,239 days in 2021 and 71,179 days in 2022.

³ The comparability of the annual occupancy/support figures for women and children in Austrian women's shelters, which originate from the reports and statistics of the AÖF, is only partially valid. This is due to the fact that counting and reporting methods have changed repeatedly, e.g. due to changes in association structures, the lack of or addition of reports from shelters that are not part of the ALF, or the opening or closing of women's shelters.

⁴ For the following overview, refer to the AÖF activity reports under: <https://www.a oef.at/index.php/infomaterial-zum-downloaden/taetigkeitsberichte-der-a oef>

The great importance of women's shelters is also reflected in the high number of consultations. In 2022, AÖF women's shelters staff provided counselling to 10,163 persons by telephone (37.4 % of counselling sessions), on an outpatient basis (22.6 % of counselling sessions) or via the internet (4.5 % of counselling sessions). The remaining 35.4% were follow-up counselling contacts, with women who had previously stayed in the shelter. There are hardly any evaluation studies on the work of women's shelters in Austria as a whole or on individual shelters. The GREVIO Shadow Report 2016 (AÖF & IST, 2016) and a 2020 working paper by *the Institut für Sozialarbeit und Sozialpädagogik e.V.* (Lange, 2020) offer a positive assessment of Austria in the area of women's shelters, but also point out structural weaknesses. The two central problems are the occasional precarious funding and the overall lack of places, particularly in rural areas. Women's shelters are often unable to offer more than short-term crisis interventions, and there are many women who cannot be admitted to the women's shelter of their region due to a lack of space (*ibid.*). In addition, there are shortcomings in the care of particularly vulnerable groups, such as asylum seekers and women with precarious residence status, also due to different legal requirements depending on the federal state (*ibid.*). Finally, despite best efforts, women's shelters only partially meet the needs of female victims of violence with addiction problems, psychological problems, and mental or physical disabilities (Mandl et al., 2014). However, many of these evaluations could not yet take into account the recent legal developments regarding the funding of women's shelters.

Unintended consequences

There are no unintended negative consequences of women's shelters

2.1.3 Solution III: Violence Protection Centres

Background and Aim

The Austrian approach to combatting Domestic Violence entails a four-pillar-approach. The first three, introduced since 1997, are the approach and entry bans, temporary injunctions and the Gewaltschutzzentren – the Violence protection centres (abbreviated GSZ) (Hengerer & Ullmann, 2005). Additionally, a fourth pillar, the violence prevention training, was introduced in 2019 and implemented 2021.⁵ Consequently, the GSZs hold a central role within the support infrastructure for victims of violence. This goes theoretically beyond DV, nevertheless cases of DV comprise large parts of GSZ casework.⁶ While the other three pillars target the perpetrator; the GSZ are a dedicated victim-survivor institution that seek to “comprehensively support at-risk persons”.⁷ These centres are mandated federally and organised on a state-by-state level. The GSZs are tasked with helping victim-survivors navigate the available support infrastructure, as well as legal procedures. In practice, this includes a wide variety of tasks. D1.2 Interviews highlighted how GSZ were supporting victims when requesting international judicial cooperation in cross-border DV cases, to help find alternative housing, to go through police reporting, and much more. To do so, state-level GSZs usually consist of one central office with local offices, as well as mobile units. This helps provide localised support to victims of violence, especially in the more rural areas of Austria.

The implementation of the GSZs must be understood as part of larger concerted efforts to overhaul the Austrian approach to DV “from a private matter” to a criminal matter (Logar, 2007). For this overhaul, the Violence Protection Centres were tasked with addressing the victim’s support needs as well as facilitate cooperation between all relevant institutions in the handling of DV. Early tasks included aiding victims to navigate the post-intervention situation, including filing for an extension of security measures, to help draft a security plan, as well as preliminary legal and comprehensive psycho-social support during the reporting and legal processes.⁸ 1997 saw a number of additional legal reforms, including changes to the Security Police Act (Sicherheitspolizeigesetz - SPG), the General Civil Code (Allgemeines

⁵ For more details, see <https://www.bundestkanzleramt.gv.at/agenda/frauen-und-gleichstellung/gewalt-gegen-frauen/gewaltformen/haeusliche-gewalt.html>

⁶ As can be seen in GSZ activity reports, including Gewaltschutzzentrum Burgenland, 2024; Gewaltschutzzentrum Wien, 2024; and Gewaltschutzzentrum Steiermark, 2024

⁷ For more details, see <https://www.bundestkanzleramt.gv.at/agenda/frauen-und-gleichstellung/gewalt-gegen-frauen/gewaltformen/haeusliche-gewalt.html>

⁸ This does not entail psycho-social court assistance, given its later implementation.

Bürgerliches Gesetzbuch - ABGB) and the Enforcement Order (Exekutionsordnung - EO);⁹ as well as financing for psycho-therapeutic support for victims of crime (via changes to the Crime Victim Act in 1999) (Wiener Interventionsstelle gegen Gewalt in der Familie, 2019).

With the increasing availability of legal recourse, court proceedings became an integral part of the handling of DV. The nationwide implementation psycho-social court assistance in 2006 has impacted and defined GSZ activities. This is in part due to the criteria for funding by the Ministry of Justice (abbreviated as MoJ), namely that psycho-social process assistance services must be provided by organisations providing wider support services (Bundesministerium für Justiz, 2024). The role of the GSZs saw further expansions with subsequent reforms to the GewSchG. The 2nd GewSchG came into force 2009 and was intended to provide a “faster, more flexible and effective approach against any type of domestic violence” (Mottl, 2009). This was followed by the 3rd GewSchG 2019, which included better interventions against stalking and harassment by requiring data transfer on such matters to GSZs.¹⁰ Furthermore, the reforms also introduced the Security Police Case Conferences (Sicherheitspolizeiliche Fallkonferenzen), which provides a platform to address high risk cases and can be utilised by the GSZs.

Implementation and Practice

The practice of the GSZ is largely based on an “active approach”. This active approach is facilitated by legally obliging police officers intervening in a DV case to forward any issued approach and entry ban or report of stalking to the relevant GSZ.¹¹ This allows the GSZs to quickly engage with victim-survivors once a forwarded police report has opened a new case.¹² GSZ internally distribute these new cases amongst staff, who then try to actively reach out to victim survivors via phone or mail. GSZ support is not mandatory, as such victim-survivors are only offered a first introduction, as well as a follow-up appointment. Where no police report was filed, victim-survivors can choose to seek GSZ support themselves. To aid in this, police officers, judges and prosecutors are required to inform victim-survivors of their rights, including the right to psycho-social court assistance.¹³ This usually entails imparting

⁹ For more details, see https://www.bmi.gv.at/magazin/2022_07_08/15_Gewaltschutzgesetz.aspx

¹⁰ For more details, see <https://www.bmj.gv.at/ministerium/gesetzsentwuerfe/entw%C3%BCrfe-2019/drittes-gewaltschutzgesetz.html>

¹¹ As defined by 38§ SPO.

¹² Police reports are compared to existing files on victim-survivors. Should a costumer file exist, the report is forwarded to the responsible social worker where possible.

¹³ As defined by §70 para. 1 & 2 StPO.

information and contact details about local GSZ branches. Additionally, public information campaigns advertising GSZs,¹⁴ as well as cooperation between the various support organisations with GSZs, help funnel victim-survivors to the central support organisations.

The rate of clients who were actively approached after a forwarded police intervention, to clients who actively sought help can vary. For Styria in 2022, the GSZ reported 1466 clients referred to by an approach and entry ban, in contrast to 2077 cases without (Gewaltschutzzentrum Steiermark, 2023). For Burgenland, a total of 778 clients were reported, while 419 referred approach and entry bans were issued (Gewaltschutzzentrum Steiermark, 2023). A comparison between states remains difficult due to a partial lack of data, as well as different formats thereof. Nonetheless, it seems safe to assume that referral due to issued approach and entry bans are an important factor to the influx of victim-survivors to the GSZs.

Victim-survivors of GSZs receive both short-term, as well as long term support. According to the annual activity reports and interviews with GSZ staff, a first support step involves addressing immediate security needs. This can include in some GSZs a preliminary risk assessment and the drafting of a security plan where clients might still be facing an active risk. More immediate actions can also include supporting clients should they choose to file a police report, including accompanying them to the police. A large part of the work of GSZ personal is providing judicial and long-term support. Judicial support, especially throughout the length of the criminal proceeding, comes primarily in the shape of psycho-social court assistance. More details on this are supplied in the corresponding chapter of this report. Interviews with victim survivors have indicated, that support provided by GSZs social workers can go beyond a single violent relationship. This means that for some victim-survivors, GSZ support transcends one violent partner or instance of violence. Hence, they can provide support across multiple interventions. For example, in 2023 the Viennese GSZ reported a total of 1303 returning clients, out of a total of 6708 (Gewaltschutzzentrum Wien, 2024). This is done, according to interviews, wherever possible, by the same social worker. For some clients, support can, therefore, entail a process that may last multiple years and multiple partners, each with different support cycles and needs. Furthermore, all interviewed GSZ

¹⁴ One example of such are GSZ contact details printed out on grocery store receipts (Spar, [2023](#))

staff reported providing long-lasting support well after a case has concluded and/or a divorce has gone through.

Strengths and Weaknesses

The strengths of the GSZs lie in a number of factors. Interviews with GSZ staff have highlighted, how most, if not all staff is undergoing psycho-social court assistance and other training. This contributes to GSZs having highly trained social workers available to support victim-survivors. This distinguished GSZ staff in particular from smaller NGOs. Furthermore, GSZs are connected to a number of external professionals. These include both, informal and formal links to hospitals, police departments and officers, legal professionals, and so on. The legal framework under which GSZs operate underpins this interconnectivity, as well as secures annual funding for the GSZs. Lastly, the victim-centred approach has been identified by interview partners as an essential strong point of GSZs, as they are able to provide support to a number of victims in various circumstances.

The main weaknesses of the GSZ can be identified in two areas: the dependence on other stakeholders, as well as the perception of the Austrian support infrastructure amongst the victim-survivors.

A topic that was discussed multiple times within the interviews with social workers from the GSZs, was the inability for the GSZs to reach parts of the population. This impression is by no means unreasonable, given existing data. The latest large-scale survey on violence against women in Austria published by Statistik Austria in 2022 concluded, that while 70% of respondents sought help for violence in intimate partnerships, only 17% did so via the police, and only 12% via dedicated support services. Health care and consultation services were sought by 20% (Statistik Austria, 2022). Consequently, usage of these services, according to the interviewees, lags far behind the needs of the victims. This is further exacerbated by a gap in awareness regarding the existence of the GSZ. The same study found, that only 53% of respondents knew about the GSZs, in contrast to over 90% who knew about women's shelter. Given the centrality of the GSZs in the Austrian support structure, one interviewee highlighted failures to adequately disseminate information on the GSZs within the last 2,5 decades. Interestingly enough, the lack of awareness was a theme present during D1.2 interviews with victims, who at times noted about not having been aware about the GSZs until police intervention.

The second weakness relates to the dependency on other external actors. As was discussed above, the GSZs rely on police officers for referrals, on judges and lawyers during the trials, as well as other external actors, ranging from medical experts operating Victim Protection Groups in hospitals, to NGOs providing expertise on marginalised victim groups. While interviews have highlighted that the cooperation infrastructure is working well, instances of problems where judges are not adequately sensitised to DV or police officers not forwarding reports to GSZs on time have been noted. All of these can impede the support services provided by the GSZs. Individual instances of such problems have been reported. They seem sufficiently wide-spread that interviewees report to avoid or specifically seek out certain judges or officers.

Justification

The successful implementation of the GSZ can be traced back to 4 distinct factors, each of which will be explained in more details. They are: Comprehensive legislation underpinning the centrality of the GSZ, interagency cooperation and standing, secured and continuous funding, as well as a victim-survivor centred approach.

The GSZs are embedded within a legal framework that ensures the funding thereof, as well as mandates the interaction between it and other institutions addressing DV. The original GewSchG and the following two reforms have delineated a number of roles and obligations for the GSZs. This underpins not just the financial backing and continues funding that will be discussed in the next paragraph, but also the cooperation with courts, LEAs and NGOs. For instance, the police are legally obliged to forward reports of cases where approach and entry bans have been issued to the regional GSZ (See for example Gewaltschutzzentrum Wien, 2024). During court trials, victims are by law entitled to receive psycho-social and legal Court assistance. Both of which can be provided or arranged by GSZs, securing GSZ staff a legally mandated position in these trials. This interlinkage is also observable during security case conferences, where GSZs are able to apply for opening of such cases by the police, or the referral of victim-survivors from smaller NGOs to GSZs where risk assessments are required.

This highlights how GSZ operations require cooperation with numerous different stakeholders throughout the entire support process. The intended centrality on the victim-support side makes GSZs, where victims have chosen to use GSZ-services, a central hub for support interventions. D1.2 interviews have provided examples of GSZ social workers helping victims with filling for social security payments, seeking accommodations, facilitate the return of children from foreign countries, find legal representation and file necessary court documents. Thus, where clients are supported by GSZs, other stakeholders are obliged and incentivized to cooperate. T1.3 interviews have indicated how a number of factors have contributed to a positive standing of GSZs amongst other stakeholder. The include the high-standard of training GSZ-employees undergo, the involvement of GSZs in the training of other professions, a general increase in DV awareness, the use of cooperation platforms, as well as the perception that GSZs can help alleviate workload. This, in turn, further enhances the cooperation, contributing to a better implementation of GSZs activities and provision of support.

In regards to funding, the GSZs are recipients of various funding streams, that ensure their continued function. Most notably, all GSZs receive direct funding from the Federal Chancellery of the Republic of Austria, as well as the Ministry of Interior (abbreviated as Mol).¹⁵ The funding from the Mol is fixed but happens on an annually renewed contract basis. It stipulates a base-line funding for the GSZ according to an estimated caseload. Should any of the GSZs support more clients within their state than stipulated, according to the number of extra cases additional are paid out. For the year 2023, a budget of 7,8 million € for services rendered (Werkleistungen) was reported (Rechnungshof Österreich, 2023). Furthermore, GSZs receive financial compensation for their work as court assistance from the Ministry of Justice . Like the funding provided by the Mol, it consists of a contractually fixed sum for an estimated contingent of services, as well as corrections based on the reported efforts (Bundesministerium für Justiz, 2024). Given that the exact funding numbers are often collated with other intervention structures, it remains difficult to ascertain the total funding for the GSZs. This has already been a point of contention in the GREVIO report on Austria (Council of Europe, 2017). Besides these national funding streams, GSZs can also receive additional funding for projects.¹⁶ It is unclear in how far all GSZ do receive this, given that some GSZ annual reports do not mention funds by state institutions. These multiple state-funding schemes ensure that the GSZs are able to provide free-of-charge support to victim-survivors across Austria.

The victim-survivor centred approach of GSZ entails two different aspects: firstly, is an “active approach” (as termed by the GSZs). This means the following: Once the GSZs have been forwarded a police report, GSZ staff actively reach out to victims of violence to offer support. Potential clients are free to decide whether to make use of GSZ services. Secondly, it is the flexibility regarding the clients’ situations. GSZs have multiple mobile units and smaller offices spread throughout the region, to ensure that geographical distances can be bridged. Additionally, GSZs will provide support to victim-survivors regardless of their housing and living situation. This includes victims residing in shelter housing, or with the perpetrator, at their own house, as well as (temporarily) unhoused victims.¹⁷ This has been highlighted by

¹⁵ The exact funding agencies are subjects to change due to possible changes in competencies.

¹⁶ Perspektive: Arbeit is one such example, where the lower Austrian GSZ, Women’s Shelter and Labour Office cooperate under directive of the national Labour Office on helping female victim-survivors of DV with re-entry into the labour market: More information available at: Bundesministerium für Soziales, Gesundheit, Pflege und Konsumentenschutz (2019): Handbuch PERSPEKTIVE:ARBEIT

¹⁷ As was the case for one interviewed victim-survivor, who was temporarily unhoused due to the DV they had experienced.

T1.2 interviews with victims of DV, who had stressed issues with shelter-provided services, who had imposed limitations to residency, including bringing teenage boys, pets, as well as substance-abuse issues. While GSZs do not provide the same services as shelters, the counselling provided by GSZs targets a wider audience.

Practical relevance

Given how victim-survivor centred GSZ activities are, practical relevance is best measured by seeing how well it reaches and supports victims of DV. On the topic of usage, GSZ case-loads have increased almost yearly, with the exception of 2018, from 1154 in 1998 to a total of 24805 in 2023.

Graphic 1: Graph of cases of support reported by the GSZs Austria-wide¹⁸

A regional comparison of growth rates shows, that while this growth is not distributed evenly, all state-level GSZs report a growing case-load between 2019 and 2023, as pictured in the graph below:

¹⁸ Data is available online, here <https://www.gewaltschutzzentrum.at/zahlen-fakten/>

As official numbers on DV are lacking and not all GSZ reports do differentiate between DV and non-DV cases, it is unclear in how far this adequately covers the support needs of DV victim survivors. A comparison with reported approach and entry bans shows that increases in GSZ cases closely followed or exceeded increases in Approach and Entry bans.²⁰

There are as of 2024 still problems regarding public perception. Close to half (53%) of the women who have experienced violence in their partnerships reported being aware of the GSZs, in comparison to over 90% who knew about the existence of women’s shelters (Statistik Austria, 2022). Interviews conducted have also highlighted, how high-risk victims in particular are not sufficiently covered by GSZ support. This problem is somewhat ameliorated by the fact, that victim-survivors are approached by the GSZs after the issuing of an approach and entry ban. Nonetheless, there appears to be a general lack of access to high-risk victims. A study on femicides by Haller et al found that only 5,4 percent of all victims of femicides were known to support services. Perpetrators were known to the police in only 28,4% of all femicide cases (Haller et al, 2023).

However, a growing number of cases indicate an increasing public awareness, if not improvement of the referral mechanisms. Additionally, as reported in D1.2, Austrian interview

¹⁹ Data is available online here: <https://www.gewaltschutzzentrum.at/zahlen-fakten/>

²⁰ Whose use as a proxy for instances is lacking, as the data published by the Statistic Austria survey from 2023 indicates.

data from GSZ clients indicate a high degree of satisfaction with GSZ support, once used. Consequently, there seems to be an ever-increasing practical relevance of GSZs.

Evidence and Data

Evidence and data to evaluate GSZ activity are available via multiple avenues. Firstly, the state-level GSZs publish activity reports themselves. While the number of details and information included in the reports varies from state to state, they do provide statistical information on the case load of the GSZs. For example, the Viennese GSZ reported for 2023 6708 clients who had experienced violence in close relationships (Gewaltschutzzentrum Wien, 2024). In the same year, 4284 reports of approach and entry bans were forwarded by the police to the GSZs. The Viennese report, which constitutes one of the more detailed examples, also includes other data points, such as geographical distribution, rate of returning clients, offence types, and so on. Similarly, detailed reports are also provided by the GSZ Styria (Gewaltschutzzentrum Steiermark, 2024) and Lower Austria (Gewaltschutzzentrum Niederösterreich, 2024). This is not to say that the other reports do not provide sufficient data, as all states provide annual statistics on their activity. For an overview of the reported statistics, see “Practical relevance” above.

Besides the self-published GSZ reports, governmental reports and evaluations of GSZs or GSZ related activities are published. Notable is the report by the MoJ on court assistance spending and activities, which are a significant part of GSZ work (Bundesministerium für Justiz, 2024). Financing reports and data are also available (Rechnungshof Österreich, 2023). National evaluations are evaluation of the 1997 GewSchG (Dearing et al., 2000; as well as Haller et al., 2002) and the evaluation of the GewSchG 2019 (Bundesministerium für Inneres, 2020). They are all part of dedicated efforts to evaluate reforms to the GewSchG at different points in time. Another evaluation preceding the 2019 reforms was conducted under the leadership of the Mol (Kommission Opferschutz und Täterarbeit, 2019). Criticism of the most recent evaluation largely focuses on the support infrastructure for victim-survivors of situational violence. GSZ operations for DV victims are largely seen as satisfactory, especially in regard to the referral mechanism. Furthermore, GSZs can be indirectly or partially evaluated. As was mentioned above, the latest Austrian victimisation survey included items regarding respondents’ use of support infrastructure, as well as whether they were aware of

services (Statistik Austria, 2022). Lastly, regional evaluations of GSZs are conducted (for example Gewaltschutzzentren Kärnten, 2019), but not all of them are publicly accessible.²¹

Context of the Solution

As was discussed in “Background and Aim”, the GSZs were part of an overhaul of the Austrian approach to DV. Consequently, they must be understood as a break with the previously practiced approach. Prior to the GewSchG reform, feminist organisations criticized the prevailing approach to DV in Austria. As it stood, police interventions were largely aimed at mediating and deescalating instances of DV, by, for example removing women from their homes in cases of DV. According to the critique, this would further infringe upon the rights of the victims, while delegating inter-familial conflicts to a purely private matter (Wiener Interventionsstelle gegen Gewalt in der Familie, 2019). Pilot implementation of the US DAIP-project were seen as a possible solution to this. Building on cooperation between police and women’s shelter, as well as policy makers, the mid 90s saw discussions and formulations of an Austrian solution. These resulted in early attempts, such as the Styrian Intervention centre in 1995, that would later become the Styrian GSZ. What followed was federal consolidation and implementation in 1997, with the introduction of the first Violence Protection Act (Gewaltschutzgesetz - GewSchG) (Logar, 2008).

Changes were therefore achieved by piloting the intervention centres and building on the piloting experiences with nation-wide reforms, including the GewSchG, as well as changes to the SPG, the ABGB and the EO ²². Interviews with high ranking members of the GSZs, that have been involved since early on, have stressed that the successful implementation of the GSZs relied on good cooperation with other stakeholders, in particular LEAs. Early training efforts and the hierarchical structure of the police allowed for widespread awareness raising amongst police officers. Similar attempts to implement DV sensitivity-training can be seen with courts. While training of judicial staff is lagging behind, past cooperation experiences has helped alleviate tension between stakeholders. GSZs provided court assistance, for instance, is seemingly perceived to help lower the workload of courts. This is in largely parts because GSZ staff can help victim-survivors understand procedural steps and file necessary documents, all of which can help lower the workload for courts. While issues can still persist, GSZ staff reported widespread acceptance amongst external stakeholders.

²¹ Interviewdata of one such evaluation was provided for D1.2.

²² For more details, see https://www.bmi.gv.at/magazin/2022_07_08/15_Gewaltschutzgesetz.aspx

Unintended Consequences and Risks

No unintended consequences of implementing the solutions could be identified or have been reported.

2.1.4 Solution IV: Court Assistance

Background and Aim

The Austrian support system for victim survivors of violence, including DV, has two distinct forms of court-assistance. These are Psycho-Social and Legal Court assistance, the former being abbreviated PSCA and the latter abbreviated LCA within this report. Both seek to cover different needs of victim-survivors during any criminal trial resulting from the experienced violence (Bundesministerium für Justiz, 2024). They are both meant to ensure that the rights and wellbeing of the victims are safeguarded during the entirety of the legal proceedings. PSCA and LCA are made available to all victims of violent crimes, and dangerous threats and sexual offences, as well as any relatives of homicide victims²³, according to § 66b para. 1 StPO. It also includes victims of terrorist acts²⁴, stalking,²⁵ incitement²⁶ and various forms of slander.²⁷ It is primarily meant for criminal procedures. Where civil proceedings result from a criminal case, PSCA can be extended free of charge to cover the civil case, as stipulated by § 73b Civil procedure Code (Zivilprozessordnung – ZPO). For DV, this is particularly relevant for matters regarding barring orders, divorces, damages, custody and alimony. The same does not apply to LCA.

PSCA aims to reduce the risk of re-traumatisation and re-victimisation of victim survivors during the court procedures. They do so by helping victims prepare for legal processes, as well as provide direct support and company. LCA seeks to complement this by providing legal representation and counselling, in order to ensure the safeguarding of victims and procedural rights.²⁸

PSCA and LCA were introduced simultaneously in 2006 via reforms to the criminal procedure code (Strafprozessordnung - StPO). Their historical roots are in attempts to support victims of sexualized violence, as well as child and youth victims (Weißer Ring, 2018). Starting with the right of victims of sexualized violence to testify in the presence of a trustee introduced 1987, the possibility was opened up to witnesses generally in 1993, which also applied to all victims of crime. More comprehensive court assistance was attempted by local projects and

²³ As defined by §65 para. 1 lit. a and b Criminal Procedure Law

²⁴ As defined by § 278c Criminal Code (Strafgesetzbuch -StGB)

²⁵ As defined by § 107a StGB and § 107c StGB

²⁶ As defined by§ 283 StGB

²⁷ This can range from §111, §113 and §283 StGB.

²⁸ As described in § 66b para. 2 StPO

victim support organisations in the 80s and 90. These small local and individual interventions were expanded upon, as procedural support for underage victims was tested in a number of federal state and later on a federal level (Bundesministerium für Justiz, 2024 & Tamar, n.A.).

This resulted, as stated above, in changes to the StPO and the introduction of the right to psycho-social and legal court assistance in 2006. Subsequent reforms saw the expansion of availability, as well as an increasing degree of institutionalisation and usage. This includes establishing of the Management Centre Victim Protection (Managementzentrum Opferhilfe - MZ.O), managed by the Centre of Legal Competence (CLC),²⁹ with the intended purpose to serve as a “Central Coordination- and Networking-Point” from which training can be implemented and quality standards can be set.³⁰

Implementation and Practice

The PSCA and LCA see differences in implementation and practice, as they both attend to different procedural needs of victim survivors. PSCA remuneration is based on standards set forth and updated nationwide by the MoJ (Bundesministerium für Justiz, 2024). These standards dictate that MoJ-financed PSCA can only be provided by recognized victim-support organisations. These organisations must be providing general victim support services and have especially trained personal to provide PSCA. As such, PSCA is usually part of a wider support intervention, that can be well in advance of court proceedings. The extent to which the PSCA is involved in the process leading reporting and subsequent legal proceedings are dependent on whether and when clients seek assistance. It can include consultation on the reporting of a crime. This includes preparing a victim to report a crime, consulting a victim on the consequences of doing so, as well as accompanying victims to the police. PSCA can also consult on the involvement of legal court assistance.

During the criminal or civil process, the PSCA can be involved in a number of ways. To a large part, PSCA is there to ensure that victims are able to emotionally endure the strain put on them by the court process.³¹ This is done by accompanying the victims to questioning and hearing, as well as helping facilitate adequate hearing conditions, including victim-sensitive adversarial questioning (Kontradiktorische Vernehmung).³² Even after the conclusion of the

²⁹ For more details, see <https://www.justiz.gv.at/service/opferhilfe-und-prozessbegleitung.961.de.html>

³⁰ For more details, see <https://www.clc.or.at/de/managementzentrum-opferhilfe/>

³¹ As defined by §65 para. 1 lit. a and b StPO

³² As stipulated by § 165 StPO

main court proceedings, PSCA can be upheld. This is the case where victims are involved in civil cases which result from the criminal case.

As LCAs aim at legal representation, they can be only done by lawyers.³³ The legal representation can happen in advance of a police report, but it concludes with the end of the criminal case. An option to extend it to resulting civil proceedings does not exist as of 2024. LCAs are tasked with “explaining [to clients] the court procedures, their rights and duties”³⁴, as well as to “ensure the safeguarding of clients rights”³⁵. In practice, this entails that LCA ensure that procedural regulations, such as the right to information, are upheld; while providing legal counselling to their clients. Examples can be consulting clients whether to file a police report, what legal remedies to seek, and discussing the chances to seek for damages. Compensation for LCAs, similar to PSCA, is set forth by the MoJ.³⁶

Strengths and Weaknesses

Given that the strengths of the solutions are highlighted under “Justification”, this subchapter only includes a short rundown of the strengths of court assistance. These are in the institutional backing via a strong legal framework, the training of staff, the acceptance amongst cooperating partners, and the victim-centred work. Many of these points are covered in “Conditions and factors for the successful implementation”. In comparison, PSCA weaknesses lie mainly in the eligibility and specificity of the service, as well as the dependence on other professions.

Regarding eligibility, 2021 changes have introduced an expansion of the eligibility criteria, by not only including victims of violence, but also children witnessing DV (Bundeskanzleramt, 2023). Nonetheless issues remain where relationships are not recognized by courts. This is leading to witnesses of DV possibly falling outside the eligibility criteria. Furthermore, once victim-survivors have not made use of PSCA during a criminal trial, PSCA becomes also unavailable for any resulting civil trial. Furthermore, PSCA training includes specialisation on different types of victims. However, non-female victims of DV do not have specialised PSCA services, as of 2024. While the institutions providing these services might be specialised in any non-female victim-group of DV, the PSCA training only explicitly covers female victims of male-perpetrated violence. As such, non-binary and male victims might not receive adequate

³³ 66b Abs 2 StPO

³⁴ 66b Abs 2 & Abs 3 StPO

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ 66b Abs 3 StPO

or less-specialized support. Changes to this curriculum have been announced, as the Court Assistance Regulation draft (Prozessbegleitungs-Regulierungsverordnung - PbRegVO) will enter into force on October 2025.³⁷

Given that court assistance requires other parties involved in the prosecution of violence to cooperate so as to ensure a safeguarding of the clients' interests and wellbeing, this cooperation becomes a possible weakness. While interviews and available information suggest that, in practice, cooperation is generally adequate; individual cases where insufficient cooperation negatively affected the support for victim-survivors have been reported. This can include instances, where LCA or PSCA are not forwarded court documents or information beneficial to their clients, in particular updates to the incarceration-status of perpetrators; where police officers do not adequately inform victim-survivors on their right to PSCA and LCA before making a statement with the police; as well as expert witnesses not permitting clients to bring PSCAs (Bundesverband der Gewaltschutzzentren, 2023 & 2024). These occasional difficulties are in part due to gaps in the existing legal framework, as well as to individual decisions, if not failures, of stakeholders to (not) abide by existing regulation.

Lastly, reform suggestions by the GSZs identify a number of weaknesses in the provision of LCA. These largely focus on the limitation of LCA. These are the limit to criminal procedures, which does not allow an extension of the LCA to any resulting civil procedures, as well as a maximum coverage-amount for LCAs in criminal proceedings. Further limitations apply to the availability of LCA, especially where abuse does not classify as criminal offense. Additionally, cases where LCA and victims were not sufficiently involved in court procedures or informed about court activities have been reported. As the LCA largely depend on the cooperation of the courts, failure to do so can disrupt the legal representation of victim-survivors and infringe upon their rights. This is in part by a lack of legal recourse in cases, where perpetrators are found guilty, even though victims and their legal representation were not adequately involved. (Bundesverband der Gewaltschutzzentren, 2024).

³⁷ For more details, see

[https://www.justiz.gv.at/service/opferhilfe-und-prozessbegleitung/prozessbegleitung/prozessbegleitungs-regulierungsverordnung-\(pbregvo\).e9e.de.html](https://www.justiz.gv.at/service/opferhilfe-und-prozessbegleitung/prozessbegleitung/prozessbegleitungs-regulierungsverordnung-(pbregvo).e9e.de.html)

Justification

The successful implementation of court assistance in Austria rests in particular on three aspects: an legal framework, funding and acceptance amongst stakeholders.

The Austrian legal framework clearly enshrines the right to PSCA and LCA in § 66b para. 1 StPO for victims according to § 65 para. 1 StPO or § 66b para. 1 StPO. The exact purposes of PSCA and LCA are defined in § 66b para. 2 StPO and detailed in “Description” above. While this is not without its flaws and gaps, as described in “Strengths and weaknesses”, this helps to clearly communicate the role of court assistance to other stakeholders and ensures legal recourse where stakeholders fail to account for them. Examples include the right of victims to be informed about support services, including PSCA and LCA, the right to support during trials and while giving a testimony, as well as the right to counsel by PSCA and/or LCA.

The legal framework also provides a vehicle to secure state funding for these services. The funding is done by the MoJ. Funding is available only to recognized PSCA and LCA, in accordance with §66b para. 3 StPO, and for eligible victim survivors (detailed in “description” above). PSCA funding is based on annually issued contracts with selected organisations providing victim-support services. These organisations are expected to have Staff trained for PSCA. A updated list of accredited institution for each states is publicly available.³⁸ Remuneration is based on a catalogue for the corresponding profession and is handed it to the court. The secured funding stream ensures that court assistance can be provided to eligible victim-survivors (Bundesministerium für Justiz, 2024).

Lastly, acceptance among third parties has been highlighted as an important factor for PSCA. Interviews have highlighted the importance of the police, prosecutors and judges to cooperate. In the case of police officers, they can serve as a first point of contact with the victim support structure for victim-survivors. In such instances, the police are obliged to inform victim-survivors of their rights, one of which is the right to court assistance.³⁹ Furthermore, cooperation with the police and prosecution is required to ensure that the victims can be informed about any steps within the investigation process or the status of the perpetrator, especially in regard to custody-release. PSCAs rely on the cooperation of courts and judges

³⁸ For more details, see

<https://www.justiz.gv.at/service/opferhilfe-und-prozessbegleitung/prozessbegleitungseinrichtungen.2c94848535a081cf0135a4a0496e002d.de.html>

³⁹ As defined by §70 para. 1 & 2 StPO.

during the trial, for example when seeking to arrange a victim-friendly testimony, such as adversarial questioning according to § 165 para. 3 StPO. In regard to LCAs, LCA are also dependent on other stakeholder groups, especially prosecution and judges. Reform suggestions by the GSZs have highlighted, that this cooperation can be flawed where legal obligations are not clearly in place (Bundesverband der Gewaltschutzstellen, 2024). As such, well-functioning court assistance requires a degree of reliance on external actors, that at times goes beyond what is legally required and secured. Nonetheless, D1.3 interviews with PSCAs have generally indicated how court assistance is largely acknowledged and respected, thus enabling adequate support for victim-survivors.

Additionally, the standards for court assistance, in particular for PSCAs, are also of note. MoJ accredited PSCA can only be offered by victim-support organisations, which have an ongoing financing contract with the MoJ. These organisations have to provide holistic victim-support and cannot solely specialize on providing PSCA. Furthermore, staff working as PSCA are expected to undergo training for accreditation. For LCA, set standards only allow for practicing lawyers to provide LCA for clients. By doing so, court-assistance is meant to provide high quality support (Bundesministerium für Justiz, 2024).

Practical relevance

The practical relevance of this solution can be gauged by the extent to which its use is widespread. Usage statistics are available and indicate that while PSCA and LCA individually see diminishing or similar usage from 2013 to 2022, dual use, i.e. clients having both PS and LCA, has been increasing since 2013. From 3102 clients in 2013, victim survivors making use of both has reached 5415 in 2022. The total number of victim-survivors has risen from 6378 to 8960 in the same time period. More on this in the Graph below.

Graphic 3: Number of Person receiving PSCA or LSCA in criminal proceedings
(based on data published in Bundesministerium für Justiz, 2024)

As the activity report by the MoJ argues, a simple contrasting of total numbers of victim-survivors with PSCA and/or LCA clients to calculate the usage rate is not possible, as not all victim-survivors are eligible to receive PCA. Similarly, contrasting PSCA and/or LCA client numbers with the numbers of trials can be misleading, as single victim-survivors can have multiple trials. Consequently, information on usage rate is not available as of 2024 (Bundesministerium für Justiz, 2024). Nonetheless, usage rates amongst some victim support organisations are available, though the issue of unclear eligibility rates persist.⁴⁰

Data and information on the quality of court assistance is scantily available. An older national evaluation noted that PSCA implementation saw issues regarding access (especially amongst vulnerable groups, such as persons with a migration background, as well as persons with disabilities or mental health issues), issues with compensation, accessibility of information and cooperation between various actors (Haller et al, 2007). Evaluation by the GSZ Corinthia, which includes insights into PSCA, describes positive feedback of clients about the support during the reporting and subsequent court proceedings. Especially the continued support throughout the different steps was highly regarded (Gewaltschutzzentrum

⁴⁰ Examples include Gewaltschutzzentrum Wien, 2024; Gewaltschutzzentrum Burgenland, 2024; and Gewaltschutzzentrum Steiermark, 2024.

Kärnten 2019). D1.2 interviews underscored the importance of PSCA. Nonetheless, a recent assessment of the quality is difficult to make based on the lack of publicly available data.

Evidence and Data

Data and evaluations of PSCA and LCA are published by various sources. Noted in the chapter on GSZs, the MoJ publishes periodical reporting on the usage and funding of court assistance across Austria. The report covering the period from 2013-2022 provides a detailed statistical picture of PSCA and LCA usage – both in regards to financial and case data. Such information is gathered via the compensation procedure, as well as entries into the data-collection system of the judicial system (Verfahrensautomation Justiz) (Bundesministerium für Justiz, 2024). Information on PSCAs is also published yearly by various providers, such as GSZs. As noted above, these data points indicate that PSCA is increasingly seeing wider use.

Interviews with experts regarding PSCA have indicated, that court assistance has also seen evaluation on a regional and national level. This is done in parts during regular inter-organisational meetings, as well as internal evaluation projects. A regular platform are round tables held on state-level biannually since 2017.⁴¹ They include local stakeholders such as prosecutors, judges, representatives of regional victim support organisations, the police and the local bar association, as well as representatives of youth- and child services, ombudsman and other support organisations. Resulting reports are not made public.⁴²

On a national level, public research into the early implementation of PSCA is also available, namely by Haller and Hoffinger (2007), noting issues regarding access for vulnerable groups, remuneration and inter-sectoral cooperation. A more recent evaluation that included CA was done by the Commission Victim-protection and Perpetrator-work. It noted room for improvement regarding the inclusion in civil procedures. Austrian court assistance has also been reviewed internationally. The baseline GREVIO report on Austria, which ion particularly criticised eligibility concerns for children, which have since been addressed (Council of Europe, 2016). A new GREVIO report is underway for 2024 but has not been published at the time of writing.

⁴¹ Earlier Iteration of these round tables were held annually until 2015.

⁴² Information on these round tables and their content has been part of the D1.3 Interviews.

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2.2 Finland

Population surveys show that the majority of victims of domestic violence (DV) are women. Compared to men, the domestic violence experienced by women is also more long-term and it is recurring violence.

Gendered and Domestic Violence in Finland study was carried out in 2021 and found that the majority of women aged 16-74 and men between 18-74 reported experiencing some form of violence at some point in their lives. A total of 57 percent of women and 46 percent of men said they had experienced physical violence, threats, or sexual violence, while 34 percent of women and 18 percent of men experienced violence from a current or former partner.

According to Statistics Finland, in 2022 there were 11,800 victims of DV that came to the attention of the authorities, which is 7.9% more than the previous year. Of the victims of DV over the age of 18, 6,700 were women and 2,300 were men. 76% of those suspected of committing DV were men. (Official Statistics of Finland, 2022). However, the majority of DV does not come to the attention of the authorities: only about 10 percent of all violence (Danielsson & Näsi, 2019) and serious domestic violence (FRA, 2014) are reported to the police.

Researchers at Statistics Finland found that around one in ten victims report their experience of violence to the police. Only half of those who have experienced intimate partner violence had confided in someone about it, and less than a tenth had reported it to the authorities. According to this study, women tend to disclose incidents of violence more frequently than men, and older women more so than younger women (Attila et al., 2023).

The high rates of DV in Finland have sparked much public debate. How can one of the world's most equal countries be one of Europe's most violent for women at the same time? In research, this contradiction observed in different Nordic countries has been called the Nordic paradox of intimate partner violence (Lyömätön Linja Espoossa ry and NYTKIS ry, 2023).

DV is described as a wicked problem for which there is no single professional solution (Rittel & Webber, 1973). Intervening in DV and breaking its cycle requires cooperation especially between social work, healthcare, the police, and support organisations that help the parties involved in the violence.

In Finland, the responsibility for organizing public healthcare, social welfare and rescue services is now placed at wellbeing services counties. In addition, the City of Helsinki is

responsible for organizing health, social and rescue services within its own area. The key objective of the reform is to improve the availability and quality of basic public services throughout Finland and to increase the cooperation of social and health services.

In Finland, violence prevention related responsibilities lie on the government, wellbeing services counties,⁴³ and municipalities. Wellbeing services counties have the most responsibilities on an operational level of preventing and combating violence. Municipalities have an obligation to promote health and welfare, and therefore violence prevention work should start already in schools, daycare facilities, youth work etc. NGOs play a significant role in intervening violence and organizing support services.

In 2022, THL published national guidelines/recommendations to support the municipalities and wellbeing services counties to prevent and combat domestic violence. Guidelines include two parts: 1) coordination of the structures for violence prevention (strategic part) and 2) organizing the services and examples of good practices from the field (October & Laitinen, 2022).

Finland is committed to the Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combatting violence against women and domestic violence (Istanbul Convention). It was ratified in Finland on 1 August 2015. The Council of Europe's Group of Experts on Action against Violence against Women and Domestic Violence (GREVIO) published its first evaluation report on Finland on 2019. The report analyses the implementation of the provisions of the Istanbul Convention on preventing and combatting violence against women and domestic violence in Finland.

GREVIO acknowledges many measures that have already been taken or are in process. GREVIO considers that there is a political will to implement the Convention. GREVIO also mentions the appointment of the Committee for Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence (NAPE) and the opening of a 24-hour telephone service called Nollalinja. In addition, GREVIO appreciates the progress made in the provision of services for victims and commends the comprehensive reform of the legislation concerning sexual offences.

⁴³ The Wellbeing Service Counties are the organisational, region units responsible for health care and social service provision in Finland. A total of 21 counties, as well as 2 autonomous regions, ensure county-wide support. For more details, see <https://stm.fi/en/wellbeing-services-counties>

At the evaluation report (2019), GREVIO points out that several issues, including especially matters concerning the training of professionals, need to be addressed. In Finland, it is possible to graduate as a social worker without having acquired a basic knowledge of DV (Niklander, Notko & Husso, 2019). GREVIO (2019) also encourages Finland to

- recognise, encourage and support women's NGOs active in preventing and combating violence against women, including community-based grass roots movements of migrant women;
- ensure the provision of specialist women's support services with a gendered approach, providing comprehensive, immediate, short- and long-term support to all female victims of violence and their children in Finland, and introduce the practice of referral to such services by law enforcement agencies;
- Higher degrees of awareness of the different forms of violence against women, and cultural sensitivity towards the specific situation of women from national minorities such as the Sámi as well as other distinct groups of women in Finland, are also needed.

GREVIO has identified several barriers faced by women from national minorities, women with disabilities and women exposed to other intersectional discrimination when seeking help for different forms of violence. According to GREVIO, there is general ignorance among the authorities and service providers about the specific cultural characteristics, limitations and obstacles that Sámi and Roma women and women at risk of honour-related violence face when seeking protection from violence. Moreover, women with disabilities or women who belong to sexual or gender minorities also face barriers in seeking help (GREVIO, 2019).

In March 2022, the Committee for Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence (NAPE) published the Istanbul Convention's Second Action Plan for 2022-2025. This action plan includes long-term goals and 36 measures. The plan has three key cross-cutting goals aimed at:

- strengthening the gender perspective and intersectionality in the implementation of the Istanbul Convention
- strengthening and consolidating inter-sectoral and multi-professional cooperation, as well as the prevention and combatting of violence against women and domestic violence at all levels, and

- improving the recognition and intervention of violence against women and domestic violence (Finnish Government, 2023).

In 2019, an Action plan for preventing violence against children 2020-2025 (Violent-free childhood) was published. The Action plan, which was considered as a good practice example by WHO, has 93 measures. The aim of the Action plan is to prevent all kinds of violence against children aged 0-17. In addition to prevention, it also covers minimizing harmful effects and providing care to victims. The Action plan covers violence against children in a vulnerable position, such as disabled children and young people, and children belonging to ethnic groups, as well as FGM, honour-related violence and human trafficking. A wide group of experts from different organisations, several ministries and non-governmental organisations participated in the planning and implementation of the plan (Finnish Government, 2023).

This report examines good practices in Finland, which aim to improve access to support services for those who have experienced violence, perpetrators of violence and those exposed to violence. In this report, we present the violence screening tools for healthcare professionals, the operation of support services, and different types of multi-professional work methods.

1.1.1 Solution 1: MARACs

1.1.1.1 Description

MARAC (multi-agency risk assessment conference) is a two-stage risk assessment method for repeated intimate partner violence. The method was developed in UK. The purpose of the method is to systemically and multi-professionally improve victim's safety (Robinson, 2004) by information sharing, coordinating safety, and action planning that links with other relevant agencies (McLaughlin et al., 2018). The method has been used in Finland for over ten years. A one-year pilot of the MARAC method was launched in Finland in 2010 and Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) was responsible for coordinating and evaluating the project. It was later continued as a project and nowadays it is a permanent approach (Piispa & Lappalainen, 2014; THL, 2024a).

1.1.1.1.1 *Background and Aim*

MARAC in Finland consists ideally of two phases. Firstly, the risk assessment is performed as a form of an interview with the client (in shelter services, social services, police etc.). At the police departments, police officers can ask a professional part of the MARAC, e.g., a psychiatric nurse or a social worker of a multi-professional Anchor team, to fill out the form together with the victim.

In the first phase a professional fills in a risk assessment questionnaire (DASH form) together with a victim. If the evaluation of the questionnaire indicates a high risk, the victim is asked for consent to take the case to MARAC. In addition, the victim gives their consent that certain authorities and NGOs can be present in the MARAC meeting and that information about them that is essential for improving security and safety can be used in MARAC risk assessment work. The victim chooses from a list which authorities and agencies can handle their case and exchange information with each other.

In the second part, if the client has given their consent and if there is an operative MARAC group in the client's area, the authority or agency that completes the MARAC(/DASH) form sends the form to the secretary of the MARAC group. From there, a code that conceals the client's personal details and the score of the MARAC risk assessment is sent to the members of MARAC group.

When a police officer of a MARAC team receives the emailed code regarding a new client, they verify the information about the victim and the suspect using the police information registers. They also check the client's history in the police registers and whether either one of the parties emerges from the register in relation to house calls. The police officer summarizes the information and records a plan of measures they would recommend to the victim. One such recommendation is reporting an offence and claiming for a restraining order.

In the MARAC meeting the person who guided the victim to MARAC will introduce the matter and the completed form to the MARAC team. Each professional who participates in the meeting presents the information gained about the case and a proposal for measures. If a victim wants to participate in the meeting, they can tell their feelings about the situation and the type of support they wish to have. After that, a proposal for actions is agreed upon and discussed with the victim. Social worker can assist the victim in economic matters and finding an accommodation or shelter.

The person who has completed the risk assessment and guided the victim to MARAC is responsible for monitoring the victim's situation. A contact person is in touch with the victim at least twice, usually during the next two months. The follow-up includes calling the client, asking about their situation, whether they have continued using the offered services, whether they have been visiting a psychiatric nurse or counsellor, and how the child welfare is working along.

States that have ratified the Istanbul Convention (Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence) have been set several legislative and operational obligations to combat DV and strengthen victims' safety. DV risk assessment is one of these obligations. According to Article 51 of the Convention, the authorities are obliged to carry out a risk assessment in cases of DV to assess the severity and frequency of the violence and the risk of death, manage the risks and provide a victim with security and support through coordinated actions. The explanatory document of the Istanbul Agreement specifies that the risk assessment obligation is not limited to the police, but also applies to other relevant authorities (CETS, 2011).

At its best, DV risk assessment initiates a multi-professional process where the relevant actors and professionals can form a comprehensive picture of the victim's situation with the help of risk assessment tools and other professional work methods, knowledge, and skills. In this way, the victim gets help from professionals and authorities as quickly as possible, and a comprehensive safety plan can be drawn up for the victim (THL, 2024a).

Most of the MARAC groups meet once a month and they have one to five client cases per meeting. In the MARAC groups there are members from at least police, social work, child protection, local shelter, and public health care.

1.1.1.1.2 Implementation and Practice

The Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) coordinates MARAC nationally and the local MARAC groups are the owners at the local level. Once a year, THL organizes a national meeting for MARAC group coordinators and is responsible for training the key professionals when a new MARAC group is established. After that, the local professionals are responsible for the training. THL also trains shelter professionals to use MARAC.

Successful cooperation with social work and health care can produce valuable information about victims' and perpetrators' mental health problems, substance abuse issues, problems

related to medication, negative life changes, family problems, violent attitudes and thoughts and about other things that can be dis-inhibitors, (or provocative factors) and de-stabilizers. However, the exchange of information is strictly regulated by the law.

About half of the MARAC groups have a steering group to support their work. All the steering groups monitor and give support and guidance to the local MARAC groups. The tasks for steering group are e.g., planning how to cover the whole region, estimating the amount of MARAC groups needed, ensuring necessary training on risk assessment, communication activities (regions leaflets, intranet etc.), monitoring the work, ensuring the groups' function, ensuring that all the right actors/organisations are represented and taking part in the MARAC conferences. Moreover, the steering groups can support MARAC groups e.g., in helping groups to solve problems, and planning special support to ensure group members' well-being at work.

1.1.1.1.3 Strengths and Weaknesses

In large cities/wellbeing services counties, social services may be divided among several agents and districts. Therefore, there may be challenges to get a suitable public servant capable for decision-making in the meetings. MARAC should offer clients practical help, which requires that the meeting involves those agencies and individuals who can make decisions that can be implemented for instance in relation to victim's housing. At some locations, social work services may be divided into several sectors. When there is a need to make decisions over the client's required services, a social worker responsible for the client's case and representing the client's district should be present in the meeting. If the client moves to another area, even within a city, their social worker will also change to another person. In this case, challenges can arise in terms of monitoring the client's situation and building trust.

Police departments do not have a national and uniform operating model or documentation method for systematic risk assessment. Differences in procedures and documentation methods cause inconsistency in the risk assessment process. The documentation of risk information may also vary: risk factors identified during the house call may be documented e.g., in the crime report or in the log of the emergency centre's information system. Crime detectives enter a considerable amount of information into preliminary investigation documents (e.g., interrogation forms) that could be regarded as useful for risk assessment. This information does not move from these documents and interrogation narratives to the

police's digital information systems unless the detectives do it themselves (Bradley et al., 2020).

These inconsistencies can weaken the smooth functioning of the risk assessment process and the exchange of information from the field police officers to the crime investigation teams and multi-professional teams. As a result of the inconsistency practices, there is a risk on the part of police departments that only a part of the cases and the cases that are already assessed as serious end up being assessed by the MARAC.

If DV risk assessment is not clearly written into the police's task description, or if the police have not received training or a tool for risk assessment, risk assessment is personal and case specific. However, in the current in-service training of the Finnish police, competence needs are considered, and police officers at the team leader level receive additional training in risk assessment.

In addition, Walklate et al. (2021) note that the ongoing challenges of MARAC methods are the appropriate identification of (high-risk) cases, the representation of appropriate agencies at these conferences, managing the volume of work, and appropriate action planning.

1.1.1.2 Justification

MARAC is effective in preventing serious domestic violence in Finland by fostering a collaborative, informed, and proactive approach to risk assessment and intervention. MARAC brings together representatives from various agencies, including police, social services, health services, housing, and non-governmental organisations, to share information and develop coordinated action plans. This ensures a comprehensive approach to assessing and managing risk. By pooling information from multiple sources, MARAC provides a more complete picture of the risks faced by victims of domestic violence. This holistic view allows for better identification of high-risk cases and more tailored interventions. In addition, the coordinated efforts of different agencies result in more effective safety planning for victims. Actions such as implementing restraining orders, providing emergency housing, and ensuring access to support services can be quickly and efficiently arranged.

Moreover, MARAC facilitates early identification of escalating risk, allowing for timely interventions before violence becomes more severe. This proactive approach is crucial in preventing serious harm or fatalities. Regular MARAC meetings and follow-up procedures

ensure that the actions agreed upon are implemented and monitored. This accountability helps in maintaining the momentum of protective measures and adapting plans as necessary.

MARAC also addresses the behaviour of perpetrators by involving agencies that can provide interventions aimed at reducing the risk they pose. This can include police monitoring, probation services, and access to perpetrator programs. The MARAC process prioritizes the needs and safety of the victim. This victim-centred approach ensures that all actions taken are focused on reducing risk and providing the necessary support for recovery and safety. MARAC processes can be adapted to consider the specific cultural and community contexts in Finland, ensuring that interventions are appropriate and effective for diverse populations.

In Finland, the implementation of MARAC includes training for professionals across different sectors. This increases awareness and understanding of domestic violence, risk factors, and appropriate responses, thereby improving the overall effectiveness of interventions.

However, the task of combatting DV has been reduced from other multi-professional mechanisms (Anchor teams), on the basis that MARAC handles the field of DV. However, only a small proportion of violence cases are referred to MARACs and its resources are not sufficient to take on mild cases of DV that other multi-professional mechanisms (Anchor teams) have handled in the past. In addition, one key limitation of the multidisciplinary risk assessment is that MARAC is intended solely for addressing intimate partner violence. Other cases of DV may therefore be left entirely without a multidisciplinary risk assessment. For example, DV committed by an adult child against their parent may not necessarily undergo such a risk assessment unless the police in charge of the criminal investigation know to consult, for instance, the Anchor team.

1.1.1.2.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

Comprehensive legislations

In Finland, the implementation of Multi-Agency Risk Assessment Conferences (MARAC) is primarily supported by legislation related to domestic violence and child protection. The following legislation collectively support the collaborative and multi-agency approach necessary for the effective functioning of MARACs in Finland:

- The Act on the Status and Rights of Social Welfare Clients (812/2000) includes provisions for the cooperation between different authorities to ensure the welfare of individuals, which underpins the multi-agency approach of MARAC.

- The Child Welfare Act (417/2007) mandates cooperation between different authorities and organisations to protect children and ensure their welfare. MARAC meetings often involve discussions about the safety of children in domestic violence situations, thus aligning with the requirements of this act.
- The Act on Social Welfare (1301/2014) outlines the responsibilities of municipalities in providing social welfare services, including support for victims of domestic violence, and emphasizes the importance of inter-agency cooperation.
- The Act on Restraining Orders (898/1998) provides mechanisms for protecting individuals from domestic violence and supports the use of restraining orders. MARAC processes often involve discussions around the implementation of restraining orders to protect victims.
- The Police Act (872/2011) and The Criminal Investigation Act (805/2011) include provisions for police involvement in protecting victims of domestic violence and working in cooperation with other agencies, which is a core aspect of the MARAC process.

Government commitment and support

In addition to the above-mentioned laws and policies steering the inter-agency cooperation and providing a legal basis for sharing information and working together, the Finnish government supports the effective implementation of MARAC through various measures that ensure coordination, funding, training, policy framework, and monitoring.

First, the government allocates funding to local authorities and to some non-governmental organisations (NGOs) that are involved in MARAC processes. This funding helps ensure that agencies have the necessary resources to participate effectively. For example, the Ministry of Justice and the Funding Centre for Social Affairs and Health (STEA) allocate funding to the Victim Support Service. In addition, shelter services receive funding from the government. On the other hand, AA (Anonymous Alcoholics) does not receive external funding. There are conditions and restrictions associated with applying for state funding. Organisations that receive grants must be able to report how the funds have been used. Thus, the organisation can decide relatively independently how the granted funds are utilized, but in accordance with what was described in the application. In STEA's performance evaluation, emphasis is placed on reaching the target group, achieving the goals and results described in the grant applications, and verifying the outcomes achieved. Second, the government funds and

organizes training programs for professionals from various sectors (e.g., police, social workers, health care providers) to ensure they have the skills and knowledge needed to participate effectively in MARAC. Third, there are national bodies or committees that oversee the implementation of MARAC, ensuring consistency and providing guidance to local MARACs. On the regional level, there are coordinators who assist local MARACs in implementing best practices and addressing challenges. Fourth, the performance of MARACs is monitored through regular reporting and evaluation, ensuring accountability and continuous improvement. Moreover, collecting and analysing data on domestic violence and MARAC outcomes helps in monitoring the effectiveness of the interventions and making necessary adjustments. Fifth, the government develops and implements national action plans or strategies that include specific measures to support MARAC and improve responses to domestic violence. Last, the government ensures the availability of comprehensive support services for victims of domestic violence, including shelters, counselling, and legal assistance which are crucial components of the MARAC process.

Sufficient resources

Overall, while there is significant support for MARACs in Finland, the sufficiency of resources can vary by region and over time. Ensuring that MARACs have adequate and consistent resources is crucial for their ability to effectively tackle serious domestic violence.

1.1.1.2.2 Practical relevance

MARACs in Finland are likely to be effective in prohibiting and protecting against domestic violence by providing a coordinated, comprehensive, and victim-centred approach. Their success is supported by evidence from other countries and is contingent on adequate resources, continuous training, and strong inter-agency collaboration. The effectiveness of MARAC in prohibiting or protecting against DV can be evaluated through various indicators and outcomes: studies and reports from other countries where MARACs are implemented, such as the UK, indicate significant reductions in risk for victims of domestic violence. In UK, MARACs enabled the agencies to assist victims more efficiently through enhanced information sharing. In a study conducted in 2006, MARACs improved victims' safety as statistics revealed that 6 in 10 victims had not been revictimized (Robinson, 2006). In parallel, a study conducted in 2007 showed that more than 4 in 10 victims reported no further violence one year after intervention of the MARAC. Nearly all victims acknowledged the importance of having multiagency support once they were ready to change their situation (Robinson &

Tregidga, 2007). In Finland, similar positive outcomes are expected, with enhanced safety planning and coordinated interventions reducing the likelihood of re-victimisation. A study conducted during the years 2010-2014 showed that after the implementation of MARAC, the police received significantly fewer reports of violence caused by the same partner compared to the corresponding period before its implementation. Within six months after MARAC, 15 percent had filed a report of IPV by the same perpetrator, whereas just under 60 percent had filed such reports within the year prior to the risk assessment. Within a year after MARAC, 17 percent had reported new violent crimes to the police. Based on the data, it seems that those who experienced violence *within* six months and *after* six months are not the same individuals. According to the criminal report data, typical situations in which violence reoccurred after the six-month mark occurred when a restraining order ended or when legal proceedings related to earlier violent crimes were approaching, triggering the perpetrator to act again. In these cases, physical violence did not occur continuously throughout the observation period but started later, after the six-month mark. In a longer-term follow-up, the recurrence of violence is more common when considering all those who had reported violent incidents to the police within 12 months after MARAC, but still, for over 70 percent, the violence did not recur after MARAC. (Piispa & Lappinen, 2014)

Through coordinated efforts, MARACs ensure that victims receive comprehensive safety plans tailored to their specific needs. This includes immediate protective measures like restraining orders and long-term support such as counselling and housing. Moreover, MARACs facilitate the sharing of critical information among agencies, leading to more informed decision-making and comprehensive support plans. This collaboration helps in identifying high-risk cases and ensuring timely interventions. The multi-agency approach ensures that all relevant agencies work together, reducing the chances of victims falling through the cracks. This coordinated response is crucial for addressing the complex needs of domestic violence victims.

Victims engaged with MARACs benefit from a wide range of support services, from emergency housing to legal aid and healthcare. This holistic support system enhances their ability to escape abusive situations and rebuild their lives. MARACs empower victims by ensuring their voices are heard and their needs are prioritized in safety planning and interventions. Evidence suggests that MARACs can significantly reduce repeat incidents of domestic violence (Piispa & Lappinen, 2014; Piispa & October, 2017). By addressing the root

causes and providing comprehensive support, MARACs help break the cycle of abuse. Regular follow-up meetings and monitoring ensure that interventions are effective and that any emerging risks are promptly addressed.

Nevertheless, while MARACs are effective, their success depends on adequate funding and resources. Ensuring consistent support across all regions is necessary to maintain their effectiveness. In addition, continuous training for professionals and raising awareness about MARACs within communities can enhance their effectiveness. Ensuring that all relevant parties are knowledgeable about the process and their roles is crucial.

Empirical evidence from countries with established MARAC systems, like the UK, shows positive outcomes in terms of victim safety and reduction in repeat victimisation. However, ongoing assessment and adaptation are essential in Finland to address any challenges and ensure the continued effectiveness of MARACs in safeguarding victims of domestic violence.

In UK, there has been a discussion about the risks of harm to victims and witnesses who have an insecure immigration status. The report 'Safe to share? Report on Liberty and Southall Black Sisters' super-complaint on policing and immigration status' (2021) points out that the risk for e.g., deportation of vulnerable individuals may arise from information sharing about people at high risk of domestic abuse, within formal and informal multi-agency discussions, e.g., at MARACs. The report notes the concerns about the police prioritizing immigration enforcement over safeguarding and the investigation of crime.

Nevertheless, clients can decide for themselves which authorities and actors they want to participate in the risk assessment conference. Therefore, a client can decide that they do not want the police to participate in the conference. In this way, the client receives multi-professional support, even though they do not want to involve the police in their case. The police can also participate in the meeting by telling the client about police's possibilities to intervene in violence and protect the victim on a general level, but then leave the meeting before the client starts to discuss their case with other agencies.

1.1.1.2.3 Evidence and Data

As of now, there is limited specific empirical data published on the effectiveness of MARACs in Finland, given that the adoption and implementation of MARAC can vary across different regions and countries. A study from 2010-2014 found that after the implementation of MARAC, the police received significantly fewer reports of violence by the same partner

compared to the period before. Six months after MARAC, 15 percent had filed reports of IPV, compared to nearly 60 percent in the previous year. After one year, 17 percent reported new violent crimes. Recurring violence often followed the end of restraining orders or upcoming legal proceedings, but in over 70 percent of cases, violence did not recur after MARAC (Piispa & Lappinen, 2014). In addition, the studies conducted in UK (e.g., Robinson, 2004; Robinson & Tregidga, 2007) support the effectiveness of MARACs in preventing serious violence.

The Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) and various municipalities have been involved in piloting and implementing MARACs. These efforts are supported by the Finnish government, indicating a commitment to adopting proven international practices. Feedback from professionals involved in MARACs, such as police officers, social workers, and healthcare providers, indicates that the multi-agency approach leads to better outcomes for victims.

1.1.1.2.4 Context of the Solution

MARAC complements existing policies, regulations, strategies, and practices of various actors in the field of domestic violence prevention in several ways. It achieves this through integration with existing frameworks, enhancing collaboration, and improving the effectiveness of interventions.

Legal frameworks

The MARAC process aligns with the Child Welfare Act by ensuring the protection and welfare of children in DV situations. MARAC meetings often consider the safety of children, and the process facilitates mandatory reporting and intervention requirements. MARACs operate within the framework of the Act on Social Welfare, which mandates the provision of social services and support for victims of DV. The multi-agency approach ensures that victims receive comprehensive and coordinated social welfare services. Additionally, MARAC complements the use of restraining orders by identifying high-risk victims who may need such protective measures and facilitating their implementation through coordinated efforts among agencies.

Enhancement of existing strategies

MARACs contribute to the objectives of national action plans (e.g., the Action Plan for Combating Violence against Women) by providing a structured and effective response to high-risk DV cases, thereby reducing incidents, and enhancing victim protection. MARACs support public health strategies by addressing the health impacts of domestic violence,

facilitating access to healthcare services, and coordinating with health professionals to ensure victims receive appropriate medical care and support.

Complementing multi-agency approach

MARACs enhance police practices by providing detailed risk assessments and comprehensive safety plans, enabling more effective protection and intervention. Social workers, on the other hand, benefit from the multi-agency approach of MARACs, which ensures that they have access to relevant information and can coordinate with other agencies to provide holistic support to victims. MARACs ensure that healthcare providers are part of the information-sharing network, allowing them to better understand the risks faced by their patients and to provide appropriate medical and psychological support. NGOs that provide support services to victims are integral to the MARAC process. Their involvement ensures that victims receive continuous and comprehensive support, from emergency shelter to long-term counselling and legal aid.

Regular MARAC meetings ensure ongoing communication and coordination among all involved agencies, fostering a culture of collaboration and mutual support. Continuous training for professionals across different sectors ensures that all actors involved in MARACs understand the process, their roles, and the importance of collaboration. Regular workshops and seminars facilitate knowledge sharing and the dissemination of best practices among MARAC participants. The development of standardized protocols and guidelines for MARAC meetings ensures consistency and clarity in the process, making it easier for various agencies to integrate MARAC practices into their existing workflows. Ongoing evaluation and monitoring of MARACs help to identify strengths and areas for improvement, ensuring that the process continues to align with and complement existing policies and practices.

1.1.1.2.5 Unintended Consequences and Risks

Implementation of the MARAC in Finland can bring significant benefits in addressing DV, but it also carries unintended consequences and risks that need to be managed.

For instance, the additional responsibilities of participating in MARAC meetings and follow-up actions can strain the resources of agencies already dealing with high workloads, potentially leading to burnout among professionals. Agencies might need to divert resources from other important areas to support MARAC activities, which could impact their ability to deliver other services effectively.

Furthermore, the process of sharing sensitive information across multiple agencies can raise concerns about confidentiality and data protection (see. e.g., Kurvinen et al., 2023). Ensuring that data is handled securely, and that privacy is maintained is crucial. In parallel, victims may be hesitant to share personal information if they fear it might be widely disseminated, which could affect their willingness to engage with services.

Some unintended consequences may arise from regional disparities. The effectiveness of MARACs might vary across different regions due to differences in resources, training, and commitment from local agencies, leading to inconsistent levels of support for victims. Without standardized procedures and protocols, the practices and effectiveness of MARACs can differ, resulting in uneven protection and support for victims.

One crucial risk is the overemphasis on high-risk cases that may lead to the neglect of low-risk cases. Focusing primarily on high-risk cases might lead to insufficient attention and resources for lower-risk cases, which could escalate if not properly managed. Determining which cases are included in MARAC can be challenging, potentially leaving some at-risk individuals without the necessary support.

Furthermore, effective MARAC implementation requires seamless communication among various agencies. Any breakdown in communication can hinder the coordination of efforts and the timely provision of support. Agencies involved in MARAC might have different priorities and mandates, which can lead to conflicts or misalignments in objectives and actions. Moreover, complex safety plans involving multiple agencies might be harder to implement effectively, particularly if coordination is poor.

The legal framework governing data sharing between agencies must be robust to prevent legal challenges and ensure compliance with privacy laws. Professionals may face ethical dilemmas when balancing the need to share information for risk assessment with the need to protect client confidentiality (see e.g., Kurvinen et al., 2023). Establishing standardized protocols for MARAC operations and clear agreements on data sharing practices can help ensure consistency and clarity in the process and management of the privacy concerns. Providing ongoing training for all professionals involved in MARAC can enhance their understanding of the process and improve inter-agency collaboration.

The risk assessment procedure must also consider the fact that every decision or measure taken by the authority can increase the risk of violence beyond the momentary level. The

involvement of multiple agencies in a MARAC might inadvertently alert perpetrators, leading to potential retaliation against victims.

1.1.2 Solution 2: Anchor teams

1.1.2.1 Description

The purpose of the Anchor team model is to promote the well-being of children, adolescents, and families at an early stage and to prevent crimes. Locally, Anchor teams can also work with DV cases. Anchor work is carried out by a multi-professional Anchor team. The team members are experts from the police, social, health and youth services. The composition of the team may vary on a case-by-case basis.⁴⁴

1.1.2.1.1 Background and Aim

In 1977, the first social worker was placed in the sobering facility of the Lahti Police Department. Sobriety facilities are units where intoxicated people can safely sober up. Cooperation between the police and social services accelerated in the 1980s, when so-called police-social work activities were established. Since the turn of the millennium, the cooperation between the police and social work has expanded significantly. Various national and local political programs, plans and strategies have influenced the forms of cooperation. The police wanted real-time support measures alongside the criminal justice system. In addition, the police shared a common view that crimes can be partly prevented by early intervention, in which social services play a very central role (Heino et al., 2005).

In 2004, the so-called Anchor project was launched in Hämeenlinna, which is a medium-sized city in the province of Kanta-Häme. In 2004, there were about 47,000 inhabitants in Hämeenlinna. The Anchor model was created in response to the authorities' initiative and needs. Its goal was to strengthen the cooperation of several authorities at the regional level to effectively and immediately intervene in the issues of adolescents and children who were at risk of being marginalized. Soon the anchor model became a national model. Today, Anchor work is done in multi-professional teams consisting of professionals from the police, social services, healthcare, and youth.⁴⁵

Nowadays, the Anchor work is a national model. There are Anchor teams working almost in 40 locations in Finland. The goals of co-operation are early intervention in the criminal behaviour of minors, comprehensive investigation of the young person's life situation and their need for help, referral to the right help and support, quick intervention in DV, and

⁴⁴ For more information, see <https://ankkuritoiminta.fi/-/ankkuritoiminta-kehitty>.

⁴⁵ For more information, see <https://rikoksentorjunta.fi/en/anchor-model>.

increasing internal security through multi-professional cooperation.⁴⁶ However, lately the focus has been shifted to promotion of the wellbeing of young people and to prevention of adolescent criminality and extremism, and the resources to intervene DV vary by location (Bradley et al., 2020).

Multidisciplinary cooperation enables professionals to serve the client comprehensively. The work is based on the "one-stop shop" principle. While the police of the preliminary investigation units investigate the crimes, Anchor teams' police officers, health and social care professionals investigate the situation of the clients and their families more broadly from the perspective of wellbeing and needs. After assessing the clients' needs, they are referred to other services, such as victim support services, shelter services, NGOs, mental health services, etc. The benefits of this holistic approach and inter-agency cooperation are particularly visible in challenging situations where the client suffers from multiple problems, such as DV, substance abuse and mental health problems (Bradley et al., 2020).

The Anchor teams do not only seem to shape the cooperation between social work, health care and the police within the team, but its effects are wider in the entire police department by building bridges and intermediating cooperation between the uniformed police officer and social work in general. The threshold for disclosing informal information is lower if the police officers can disclose the information to the Anchor team's police officer. By doing this, they do not have to assess the possibilities provided by the law for the exchange of information between the police and the other authorities. The Anchor team's police officer, on the other hand, is experienced in evaluating the possibilities of handling information within a multi-professional team (ibid.).

In addition to the fact that Anchor teams can combat criminal phenomena more effectively, Anchor teams also offer their members collegial support, which is considered to have a positive and very important effect on well-being at work. Collegial support has been described as an opportunity not only to share one's expertise for common use, but also as freedom to work as one's own person and an opportunity to share responsibility. The promoters of collegial support are shared rules and values, good interaction, and respect for other professional skills. In contrast, inflexibility, inability to cooperate and remote work may be factors preventing collegial support (Peltonen & Pöllänen, 2021).

⁴⁶ For more information, see <https://ankkuritoiminta.fi/toiminta>

1.1.2.1.2 *Implementation and Practice*

The multi-agency cooperation and the exchange of information between the police, social services and health care are the core of Anchor model. The work of Anchor teams is based on an agreement between the police and the city. Each agency provides its own funding. In early years, the establishment of Anchor work as a permanent function required a common will of municipalities and regional councils (Bradley et al., 2020).

One of the significant results of Anchor's work is better information exchange, trust, and mutual knowledge between partners. Effective communication and information exchange are based on the law and agreements between the police and the city. In parallel with the observations of Goldman et al. (2010), if the members of the Anchor team work in the same office, collaboration goes more smoothly. Regularly offered personnel work guidance clarifies the team members' professional roles and strengthens their professional identity. The cooperation of the authorities improves the problem-solving ability and the ability to better consider the special characteristics of each victim (Bradley et al., 2020.).

The information-exchange between the authorities is regulated by the law. According to the law, social workers can report their information to the police on their own initiative based on the child's best interest or a very important private or public interest. Social services also have the right to notify the police on their own initiative when they are trying to prevent an act that threatens life or health. (Act on the Status and Rights of Social Care Clients Section 18). Child welfare authorities have the right to request information from the police, e.g., about criminal information concerning guardians (Act on the Status and Rights of Social Care Clients Section 20), e.g., when considering whether the child is in a safe environment in their family. In addition, the police are obliged to make a child protection report to social work if there are concerns about the child's well-being or safety (Child Welfare Act Section 25).

Anchor work is coordinated nationwide. The steering group consists of representatives from several institution, such as the Ministry of the Interior, the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, and the Ministry of Education and Culture, the Police Board etc. Among other things, the purpose of the steering group is to coordinate the Anchor work and monitor the consistency, availability, quality, and effectiveness of the work locally and regionally, as well as to address possible problems (Ankkuritoiminta, 2020.). At the beginning of 2021, a common 'extranet' for all Anchor team operators was introduced. The purpose of the extranet is to collect information about the scope of the operation, customers and the channels through which

clients come and to which they are directed. The information collected under data protection is anonymous and it is used to improve the Anchor work (Hämäläinen, 2022.).

To develop the Anchor model, the Ministry of the Interior (2022) has prepared a Manual on Multi-professional Anchor work. The purpose of the Manual is to support the implementation, development, and evaluation of Anchor work activities in Finland. The goal is to guide, support and unify the Anchor work so that (young) people have equal opportunities for services nationally and that (young) people do not find themselves in an unequal position in terms of services. Although the newest version of the Manual on the Multi-professional Anchor work emphasizes the prevention of youth crime, with the prevention of domestic violence being less emphasized, the social workers working under the Anchor team still have another role. They act as representatives of social welfare in crimes where the suspect is a minor and they are present during the interrogation of the young person. In addition, they can act as members of MARAC. Moreover, the Anchor teams are still allowed to work in cooperation to intervene DV, and in some locations the teams continue work in this field actively (Bradley et al., 2020).

According to Niklander et al. (2019), the critical points of multi-professional cooperation are information flow and information sharing, functioning institutional practices, commitment of organisations and management level, finding common goals and a common language, knowledge of the responsibilities, duties and tasks of different actors, and mutual respect.

The interviews conducted in the IMPRODOVA project brought up similar observations regarding the creation of mutual trust among the Anchor team members. The interviewees identified five important aspects: first, the background organisations of Anchor work have made formal agreements of the cooperation. Second, the legislation forms the formal limits and restrictions to the work, but the Anchor team members are allowed to do the fine-tuning themselves. Third, the supervisors of Anchor team members oversee the high-level policies. Fourth, a team benefits from having a leader/coordinator, even though every professional has their own supervisors in their own organisations. Fifth, the formation of the common spirit and trust of the Anchor team members and its maintenance is considered important. There are well-established methods for this, and everybody must have a common vision of the importance of the work. Such clear formal arrangements and the acknowledged importance of mutual trust may reduce the uncertainty and the feeling of risk regarding information-sharing among the Anchor team members.

1.1.2.1.3 *Strengths and Weaknesses*

An Anchor team may lower the threshold for victims of violence to apply for the social and health service they need, because they can get advice and guidance from professionals who, if the victim so wishes, can familiarize themselves with the criminal case concerning the victim.

Crime detectives often observe or hear, for example, in connection with the questioning, things about the client's life, the solution of which may require multi-professional cooperation. In connection with the interrogation, the crime detectives can tell the client about the services of the Anchor team. The crime detectives can consult with the Anchor team and advise the victim to meet the Anchor team's social worker or psychiatric nurse if needed. With the client's consent, either of these two professionals can also be present during the interrogation. The Anchor team is experienced in referring clients, for example, to anti-violence work or a shelter (Bradley et al., 2020).

The Anchor team also dismantles traditional occupational cultures and thinking models, which in the past could have acted as an obstacle to effective cooperation. Notko et al. (2021) state that when an issue is situated and understood within a single professional taxonomy, for example as a crime or a non-crime, other possible interpretations of the situation are usually left out or not recognized at all, as they remain outside the professional field as irrelevant problems. Moreover, a strong profession is defined by its own disciplinary knowledge base, distinctive perspective, unique problems and solutions, and relative autonomy. Paradoxically, all this makes the profession weak for interprofessional collaboration. The domains of issues outside one's own profession are not considered necessary, and therefore do not act as a motive for action (ibid.).

Heinonen, in turn, argues how the criminal process in Finland utilizes the 'favor defensionis' principle, according to which there must be strong evidence against the suspect and whenever there is uncertainty about the suspect's guilt, the case is decided in the suspect's favor. Although a child's best interest must be considered, it is not the guiding principle when assessing someone's guilt in a criminal trial. On the contrary, in Finnish child protection, a child's best interest and the right for special protection are central principles (Heinonen, 2015). The Anchor team model builds a bridge between these two approaches, by aiming to prevent crime and support the well-being of families.

The presence of a psychiatric nurse in an Anchor team is important. A nurse is easier to approach for many victims and clients because some clients may have prejudices against police or social workers or may fear punishment or custody of the children. Therefore, it may be easier for clients to talk to a specially trained nurse, even if they openly concede their cooperation with a social worker and a police officer. (P017, P018) In some Anchor teams, a psychiatric nurse can participate in the DV interrogations with the consent of the client. In addition, to get more information about the client's well-being, the psychiatric nurse can meet the client a few times privately. Moreover, a psychiatric nurse is trained to assess the client's emotional shock and acute crisis disorder, as well as the client's functional capacity and endurance to go through things in meetings. A psychiatric nurse can also manage the client's connections to healthcare services (Bradley et al., 2020; Järvenpää & Nurminen, 2016).

The cooperation within the members of the Anchor teams is described as functional and flexible, but there is still room for improvement in the cooperation of the anchor team of other police units and police departments. First, not everyone working in criminal investigation units and emergency response units is familiar with the work of Anchor Teams, and therefore the police's initiative in giving and handing over information depends on their personal motivation, skills, and knowledge. Second, police officers describe multi-professional cooperation as smoother if the different professionals work on the same premises of a police station. For example, in the IMPRODOVA interviews the uniformed police officers described the threshold to share information as low, if they could just enter the room of the other agencies to talk about a concerning case. On the other hand, if the other agencies worked in another premises, the police officers did not consider telephone contact as good an option as face-to-face dealings with a social worker they knew personally (Bradley et al., 2020).

Challenges in cooperation of the police and other agencies may arise at the individual level, if individuals have different ideas about how another authority should act. If the goals of e.g., social work are not understood in the police, this may cause frustration (ibid.).

Members of the Anchor team exchange information with each other with the client's consent. The law allows the exchange of information without consent if the client has children, because cooperation can be justified by the best interest of a child. On the other hand, childless couples who do not want to receive help from the Anchor team usually fall through the service net (ibid.).

In addition, Kurvinen et al. (2023) state that the current and recurring challenge of information exchange between the police and social work is related to different interpretations of what information can be handed over to another authority. Moreover, these interpretations depend on the place where the matter is discussed. The interpretations of other authorities are often seen as unnecessarily narrow and thus a factor complicating crime prevention and preliminary investigation. According to Kurvinen et al., the problems relating to authorities' ability to provide and release information seem to be dependent on legislation. Therefore, it is recommendable, among other things, that access to information is uniformly regulated in different laws (Kurvinen et al., 2023).

Anchor team's cooperation is guided by legislation, functional organisational structures, and processes. However, as for the rest of the police organisation, cooperation with the police department's Anchor team is often discretionary and voluntary and depends on whether individual police officers decide to contact the team. Often the motivation to contact the team is based on personal relationships and knowing the team members personally, which is indeed an effective, but vulnerable mode of operation (Bradley et al., 2020).

1.1.2.2 Justification

The Anchor team model in Finland has several elements that support effective interventions in domestic violence. The Anchor team model is based on multi-agency collaboration. A multidisciplinary approach ensures that victims of domestic violence receive comprehensive support, addressing both their immediate safety needs and longer-term assistance. This collaboration enables a more holistic understanding of the situation, allowing for tailored interventions. The Anchor teams operate with a victim-centred approach, ensuring that the needs and safety of the victim are prioritized. This approach increases the likelihood that victims will feel supported and empowered to take the necessary steps to protect themselves.

However, in recent years, the Finnish government has directed Anchor teams to focus increasingly on combating youth crime and radicalisation, and combating DV is no longer a priority. In the Manual on Multi-professional Anchor work (Ministry of Interior, 2022), which guides the work of the Anchor teams, intervention in DV is mentioned only when the client is a minor who needs multi-professional support due to a difficult family situation, such as DV. On the other hand, Anchor teams are not strictly prohibited from dealing with DV, and some teams still work with DV cases. This change in Anchor teams' priorities and its consequences are discussed in the following subchapters.

1.1.2.2.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

Governmental support

The Finnish government has provided strong support for Anchor teams through legislation and policy frameworks that emphasize the importance of multi-agency cooperation. Policies that promote the integration of social services, law enforcement, and healthcare have created a conducive environment for the establishment and operation of Anchor teams.

Comprehensive legislations

The implementation of Anchor teams in Finland is supported by various pieces of legislation and legal frameworks that emphasize the importance of multi-agency collaboration, victim protection, and effective intervention in cases of domestic violence.

First, the Police Act (872/2011) governs the duties and powers of the Finnish police, including their role in preventing and responding to crime. It emphasizes the need for cooperation between police and other authorities and communities in promoting safety.

Second, the Social Welfare Act (1301/2014) outlines the responsibilities of social services in Finland, including the provision of support and protection for individuals and families in vulnerable situations. The Social Welfare Act mandates the collaboration between social services and other authorities, such as the police and healthcare services, in organizing social emergency services.

Third, the Child Welfare Act (417/2007) mandates that any authority or professional who works with children must report to child welfare services if they suspect that a child is in danger or at risk due to domestic violence. This law reinforces the involvement of child welfare services in Anchor teams, ensuring that the protection of children is a central focus. In addition, the exchange of information between the authorities is especially justified when the best interest of the child is involved. The best interest of a child has enabled the Anchor teams to intervene DV effectively and in a multi-professional manner when there have been minors and children in the family. On the other hand, childless families have been at risk of being left without help if the parties have not given their consent to pass on the information to other authorities (Bradley et al., 2020).

Fourth, the Act on the Status and Rights of Social Welfare Clients (812/2000) ensures that clients of social services, including victims of domestic violence, have their rights protected.

It supports the client-centred approach of Anchor teams, emphasizing the importance of privacy, informed consent, and the right to receive appropriate services.

Fifth, the Criminal Code of Finland (39/1889) provides the legal framework for prosecuting perpetrators of domestic violence. The Criminal Code also supports the protective measures such as restraining orders and other legal protections for victims.

Sixth, the Act on Restraining Orders (898/1998) provides the legal basis for imposing restraining orders to protect victims of domestic violence.

Seventh, the European Union's Victims' Rights Directive ensures that victims of crime, including domestic violence, receive support and protection.

Last, the Health Care Act's (1326/2010) purpose is to strengthen the operating conditions of basic health care and to improve cooperation between health care providers, cooperation between different sectors in the welfare area and cooperation between the welfare area and the municipality, as well as cooperation with other operators in the promotion of health and well-being and in the organisation of social and health care.

Continuous evaluation and development

Anchor activities are evaluated through systematic data collection, monitoring the quality of work, and assessing whether set goals have been met. This process also helps in understanding local youth well-being and informing stakeholders. Data is collected on the Anchor Activities Extranet and used for planning, development, and management at all levels. Each team produces an annual report summarizing collected data and local activities. Consistent data collection improves coordination, organisation, and decision-making, allowing for comparisons at local, regional, and national levels.⁴⁷

Anchor activities are consistently monitored nationwide on a shared Extranet platform, recording work with youth and cooperation with stakeholders. Annual reports are prepared for local, regional, and national steering groups, based on systematic, anonymous data, and feedback collection.⁴⁸

Anchor activities are developed based on evidence and good practices, with national statistics and reports identifying areas for improvement. Local and regional activities are

⁴⁷For more details, see <https://ankkuritoiminta.fi/kasikirja/arviointi-ja-kehittaminen>

⁴⁸ Ibid.

tailored to youth needs and involve feedback from youths and parents. Professional competence is enhanced through continued education and multidisciplinary collaboration. Development is guided by national guidelines and based on evidence, statistics, and monitoring. National development focuses on creating structures that meet changing needs, with the national Anchor activities development group overseeing this process in cooperation with the responsible ministry.⁴⁹

1.1.2.2.2 Practical relevance

The shift in focus of Anchor teams in Finland from addressing domestic violence to concentrating more on youth delinquency and radicalisation has raised questions about their current relevance and effectiveness in dealing with domestic violence cases. Originally, Anchor teams were designed to be a multi-agency approach to tackle issues like domestic violence, juvenile delinquency, and other social challenges by providing holistic support. However, as the focus has shifted more towards youth-related issues like delinquency and radicalisation, the emphasis on domestic violence is diminished. This shift might limit the teams' ability to address domestic violence cases effectively, as resources and attention are now more directed towards other priorities.

Despite the shift in focus, the multi-disciplinary nature of Anchor teams still holds potential for addressing domestic violence cases when they do arise. The presence of professionals from different sectors (social services, police, healthcare, youth services) within the teams means that with domestic violence identified, the responses can still be comprehensive. However, without a clear mandate or priority to focus on domestic violence, the effectiveness of these teams in this area may not be as strong as it previously was.

Although the Anchor model has recently emphasized addressing criminal behaviour among children and youth, it remains an important part of tackling DV. First, in many police departments, the Anchor teams also handle DV cases. Research (e.g., Anda et al., 2006; Dube et al. 2003) shows that the root cause of criminal behaviour in children and youth can often be linked to adverse childhood experiences such as DV, and multidisciplinary collaboration can help assess the family's need for support, including in cases of violence. This violence may occur in the young person's own relationship or in the relationship between

⁴⁹ Ibid.

the youth's guardians. Detectives at the police department can also benefit from the Anchor team's expertise in DV cases that require multidisciplinary cooperation.

Even though the Anchor manual no longer highlights domestic violence, police departments have some autonomy in organizing Anchor activities in the way they deem most effective. For example, in Helsinki, the prevention of DV is still listed as one of the goals of the Anchor program. In the Häme region (Forssa, Hämeenlinna, and Riihimäki areas), the Anchor teams are also responsible for handling family and domestic violence reports. In Eastern Finland, the focus includes the prevention of DV regardless of age, as well as connecting both victims and perpetrators to support services. In Southwest Finland, the Anchor team works with families where family and domestic violence occurs.

Ideally, members of the Anchor team work in the same facilities at the police station. This can lower the threshold for police officers to seek the opinion and advice of the multidisciplinary team in cases where the client could benefit from collaborative support. For this reason, the role of Anchor in addressing DV is crucial, as it enables the sharing of multidisciplinary expertise with the police. In addition, since MARACs only deal with intimate partner violence, elderly people experiencing violence from their adult children, for example, may be left without risk assessment and multidisciplinary support. In such cases, the Anchor team may be a police department's only 'fast track' to multidisciplinary consultation.

The change in focus might affect how the police departments perceive the Anchor teams' role in handling domestic violence. If the police organisation sees these teams primarily dealing with youth issues, the police officers may be less likely to ask them for consultation on DV cases (adults without minors) that would require a multi-professional approach.

Studies show that young people who have experienced traumatic events within their families are more likely to engage in criminal activity in the future (Herrera & McCloskey, 2003; Asscher, van der Put & Stams, 2019). Considering the fact that young people who commit crimes are often exposed to or have experienced domestic violence, it is remarkable that there isn't a stronger connection between Anchor teams and the prevention of domestic violence. One would expect that efforts to combat youth delinquency would also include effective measures for preventing domestic violence, and that examining the life situations of young people could reveal instances of family violence that might otherwise go unnoticed by professionals.

1.1.2.2.3 Evidence and Data

A study on the effectiveness of Anchor activities (Kaakinen et al., 2022) was conducted by the Institute of Criminology and Legal Policy (Krimo) at the University of Helsinki. The research was part of the "Effectiveness of Anchor Activities" project carried out between 2021–2022, funded by the Prime Minister's Office.⁵⁰

The study was based on an analysis of the effectiveness of Anchor activities, the experiences of those involved in the activities, and a description of the Anchor process. The analysis was supported by comprehensive quantitative and qualitative research data. The study assessed the impact of Anchor activities on youth criminal behaviour and explored the experiences of professionals working within the Anchor teams, as well as the potential opportunities for developing the activities based on these experiences (ibid.).

The study's key conclusion suggests that the Anchor interventions appear to prevent future criminal behaviour. Youth involved in Anchor activities had a significantly lower risk of being again suspected of a crime within the following year compared to their peers (ibid.).

1.1.2.2.4 Context of the Solution

The Anchor team model aligns with and complement existing policies, regulations, strategies, and practices in the field of domestic violence, though its primary focus has expanded to include youth delinquency and radicalisation. Anchor team model is achieved through a conscious effort to integrate and complement existing frameworks and practices. This is done by promoting inter-agency cooperation, adhering to legislative requirements, and aligning with national strategies for domestic violence prevention and victim support.

The Anchor teams bring together professionals from police, social services, healthcare, and youth services. This multidisciplinary approach ensures that the interventions align with broader social and health policies that emphasize collaboration between various sectors to address complex issues like domestic violence (Bradley et al., 2020).

The operation of Anchor teams is supported by Finnish legislation that mandates cooperation between different authorities in protecting and promoting the well-being of citizens. For instance, the Social Welfare Act (1301/2014) and the Child Welfare Act (417/2007) require

⁵⁰ For more details, see <https://rikoksentorijunta.fi/ankkuri>

local authorities to work together to protect children and families, which is a core function of the Anchor teams.

The Anchor model complements national strategies aimed at preventing domestic violence and supporting victims. For example, Finland's Action Plan for Combatting Violence against Women for 2020–2023 (Ministry of Justice, 2020) emphasizes the need for early intervention, risk assessment, and support for victims, which have been all integral parts of many Anchor team's work.

Anchor teams are embedded within local communities, allowing them to adapt their practices to fit local needs and conditions. This local integration ensures that their work is relevant to the specific challenges and dynamics of domestic violence in each area, thus aligning with local policies and practices.

1.1.2.2.5 Unintended Consequences and Risks

The shift of Anchor teams to focus more on juvenile offenders, and thereby reducing their intervention in domestic violence cases, could have several implications for the provision of multi-professional help to adult victims of DV. Anchor teams have traditionally provided a coordinated approach to managing DV cases, involving multiple professionals such as police, social workers, healthcare providers, and NGOs. With their focus shifting away from domestic violence, there might be a gap in the availability of such coordinated services. Victims may experience more fragmented support if the multi-professional collaboration facilitated by Anchor teams is diminished.

Anchor teams are often involved in early intervention, identifying and addressing risks before they escalate. Their reduced involvement in DV cases could result in missed opportunities for early intervention and prevention, especially if their young clients' adverse childhood experiences such as DV are not detected and actively addressed.

According to the Manual, MARACs are assumed to take on a more prominent role in coordinating multi-professional help for DV victims. Ensuring that MARACs are well-resourced and supported may help mitigate the impact of Anchor teams' shift in focus. However, MARACs are primarily intended for victims of severe and prolonged violence, and not all victims of domestic violence can be referred to MARAC due to resource constraints.

1.1.3 Solution 3: Tools for screening risks of domestic violence and female genital mutilation (FGM) in health care

A domestic violence enquiry and assessment form is a tool for detecting domestic violence in health care services. The Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) recommends its use in maternity and child health clinics and elsewhere in health care services. (THL, 2024b)

A form for evaluating the threat of female genital mutilation (FGM) is a tool for detecting the possible risk of a girl child to have her outer genitals mutilated. (THL, 2019)

The report is complemented by recent interviews with professionals, conducted as part of the EU project IMPROVE.

Code	Profession, discipline	Representing	Year
THL_T1	Health Care Specialist (development tasks)	Wellbeing Services County	2023
THL_T2	Health Care Specialist (development tasks)	Wellbeing Services County	2023
THL_T3	Health Care Specialist (Maternity and Child Health Clinics)	Wellbeing Services County	2023
THL_S3	Social Worker	Wellbeing Services County	2023
THL_S4	Social Worker	Wellbeing Services County	2023
THL_S5	Social Worker	Wellbeing Services County	2023
THL_N2	Specialist	NGO/victims of DV	2023

1.1.3.1 Description

1.1.3.1.1 Background and Aim

According to the recommendations of THL, domestic violence should be detected with a special questionnaire from both parents at least once during pregnancy at the maternity health clinic, and again later in child health clinic. Both these services are universal, free, and voluntary. Almost 100 per cent of expecting couples and families with small children regularly visit these clinics. Therefore, these places offer an excellent opportunity to detect domestic violence.

The suitable time to give the questionnaire to the pregnant woman and her spouse would be around mid-pregnancy. By then the initial excitement of having a baby may have subsided a little, and the future parents are able to concentrate on other topics, too. The public health nurse/midwife in the maternity clinic will also be more familiar to the couple at that point.

THL also recommends that the topic of female genital mutilation (FGM) is discussed in maternity and child health clinics with families originating from countries where FGM tradition is still alive and practised. Preventive work should start already during the pregnancy; first by inquiring about expecting woman's own possible genital mutilation and secondly by discussing future parents' attitudes towards the tradition and their plans concerning their own daughter (THL, 2024c).

It is important to emphasize that there are no health benefits of FGM, but instead it causes a wide range of health problems to girls and women. FGM is a punishable act under the Criminal Code of Finland as assault or aggravated assault. Penalty for aggravated assault is as long as 10 years of imprisonment.

A form for evaluating the threat of female genital mutilation (FGM) is a tool for professionals working with families of foreign origin. Public health nurse/midwife, for instance, can use the form in the reception of a maternity health clinic or a child health clinic to evaluate whether the girl is in risk of FGM or not (Hongisto & Kahelin, 2016).

The Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) gives recommendations to municipalities and wellbeing services counties on how to arrange certain social and health care services. There are detailed recommendations of the contents of the services; for example, what kind of questions to ask in detecting domestic violence in maternity clinic or child health clinic. THL has created a specific domestic violence enquiry and assessment form, and a clinical pathway for professionals to follow in case domestic violence is suspected or reported.

A health care specialist (T1) working in the welfare services county in Southern Finland, stated that there are regional differences when it comes to asking about domestic violence in the above-mentioned clinics.

“Partly it is due to available resources, and partly due to individual differences amongst professionals and organisational structures. Asking about DV seems to depend also on professional's own interest, will, and courage. Organisational structures either support asking about DV or prevent it.” (T1)

There are many other things that need to be asked too during the reception in maternity health clinic and in child health clinic. (T1, T3) These include, for example, the client's substance use, social environment, and mental health issues. Time must be found for all of this, so screening must be recorded in the organisation's structures so that professionals have a real opportunity to carry out screening. In addition, THL recommends that clients who need an interpreter be given double time for the reception, because using an interpreter makes customer service more time-consuming.

According to an interviewee (T2) working as a health care specialist in the capital area, a solution could be detecting domestic violence already in the hospital after the birth of the baby. Usually, family stays overnight or even longer in the hospital ward, where professionals have more time to discuss with families before they go home. In the hospital, there are more professionals present of different fields like social worker and priest with whom families can discuss.

Finland has its own action plan for the prevention of female genital mutilation. (Koukkula & Klemetti, 2019). As FGM is a tradition that violates human rights and breaks the Finnish law, THL recommends that professionals should take up the topic with clients originating from countries where the tradition persists. It is a culturally sensitive topic, and it may feel difficult to discuss the matter in the reception. Therefore, THL has developed this tool based on a similar tool used in Britain (HM Government, 2017) to make it easier to talk about FGM with clients, and at the same time evaluate whether a girl is at risk of FGM. Preventive work could also be carried out in the hospital after the birth of the baby – just like any form of domestic violence.

1.1.3.1.2 Implementation and Practice

THL's work is guided by international agreements, research evidence, and national policies, and law. THL's recommendations concerning domestic violence are based on Istanbul Convention battling against violence towards women and domestic violence. The wellbeing services counties should ensure that there are enough resources in the health care sector and other necessary sectors to detect domestic violence including harmful cultural practices like FGM.

Resources here refer to hiring sufficient personnel and providing tools, methods, and training to address these demanding domestic violence related topics. A social worker (S3) emphasized that the training should be compulsory and constant due to high personnel

turnover in both social and health care fields. When the training is compulsory, it is easier to clear space for it compared to some voluntary training.

As mentioned before, almost all expecting couples and families with small children are encountered in these clinics. Therefore, both these solutions meet the needs of people who belong to vulnerable groups. The ideal situation for any expecting couple and family with small children would be that professional asks about domestic violence during their visit in the clinic. A professional would then follow the clinical pathway according to the result of the enquiry and assessment form. The same practices apply for the evaluation of the threat of female genital mutilation. Clients assisted by an interpreter need to be reserved twice as much time for the appointment.

Few victims of DV report their experiences on their own initiative (Notko, M. et al., 2011). Therefore, it is very important for professionals to ask directly about DV at the reception. When asked from everyone, it is not stigmatizing to any group of clients. Besides covering people with immigrant background, it also covers many other vulnerable groups such as Roma, sexual minorities, people with disabilities, and people with mental health problems. The professional at the reception should also mention that the question of domestic violence is asked equally from everyone, not just from one particular group of people.

1.1.3.1.3 Strengths and Weaknesses

We already have a high-quality and proven tool existing for detecting domestic violence amongst expecting couples and families with small children. The challenge is the scarcity of resources (Kankaanpää et al., 2022) and uncertainty and sometimes even unwillingness of professionals to use the tool. Screening should be part of the organisation structures.

Solutions to these obstacles would be for decision makers to ensure that there is enough staff working in maternity and child welfare clinics so that professionals have enough time to ask about domestic violence and to guide persons forward along the clinical pathway, when needed.

Professionals should also get regular and compulsory training on the topic of domestic violence. The training should at least cover topics like different forms of DV and how to detect it by asking the right questions at the right time (T1, T2, S3, S4).

Asking about violence is part of the overall survey of the client's situation in health care. A *domestic violence enquiry and assessment form* is used as a tool for mapping the situation.

Asking about violence initiates a process that strengthens the safety of the victim. At the same time, a professional can spread information about violence, its various forms, and the services available. According to a study (Perttu, 2004), the experiences of public health nurses and women (as clients) in asking about DV showed that discussing the topic in maternity and child health clinics was perceived as natural and women generally accepted it.

If a professional suspects that a girl is under the threat of FGM or has gone through the procedure while living in Finland, the topic should be taken up with the girl and her parents/guardians. In addition, the professional is obliged to submit a child welfare notification to the social welfare authorities and to report the matter to the police. “A form for evaluating the threat of female genital mutilation” (FGM) is a tool for detecting the possible risk of a girl to have her outer genitals mutilated. Inquiring about FGM is the most effective form of preventive work in order to eradicate this harmful tradition. According to a recent survey by THL, the FGM threat assessment form has so far only been rarely used by professionals. In the future, information about the form and its use should be more effective at various training events, which THL also organizes (Parekh & Koukkula, 2024).

Ideally, in both cases – inquiring regularly about DV and FGM - the expertise of the employees of maternity and child health clinics gradually increases. Work related to domestic violence becomes routine without uncertainty and fear.

1.1.3.2 Justification

Implementing a domestic violence enquiry and assessment form in health care in Finland can be justified on several grounds, e.g., reflecting the importance of addressing and mitigating the impacts of domestic violence on individuals and society as a whole.

Domestic violence is a significant public health issue that affects individuals' physical and mental health. Implementing a DV enquiry and assessment form helps healthcare providers identify victims early, leading to timely intervention and support; ultimately reducing the long-term health consequences associated with this phenomenon.

In the study (Notko et al., 2011) involving over 500 patients in three specialized hospital wards in Central Finland, the prevalence of domestic violence, its different forms and recurrence of experienced violence and need of further care were clarified. The health care personnel utilized a questionnaire to identify domestic violence and the need for further care. According

to the results of this study, the need for help of these patients would have remained unrecognized without a systematic survey with the help of the questionnaire.

A structured DV enquiry and assessment form enables healthcare professionals to systematically screen for signs of abuse. Early identification allows for immediate intervention, providing victims with resources, support, and safety planning. This proactive approach can prevent further harm and save lives. In the long run, it can also help use scarce resources of health care more efficiently.

Training healthcare professionals to use an enquiry and assessment form to detect DV raises awareness and sensitivity towards domestic violence issues. It provides professionals with the knowledge and skills necessary to recognize and to respond to signs of abuse, leading to a more supportive and responsive healthcare environment. The education of health care professionals is imperative in order to implement screening policies and change the attitudes about patients experiencing DV (Koistinen, 2012).

In the same way, the form for evaluating the threat of female genital mutilation (FGM) enables health care professionals to identify girls of immigrant background at risk whose traditions include genital mutilation. Implementing this form health care professionals can ensure that this vulnerable group is efficiently identified and provided with the necessary support and protection (Parekh & Koukkula, 2024).

1.1.3.2.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

Implementation of enquiry forms for risk assessment of domestic violence (DV) and female genital mutilation (FGM) in health care settings in Finland has required careful consideration of several factors. As mentioned earlier, THL's work is guided by international agreements, research evidence, national policies, and law. THL's recommendations concerning domestic violence are established on the Istanbul Convention battling against violence towards women and domestic violence.

The wellbeing services counties are tasked with ensuring that the health care sector and other relevant sectors have sufficient resources to detect DV (including harmful cultural practices like FGM). These resources encompass hiring adequate personnel and supplying necessary tools to combat DV. The questionnaires should be easily integrated into routine health care procedures to ensure they are used. They should be compact to ensure that they do not overly burden health care professionals or clients/patients.

Comprehensive training of the health care providers on how to use the enquiry and assessment forms effectively, identify signs of DV, and manage disclosures sensitively is of utmost importance. (Koistinen, 2012) Training should also cover topics like culturally sensitive approach (including how cultural factors may influence DV dynamics) and awareness of the diverse background of clients/patients.

It is equally important to implement ongoing training to keep professionals updated on best practices and possible changes in protocols. Ongoing training is also important due to high personnel turnover in both fields, social and health care. It would be essential to integrate the forms into the daily routine work thus ensuring that risk assessments become a standard part of health care. This would require efficient procedures in order to minimize the additional time required for assessing risks of DV and FGM so that other activities are not duly affected.

1.1.3.2.2 Practical relevance

In Finland, implementing enquiry forms for risk assessment of domestic violence (DV) and female genital mutilation (FGM) in health care settings in Finland has significant practical relevance. It covers for example improved patient care (via addressing DV more efficiently) and better public health outcomes.

When health care professionals can identify victims early, it leads to timely interventions that can, in turn, prevent further harm and potentially save lives. Early detection can also prevent or reduce the severity of injuries and other health problems (e.g., mental health issues) associated with DV. Clients/patients also become aware of their situation, and they learn about available resources. Providing information about support services helps victims access necessary legal, social, and psychological support in addition to health care services. When health care professionals address DV with sensitivity and confidentiality, it builds trust, encouraging victims to seek help and disclose abuse (Notko et al., 2011).

Regular screening and interventions can, in the long run, reduce the overall prevalence of DV on all levels of society. Effective risk assessment and intervention can help break the cycle of violence, particularly in families with children who might otherwise continue the cycle. This applies to harmful cultural practices as well, like FGM.

Early intervention can also reduce health care costs by preventing severe injuries and chronic conditions resulting from prolonged abuse. Addressing DV can reduce the burden on social

services and legal systems as well. Early intervention can also improve productivity at work by supporting victims.

With the help of identified DV, it is possible to allocate resources and actions to the issues that can be used to reduce the violence and treat its various parties in accordance with jointly agreed procedures. In this way, the well-being of individuals, families and society as a whole can be increased. (Kivelä et al., 2016)

1.1.3.2.3 Evidence and Data

Research indicates that domestic violence is a significant issue in Finland, affecting both women and men. According to the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), Finland has one of the highest rates of reported intimate partner violence in Europe (OECD Statistics, 2020).

Implementing questionnaires for assessing the risk of DV and FGM in Finnish health care requires a multifaceted approach that addresses evidence-based design, ongoing training of professionals, client/patient privacy, cultural sensitivity, integration into routine practice, and efficient support systems. By taking into consideration all these factors, the health care system can more effectively identify and support individuals at risk of DV and FGM.

Systematic use of these enquiry and assessment forms contribute to data collection, thus providing valuable insights for research and policy development. The questionnaires must always be tailored to country specific cultural contexts, considering local attitudes towards domestic violence, gender roles, and family dynamics. They should have clear and culturally appropriate language and terminology to ensure comprehensibility and acceptance among local clients/patients (in this case, Finnish people and people with an immigrant background residing in Finland).

According to a recent survey (Krogell & Niklander, 2023), a questionnaire to assess the risk of DV is used in the majority (73 %) of the wellbeing services counties in Finland. Three out of four professionals responded that voluntary training on domestic violence is available in their area. Compulsory training on domestic violence, on the other hand, is only available in two wellbeing services counties, according to the survey.

Health care professionals must receive thorough training on how to administer the questionnaires, interpret results, and respond appropriately to disclosures of DV and FGM. Ongoing training sessions are essential to update staff on the latest practices and findings in

this field. THL also trains professionals in various fields and shares information about the questionnaires and their use. In addition, clients/patients need to feel safe and assured that their responses will be kept confidential.

1.1.3.2.4 Context of the Solution

Finland has a publicly funded health care system that provides comprehensive services to all residents (universal coverage). This means the questionnaires should be able to be used across various health care settings, including primary care, hospitals, and specialized clinics. Health care services in Finland are integrated with social services, which can facilitate a multidisciplinary approach to DV risk assessment and management.

Understanding the society's attitudes towards domestic violence in Finland is crucial. Finnish society has relatively high awareness of gender equality issues, but there is still stigma associated with disclosing DV. Finland is a bilingual country with Finnish and Swedish as official languages. The questionnaire of DV should be available in both languages, and possibly other common languages spoken by immigrants to ensure accessibility. This applies also to the FGM risk assessment form.

There are laws and regulations in Finland aimed at preventing domestic violence and protecting victims. These include provisions in the Criminal Code and specific acts like the Act on Restraining Orders. There are also action plans to combat domestic violence, which provide a supportive framework for implementing risk assessment tools in health care.

Finnish health care professionals are highly educated and well-trained, but specific training on DV risk assessment and intervention is necessary. This training should be part of continuous professional development programs. The Finnish health care system supports multidisciplinary collaboration, which is essential for addressing a phenomenon like domestic violence. Health care providers should work closely with social workers, psychologists, and legal professionals. In other words, considering the social norms and the health care system in Finland in its own special context, is necessary to successfully implement enquiry forms for risk assessment of domestic violence (DV) and female genital mutilation (FGM).

1.1.3.2.5 Unintended Consequences and Risks

Although the enquiry forms for risk assessment of domestic violence and female genital mutilation have been carefully designed and tested, their use may still involve unexpected consequences or risks.

Disclosure of DV risk through the questionnaire might lead to immediate or increased violence from perpetrators if they become aware of the situation. Therefore, it is important to conduct the assessment in a private setting (client/patient alone with the health care professional). Professionals should be trained to recognise the signs of immediate danger and make safety plans for the victim.

Answering questions about DV or FGM can cause emotional distress or re-traumatisation for survivors. Health care professionals should approach the subject with sensitivity, and be able to offer mental health support, if needed, immediately after the questionnaire is administered.

Identifying DV without adequate follow-up and support can leave clients/patients feeling vulnerable and unsupported. Health care professionals should ensure that there are referral pathways and support services available to provide comprehensive support to victims of DV.

Health care professionals may also experience stress, burnout or vicarious trauma when repeatedly exposed to clients'/patients' experiences of DV. A solution is to offer the health care staff regular training on managing emotional stress and provide access to psychological support. It is important for staff to be able to discuss their experiences and feelings as well.

The additional task of administering the questionnaire might burden health care professionals, potentially affecting other areas of care. Hence, the questionnaire should be concise and easy to administer so that it would integrate easily into already existing routines.

1.1.4 Solution 4: Cultural interpreter

The Finnish Refugee Council (FRC) is an international NGO based in Finland with no political or religious affiliations. They support people who have been forced to escape from their home countries as well as hosting countries. One of their goals is to promote inclusion and integration.

MONIKA – Multicultural Women’s Association is an umbrella organisation of multicultural women’s organisations that helps and supports women in different languages. It promotes equality, non-discrimination, and inclusion of women with immigrant background. MONIKA also prevents violence against women.

Iraqi Women’s Association (INY) supports women with immigrant background by promoting their position in the family and in the society. The association focuses on supporting the study and work of immigrant women. In addition, INY works against violence, such as domestic violence and honour-related violence.

The report is complemented by recent interviews with professionals, conducted as part of the EU project IMPROVE.

Code	Profession, discipline	Representing	Year
THL_T1	Health Care Specialist (development tasks)	Wellbeing Services County	2023
THL_T2	Health Care Specialist (development tasks)	Wellbeing Services County	2023
THL_T3	Health Care Specialist (Maternity and Child Health Clinics)	Wellbeing Services County	2023
THL_S3	Social Worker	Wellbeing Services County	2023
THL_S4	Social Worker	Wellbeing Services County	2023
THL_S5	Social Worker	Wellbeing Services County	2023
THL_N2	Specialist	NGO/victims of DV	2023

1.1.4.1 Description

1.1.4.1.1 Background and Aim

There are still considerably less immigrants entering Finland compared to many other European countries. The fairly small numbers are partly due to restrictive Finnish immigration

policy. Multiculturalism is still being learned in Finland. This causes challenges for both immigrants and professionals belonging to the majority population. Immigrant associations seem to have an important role in the integration of the immigrant groups - especially women (Saksela-Bergholm, 2010).

Elsewhere in Europe in the 1980s, a concept called cultural mediation was developed to help migrants navigate complex systems. The goal was to promote the access of health care and other services and facilitate the interaction of professionals and clients in different areas of life, such as birth, well-being, illness, and death. Cultural mediation is an inclusive approach that helps to reduce cultural and language barriers also in the field of gender-based violence (Rakovica & Ianovitz, 2021).

This solution helps to find vulnerable victims of violence and bring them into the service system. The cultural knowledge and language skills of the organisation's victim support workers lower the threshold of victims of violence to disclose their experiences. The victim support workers help the victim to cooperate with the authorities and at the same time they create bridges between the authorities and the victims. Moreover, they help victims to understand that normalized experiences of violence in the lives of victims are wrong and that these are crimes, and that victims have the right to receive help, support, and get justice like everyone else.

When considering a solution, local professionals could try to build collaboration with key persons in the communities - including religious leaders. Immigrant women seem to trust other immigrant women who have stayed longer in the country. It is also important that they come from the same country or at least from the same language group. It is especially appreciated if they are already involved in working life in some capacity (Delpauch et al., 2024).

NGOs working with immigrant women have paid attention to this phenomenon, and they call them "cultural interpreters" who can offer peer support. An example of this could be a (voluntary) worker in an NGO or a shelter for victims of DV specialising in the issues of immigrant women. The worker could help the victim in contacting local authorities and in building confidence in the system. The cultural interpreter may also be able to estimate more accurately the urgency of required intervention in the DV situation.

In addition, local professionals seem to be afraid to ask about honour related violence from their clients with immigrant background because they are afraid of being labelled as racists. According to the interviews conducted in D1.3 (Delpeuch et al., 2024), it is desirable to talk about all the problems directly without reservation - even if the topic is taboo in the community. If professionals ignore difficult topics, things might just get worse.

Cultural interpreters can be an important asset in combatting domestic violence experienced by women with immigrant backgrounds. Good experiences have already been gained, for example of the projects led by NGOs in Finland. This came up in the interviews with the professionals, when they were asked about the removal of obstacles for women with immigrant backgrounds to seek help (Delpeuch et. al, 2024).

There is an essential difference between a regular interpreter and a cultural interpreter; while the regular interpreter only translates, the latter can also provide cultural context, information, and instructions. It is also commonly known that many clients with immigrant background have difficulties in trusting interpreters. They believe that interpreters leak information to their own community despite their official non-disclosure agreement. This is also one critical barrier, why victims of domestic violence with immigrant background, are often unwilling to disclose their problems to local professionals, even though they are already using available services (Lilja, 2020). A cultural interpreter could be a valuable resource in such situation, as well.

1.1.4.1.2 Implementation and Practice

A study conducted by Honkatukia & Suurpää (2007) reinforces the conception of lack of knowledge of families of foreign origin of their rights and duties in the institutional system of Finnish society. This seems to be the case for both young people and their parents. Families are not aware where to seek help in situations of crisis or even with less serious problems, as a professional described in D1.3 (Delpeuch et. al, 2024):

“Victims of domestic violence can ponder in their minds: What’ll happen to my mother, if I seek help from the shelter for victims of domestic violence? What’ll people say to my father? Members of one’s own community can also give misleading information, for example about the role of officials/professionals or consequences of reporting DV. Sometimes family can consult a religious leader (e.g., an imam staying locally or even in another country) rather than a local professional like nurse, social worker, or police.”
(N2)

A social worker specialised in adult social work (S3) raised concerns related to men with immigrant background. Intercultural marriages - where one party is a Finn, and the other party is of foreign origin – are becoming increasingly frequent in Finland.

“The foreign male spouse is often left totally alone in cases of domestic violence (usually psychological and/or economical violence) when the perpetrator is a Finnish woman. He doesn’t know where to contact to seek help. On top of everything, he is too embarrassed to talk about his situation to anyone. His friends would say ‘can’t you control your woman?’. This applies naturally to female spouses of foreign origin as well; they may feel extremely lonely and lost in situations of domestic violence.” (S3)

The interviewee emphasized that it would be very important for men with immigrant background to also have a support person/cultural interpreter originating from the same country or at least from the same language group. It seems to be difficult for them to talk about their problems to a Finnish female (social) worker, especially in situation where the perpetrator is also a Finnish woman.

Women with an immigrant background who suffer from DV (sometimes a lifetime of violence and abuse) can find it very difficult to trust the authorities in their new home country (Lilja, 2020). Cultural interpreters can help victims to contact and trust professionals and/or authorities by removing prejudices on both sides. In an ideal situation they build bridges between victims with immigrant background and professionals/authorities belonging to the majority population.

As an example, in 2017 the Finnish Refugee Council (FRC) launched a project called Linkki (*Link* in English) related to training and use of cultural interpreters in various situations. The aim of the project was to strengthen the interaction between staff in various services and families with an immigrant background. This, in turn, was believed to increase mutual understanding and trust between the families with immigrant background and the authorities/professionals.

In 2019, there were 146 individual cultural interpretations performed by the project staff of Linkki. The most common places for them to work were kindergartens, schools (e.g., with teachers, school welfare officers, and psychologists), and healthcare (e.g., with nurses and doctors in maternity and child health clinics and health stations). At some stage, they started cooperation with employment office services too. The most common languages used were

Somali, Kurdish and Arabic. There were more women than men working as cultural interpreters.

The project was running for three and a half years, i.e. from 2017–2020 until the funding ran out during Covid-19 pandemic. After that, for example Helsinki City has adopted the model in some form, but instead of cultural interpreters they call these professionals multilingual counsellors.

Another example is MONIKA that develops and provides specialized services for women with an immigrant background and their children who have been subjected to violence. This work is carried out at Crisis Centre Monika and Shelter Mona. Crisis Centre Monika provides low-threshold crisis assistance, guidance, and counselling services for women with an immigrant background, who have experienced violence (crisis help, psychosocial support, peer support groups, advice and service guidance, and supportive housing services after a period in a shelter). Services are provided in the following languages: Arabic, Belarussian, Dari, English, Farsi, Finnish, French, Persian, Russian, and Spanish.

MONIKA also develops and offers integration activities that support the social skills and employment of immigrant women, thus fostering their successful integration into society. This work is carried out at Integration Centre Monika. They provide, among other things, individual guidance for applying to study and for jobs, residence permits, family reunification, housing, and livelihood.

In D1.3 (Delpuech et al. 2024), several interviewees (S3, S4, T1) referred to Monika Women's work as an excellent example of handling complicated and demanding situations connected with DV amongst women with immigrant background. Language skills and understanding of different cultures were specifically mentioned as an advantage over local professionals. They knew how to ask the right questions and they managed to get to the core of the problem much faster.

The third example of an NGO that works with women with immigrant background is Iraqi Women's Association (INY). The focus of their work is also on integration like supporting women in finding study place or job. Another important goal of their work is to prevent violence, especially the domestic violence that can sometimes have features of honour-related violence too.

“It is important to get information on one’s own language from someone whom you can trust.” (N2)

INy has good experiences of cultural interpretation in various situations. They guide women with immigrant background to various services whether it is a Finnish language course, an employment office, or some service in the social or health care field.

1.1.4.1.3 Strengths and Weaknesses

The primary purpose of using a cultural interpreter is to familiarize immigrants with the Finnish society and culture, and at the same time support their integration. In addition, cultural interpreter acts between the immigrant and the official/professional. The goal is to build trust in authorities and Finland's institutional system (Delpuch et. al, 2024).

Immigrants are not a homogenous group – instead there are huge differences when it comes to their background like nationality, language, level of education, and skills. This can be challenging for the cultural interpreter. It is essential that cultural interpreters are familiar with the Finnish society and its basic values. They must also have a good command of Finnish language and the knowledge of at least one other language (Savolainen, 2020).

The Finnish Refugee Council has been piloting so called trainers' training (for civic orientation of immigrants). Educational institutions, NGOs, and municipalities can hire trainers who provide training in several languages, for instance in Arabic, Dari, Farsi, and Kurdish (Suomen Pakolaisapu, 2020). A similar kind of method could be applied for cultural interpreters'/multilingual counsellors' training too.

D1.3 (Delpuch et al., 2024) showed that this solution supports well the needs of immigrant women and children, who belong to the category of the most vulnerable victims. With the help of cultural interpreters, they will be able to more rapidly acquire the necessary information about their rights and duties. They will also get a basic understanding of the law in their new home country. Cultural interpreters cannot function alone; it is important that they work together with local authorities/professionals.

Women who arrive to Finland via *family reunification* seem to be one of the most vulnerable groups because they often stay without any information compared to refugees and asylum seekers who participate in specific information events arranged for them.

Knowledge gives strength and courage to persons in vulnerable position so that it is easier to seek help and trust the local authorities/professionals. In some countries, DV is considered strictly to be a private issue, and victims seldom approach “outsiders” in this kind of situation. It requires that persons with immigrant background rethink their values and ways of seeing the world, to be able to seek external help. The interviews conducted in D1.3 (Delpuech et al, 2024) showed that cultural interpreter would be valuable there, too.

During the implementation of Istanbul Convention, for example the Ministry of Justice has been financing the work of NGOs fighting against violence towards women and honour related violence. In addition, the Ministry of Social Services and Health has financed the work of NGOs battling against similar topics.

According to the interviews with the professionals, the biggest obstacle is to find regular funding for the NGOs to enable them to recruit staff that can work as cultural interpreters and offer peer support for newcomers in the country. It is also important to emphasize that the role of cultural interpreters is to guide victims of domestic violence into the services, and not to try to solve the problems by themselves.

A solution for receiving required funding could be the dissemination of information of the cultural interpreter model. Wherever it has been used, the experiences have been positive and encouraging. On the other hand, the responsibility of arranging this kind of service should not be on the shoulders of the NGOs alone. There should be more cases like Helsinki City where it was decided to train and hire cultural interpreters/multicultural counsellors.

To avoid misunderstandings or misinterpretations of the role of cultural interpreters - for cultural interpreters themselves, authorities/professionals, and immigrants - a proper training is required. Once the role of the cultural interpreter is clear to all the parties, it is easier to act accordingly and achieve positive results.

1.1.4.2 Justification

Introduction of the cultural interpreter model in the battle against domestic violence can be justified for several reasons, e.g., reflecting the importance of finding vulnerable victims with immigrant backgrounds and bringing them into the service system.

Domestic violence can manifest itself differently across cultures; influenced for example by various social and religious factors. A cultural interpreter can provide insights into these specific contexts, thus helping frontline responders to better understand and address the

underlying issues. Using cultural interpreters, all individuals have equal chances to seek help and enter support services in cases of domestic violence.

1.1.4.2.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

Domestic violence is a significant public health issue that affects both the native population and the population with immigrant background. As mentioned earlier, the research material (Honkatukia & Suurpää, 2007) confirms the perception that families with foreign background don't always have the knowledge about their rights and obligations in the institutional system of Finnish society. They don't know whom to contact in crisis situations or even smaller problems.

Implementation of the cultural interpreter model helps frontline responders to identify these victims earlier, which in turn leads to timely intervention and support; ultimately reducing the manifold long-term health effects and costs to society associated with the phenomenon.

To successfully implement the model, institutional support is also required. Securing adequate funding to reinforce the recruitment, training, and retention of the cultural interpreters is essential. Immigrant communities should be engaged as well to raise awareness about domestic violence and the availability of cultural interpreters.

1.1.4.2.2 Practical relevance

Implementing the model of a cultural interpreters in combatting domestic violence has significant practical relevance. First of all, cultural interpreters can help in overcoming language barriers by ensuring that victims can effectively communicate their experiences and needs to frontline responders in support services. This, in turn, facilitates accurate reporting of DV incidents.

Cultural interpreters also provide information about cultural norms and practices that might influence both the behaviour of victims and perpetrators. As a result, frontline responders can offer more culturally sensitive support, which can be crucial in building trust between clients/patients of immigrant origin and authorities. When victims receive information about their own rights and the processes involved, it is easier for them to decide about seeking help.

The aim of this model is to help frontline responders to detect domestic violence more efficiently among vulnerable victims and to provide them with support and refer them to the service system. Early intervention can also reduce health care costs and, in addition, the need for social services and legal systems.

1.1.4.2.3 Evidence and Data

The use of cultural interpreters (in domestic violence cases) is a recognized good practice in many countries. So far, a limited amount of empirical data on the implementation of the cultural interpreter model has been published in Finland. However, there are studies carried out for example by the University of Helsinki and THL revealing that language barriers may significantly deter especially immigrant women in Finland from reporting domestic violence and accessing support services.

The insights of cultural interpreters can provide decision makers with valuable information about the special needs of immigrant communities. This can lead to more effective forms of prevention of domestic violence and intervention strategies, for example by ensuring that services are inclusive and accessible to all groups of people.

Based on the experiences of employees of NGOs working with immigrants in Finland, cultural interpreters also help to build bridges between different (cultural) understandings connected with domestic violence. For example, perceptions of raising children and what is and what is not a family matter, can differ greatly between the population with an immigrant background and the majority population. Cultural interpreters can help victims to contact and trust authorities by removing prejudices on both sides.

Evidence and data support the implementation of the cultural interpreter model in combating domestic violence (including harmful cultural practices such as honour related violence including female genital mutilation). Among other things, they can overcome language and culture barriers, enhance cultural sensitivity among professionals/authorities, build trust between different parties, and empower victims (Delpeuch et al., 2024).

1.1.4.2.4 Context of the Solution

This solution reflects relatively recent demographic changes in Finland since there has been a significant rise in its immigrant population over the past few decades. According to Statistics Finland, in the end of 2022, approximately 9,1 % of the population were of foreign origin.

The solution of implementing cultural interpreters in combating domestic violence (including harmful cultural practices like honour related violence and female genital mutilation) is based on the need to address the unique challenges faced by the growing and diverse immigrant population in Finland. Cultural interpreters can play a crucial role in making domestic violence services more accessible and effective for all residents.

The need for cultural competence is increasingly recognized when dealing with cases of domestic violence among immigrants. This approach is an example of best practice that has been tested in practical work, which is also supported by our research findings and encouraging international experiences.

1.1.4.2.5 Unintended Consequences and Risks

While this solution has multiple benefits, there are also potential risks that need to be considered. The biggest risks are related to understanding the role of cultural interpreters (both by clients and authorities) and organising adequate training.

Limited resources may affect the quality and availability of cultural interpretation services. Standardised training programs are necessary, otherwise there may be inconsistencies in the quality and results of cultural interpretation. Thorough and ongoing training is essential for interpreters to stay updated, which might not always be possible due to the lack of resources. The training should also include topics such as confidentiality, impartiality, and cultural competence.

The involvement of a cultural interpreter from one's own community may also cause risks. Questions about trust and safety may arise during interpretation; especially if all parties (victim, perpetrator, and interpreter) come from the same community. This, in turn, may affect victim's willingness to seek help in cases of domestic violence (Lilja, 2020).

By proactively addressing these potential risks, the cultural interpreter model can be useful in battling domestic violence in the context of Finland also.

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2.3 France

The present report delineates and analyses two major initiatives in France's domestic violence policies: the embedded social workers within the police and gendarmerie, and the newly established Family Violence Task Forces in all courts and public prosecutors' offices across the country.

The "Embedded Social Workers" solution in France represents a widely adopted and successful approach to addressing social distress and domestic violence (DV) by embedding social workers (Intervenants Sociaux en Commissariat et Gendarmerie, ISCG) within police and gendarmerie stations. This initiative, formalised in 2006, promotes collaboration between law enforcement and social services, historically separate fields, to ensure timely support for victims. The primary tasks of ISCGs include identifying the victim's needs, providing short-term social and psychological support, informing victims of their rights, and facilitating access to appropriate services. Embedded social workers bridge the gap between victims, law enforcement agencies and the surrounding local support system, enhancing victims' understanding of police and judicial procedures.

The deployment of ISCGs has improved police responses to domestic violence cases by relieving officers of the social support duties that they are often ill-equipped to handle. This allows law enforcement to focus on criminal investigations while ensuring that victims receive the necessary social care. However, the scheme faces challenges, such as inconsistent funding and the psychological burden on ISCGs, who are unevenly integrated into the police organisations where they work (depending on the level of commitment from the hierarchy in supporting the scheme), sometimes work in relative isolation and deal with emotionally taxing cases. Despite these issues, embedded social workers play a crucial role in improving victim outcomes by fostering interagency cooperation and providing early intervention.

The scheme has been shown to prevent the escalation of domestic violence by offering timely assistance and increasing victims' trust in law enforcement. Through their unique position, ISCGs also raise awareness among police officers regarding the social and health services available to victims, thus enhancing the overall response to DV. In Réunion Island, ISCGs are viewed by all stakeholders as a crucial part of the victim support system, primarily because their role in supporting the victim during their first contact with institutions. Given that reporting violence to the police or gendarmerie is often the initial step for most victims in accessing institutional support, ISCGs frequently act as the gateway to this system,

facilitating access that allows victims to embark on an effective path towards receiving assistance.

The report highlights the recent introduction of FV Task Forces in the French judicial system to combat domestic and family violence (FV). These Task Forces, established in all courts and public prosecutors' offices, aim to enhance the prevention of high-impact domestic violence and improve victim protection. Implemented in 2019, they focus on coordination, information sharing, and specialisation to address domestic violence cases more effectively. The task forces facilitate collaboration between judicial actors, social workers, law enforcement, and victim support associations to ensure a comprehensive approach to victim safety and perpetrator accountability.

FV Task Forces articulate a series of other innovations such as the use of personalised victim assessments (EVVI), improved risk detection tools, Anti-Approach Bracelets (BAR), emergency tracks within jurisdictions, and a feedback process (RETEX) for evaluating systemic failures following homicides.

The report outlines put a particular emphasis on the role of specialised judicial assistants (JA VIF). These assistants play a crucial role in managing DV cases, supporting magistrates by assessing risk, gathering key information, and ensuring effective communication between judicial actors and victim support services. Their involvement helps compensate for the limited time magistrates can devote to these cases, ensuring continuity and improved case management. The presence of JA VIF has been instrumental in professionalising the handling of domestic violence cases, especially in regions like Réunion Island, where they act as key coordinators.

The report also highlights the importance of training in the success of these task forces. Many magistrates initially lack specialised knowledge in domestic violence cases, but through on-the-job training facilitated by the FV Task Forces and judicial assistants, they develop expertise. This training, combined with the increasing specialisation of magistrates in DV cases, ensures a more consistent and knowledgeable approach to domestic violence litigation.

However, challenges persist, including the strain on court resources, ethical concerns surrounding information sharing, and the emotional toll on magistrates handling FV cases. One of the major challenges identified is the tension between the institutional focus on victim

protection and the need to respect victims' autonomy and free will. The report notes that victims may not always want the protective measures imposed by the courts, such as anti-approach orders or notifications of an abuser's release. This creates a dilemma for magistrates, who must balance protecting victims from further harm with respecting their personal choices and circumstances. The judicial system's emphasis on protection can sometimes lead to paternalistic practices, treating victims as "at risk" individuals, rather than fully respecting their autonomy, a trend particularly noticeable in the application of judicial measures.

These two reforms have generally led to a reduction in femicides on Reunion Island - the number of which has been roughly halved - and to a significant improvement in the support provided to victims, as observed in our empirical investigation.

Methods

The report is based on a study of administrative, expert, and academic sources dedicated to the selected solutions, as well as professional articles and evaluation reports. In the case of embedded social workers, we also conducted an in-depth review of the international literature on this type of solution. Both solutions are highlighted in all parliamentary, independent administrative authority, and government reports we consulted. The data used for the description are listed in the respective solution.

The relevance of the solutions is supported by the results of our own empirical studies conducted in Reunion Island: interviews were carried out in a single area, the overseas region of Reunion Island – one of the French territories most affected by domestic violence, and one where the public response is most developed – at two different times: 2019 (53 interviews, as part as the IMPRODOVA project) and 2023 (34 interviews, with different respondents, except for 4 social workers who were re-interviewed, as part of the IMPROVE project T1.3). The sampling strategy enabled an analysis of the local consequences of policy change. Interviews were semi-structured, with questions about individual and organisational work practices on domestic violence, collaboration (or not) with other professions, and evaluation of the frontline response to DV.

Reasons for case selection

The primary reasons for selecting these two solutions are as follows:

- The CNRS IMPROVE team was able to directly examine the local implementation of these solutions and consult with various stakeholders about their perceived effectiveness and relevance. In both cases, the feedback received was overwhelmingly positive.
- These solutions are highly acclaimed at the national level and are regarded as significant advancements in domestic violence policies.
- Both solutions successfully contribute to establishing and maintaining active partnerships that bring together various local stakeholders. Both participate in successfully defining and promoting a common vision and clear, shared objectives within the partner network. It effectively promotes, facilitates, and organises information exchanges among partners.
- Both contribute to a comprehensive public policy response to victims. Victims benefit from a more personalised follow-up and support.
- Both solutions place emphasis on identifying and prioritising emergency situations, as well as assessing the danger faced by the victim, in order to provide appropriate responses.

ISCGs were introduced in a previous deliverable (D1.3), but this report offers new insight and analysis. The description and scrutiny of FV Task Forces, however, is an original input.

Solution 1: Embedded Social Workers

1.1.4.3 Description

1.1.4.3.1 Background and Aim

Initially, the role of French police social workers was to ensure that information gathered by police officers concerning situations of social distress was effectively communicated to, and utilised by, social services. Embedding social workers within police stations appeared to be the only efficient method to facilitate the swift transfer of information to social services. The establishment of embedded social workers marked the first instance of collaboration between the law enforcement sector and the social sector in France—two professional spheres that historically harboured mutual distrust (Biezanek et al., 2008).

- The main tasks currently assigned to ISCGs (Intervenants Sociaux en Commissariat et Gendarmerie) are as follows:

- Identifying situations of social distress to prevent their deterioration and any escalation.
- Facilitating help-seeking behaviours and providing social support for a limited period: specifically, when the victim reports abuse, files a complaint, is granted protection, and criminal investigations are initiated.
- Assessing the social needs of the victim.
- Informing the victim of their rights and social assistance entitlements, and referring them to appropriate support services, shelters, and victim support associations.
- Explaining police and legal procedures, and assisting the victim in interacting with police or gendarmerie officers.
- Establishing a network of contacts within various local support services to facilitate emergency responses for victims in need.
- Facilitating dialogue, understanding, and cooperation between the police and social sectors, and acting as an interface between various agencies.

The idea of embedding social workers within police and gendarmerie departments dates back to the early 1980s. During this period, there was growing recognition that a significant portion of police work involved elements of social work. It became evident that police interventions and criminal investigations generated a substantial amount of information regarding the social difficulties faced by victims. However, this information was rarely utilised to assist victims, despite its potential to trigger social interventions. The police and gendarmerie lacked both the tools and the expertise to address the social needs of victims. Consequently, tragedies occurred, where the warning signs had been detected by the police but could have been prevented if appropriate social measures had been implemented in time.

The scheme was successfully deployed for the first time in Limoges in 1991. A series of negotiations between stakeholders from 2002 to 2006 led to the definition of a workable framework. These negotiations involved the national police and gendarmerie, the government agency responsible for crime prevention, the relevant ministries (Interior, Justice, and Social Affairs), several local authorities and victim support NGOs, and the newly established professional organisation of police social workers, the national association of ISCGs (renamed ANISCG in 2006).

This framework was formalised in a circular issued by the Ministry of Interior on 21 December 2006. The directive established one of the scheme's fundamental principles: the ISCG is based within a police or gendarmerie department and operates under the functional authority of the department's chief, while simultaneously being employed by a local administration or social sector association and subject to the hierarchical authority of that service director (Biezanek et al., 2008). The following year, the scheme was enshrined in law by the Crime Prevention Act of 5 March 2007, and since 2013, all successive Inter-ministerial Plans to Combat Violence Against Women have included provisions for the scheme's expansion. ISCGs have increasingly been recognised as a new professional group within the social sector, working at the intersection of several fields: combating violence against women, child protection, access to rights and justice, and emergency social assistance (ANISCG, 2012). The number of ISCGs increased from 11 in 2005 to 164 in 2012, 261 in 2018, and 450 in 2023.

While women victims of domestic violence (DV) are the primary focus for ISCGs, the scheme also extends its benefits to other groups, including minors who are victims of DV, victims of sexual abuse, rape, or incest, and parents facing difficulties in raising their children.

1.1.4.3.2 Implementation and Practice

Creating a new ISCG position is a partnership process at the local level, involving the prefecture (the administration representing the government in a French department or region), the police or gendarmerie, one or more local authorities, and sometimes a victim support association. Local partners can adapt the scheme to their specific needs and constraints. The ISCG's tasks and employment framework are defined by a partnership agreement and a job description. This agreement specifies the ISCG's workplace, the resources allocated, the priority victim groups, preferred work methods, and more (ANISCG, 2012).

The police service hosting an ISCG must provide it with operating resources and ensure the day-to-day human resources management (leave of absence, overtime, etc.) (Biezanek et al., 2008). The administration or association that is the ISCG's employer is its sole hierarchical authority. It evaluates its work and professional performance. The ISCGs' work is conducted in accordance with legal and ethical rules governing social workers. The assistance and support provided to a victim must be accepted voluntarily. What victims say during meetings with social workers is confidential.

On average, a social worker deals with around 400 cases a year. The time devoted to each case depends on the nature and urgency of the situation. It varies according to the complexity of the case and the time needed to activate the relevant support services (ANISCG, FORS, 2012).

At local level, the steering and evaluation of the scheme is carried out by board which brings together the employer, the department's chief and the ISCG. Police social workers have reporting duties to their employer and to the police or gendarmerie department. They must provide data on the number of people received and supported, their profiles, their requests, the types of situations dealt with and the responses provided (ANISCG, 2012). At national level, the system is monitored by an inter-ministerial committee coordinated by the government agency in charge of crime prevention (CIPDR). Existing steering tools do not allow to assess the effectiveness and impact of the scheme (IGA, 2021).

ISCG's tasks:

DV detection: The first stage of support provided by an ISCG involves gathering information to identify victims who require intervention. This information is most commonly transmitted by the police or gendarmerie through various channels: the ISCG may have direct access to certain information systems; some police or gendarmerie officers regularly provide data to the ISCG; and officers may report situations of violence identified during DV calls (Biezanek et al., 2008). Less frequently, other DV stakeholders, such as social services, associations, hospitals, or schools, report victims they have detected. Finally, some victims directly contact the ISCG, typically upon the recommendation of a professional within the ISCG network.

Establishing Contact with Victims: Once a victim is detected, the ISCG initiates contact and suggests a meeting (either face-to-face at the ISCG office or remotely) to assess the situation. The ISCG may conduct a home visit when the situation allows and requires it. The ISCG prioritises contact with victims based on their initial assessment of the victim's needs and their current workload.

Victim's Needs Assessment: The next stage involves evaluating the victim's social needs. The ISCG conducts a comprehensive assessment of the individual's social situation, covering social, financial, psychological, legal, and family aspects (particularly the situation of children). In principle, the ISCG is not directly involved in assessing the severity of DV or the danger to the victim (IGA, 2021, p.29). However, they play a significant role in assessing the risk to children as part of the procedure for reporting children in danger.

Emergency Social Support: Finally, the ISCG provides the support deemed appropriate. The duration of this support varies from a few weeks to several months (IGA, 2021). Support concludes when the victim no longer requires police intervention and other social support services have assumed responsibility for the case.

In addition to the services already mentioned, the ISCG may provide various types of support, such as physically accompanying the victim to a police interview or court hearing, assisting with administrative procedures, or finding accommodation (Biezanek et al., 2008).

1.1.4.3.3 Weaknesses

Short-Term Funding: Each ISCG is funded differently, with financing arrangements varying over time depending on the agreement reached between partners, which is renegotiated annually. This results in significant uncertainties regarding the continuity of positions, requiring partners to engage each year in arduous discussions and cumbersome procedures. This creates the impression that the State is not investing adequately in the scheme, despite it being declared a national priority (IGA, 2021). Associations, which employ 46% of ISCGs, are particularly affected by this unpredictability. To mitigate budget deficits, they tend to recruit less qualified and less experienced ISCGs under more precarious employment conditions and with unattractive salaries, leading to high turnover (Ministère des Outre-mer, 2020).

1.1.4.4 Justification

The solution presented here meets the following selection criteria:

- Most widely employed solution
- Most established solution across different stakeholder groups
- Most effective solution

1.1.4.4.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

The main characteristics of the schemes that facilitated its development and successful implementation are as follows:

- A prolonged period of local experimentation and consultation among all stakeholders enabled the definition of objectives, organisational structures, and operating methods that were agreeable to all parties.
- Numerous studies, assessments, expert reports, and programmatic documents were produced to support this bottom-up construction process of the scheme. This high level

of reflexivity in the early stages contributed to establishing a solid foundation for subsequent policy developments.

- The legal framework of the scheme allows for significant local adaptation, with standardisation encouraged through the dissemination of best practices.
- Regular evaluations of the scheme's implementation have been conducted, involving all stakeholders. Based on these evaluations, a comprehensive implementation doctrine has gradually been developed.
- The professional association of ISCGs has actively and consistently participated in policy development. Through regular surveys of all police social workers, it has gained in-depth knowledge of local practices. This expertise enables ANISCG to exert considerable influence over the governance and management of the scheme.

Other factors such as Government commitment and support, interagency/inter-stakeholder cooperation, and community involvement were also present.

An important factor in the scheme's success is that it benefits the police without imposing additional constraints or interfering with their activities. The scheme is based on a strict division of labour between police officers and ISCGs. ISCGs are prohibited from interfering with police activities, particularly criminal investigations. The scheme allows for very few joint tasks, which means very few sources of potential conflict. ISCGs are tasked with relieving police officers of “extensive” victim support responsibilities, such as finding emergency accommodation or reporting a child at risk to appropriate social services. This enables police officers to focus entirely on “real” police tasks, such as responding to domestic violence calls and conducting criminal investigations.

On the other hand, ISCGs' regulation safeguards their professional autonomy from police interference, for reasons of professional secrecy. Police chiefs have no hierarchical authority on ISCGs working in their department, but only a functional authority. This means that the police or gendarmerie department managers can only define general guidelines, trigger the ISCG's intervention and check that ISCG is fulfilling its missions. This a posteriori control is carried out by means of regular statistical reports, and does not concern the way in which the ISCG has carried out its work.

The support of the police or gendarmerie department's hierarchy is crucial to the scheme's success. This support can manifest itself in various forms, such as memos or invitations to

specific work meetings (ANISCG, FORS, 2012). In the gendarmerie, the staff officer responsible for the department's prevention programs (OAP, deputy chief for prevention) must ensure that the new ISCG is well integrated into the workplace. Some OAP facilitate this by organising training sessions to explain the ISCG's role and how to cooperate with them. The OAP serves as the ISCG's primary point of contact in case of any issues (Ministry for Overseas France, 2020). When the ISCG lacks support from the department's management, several problems can arise: limited access to information crucial for identifying victims, inadequate working conditions (such as an unsuitable office or lack of equipment), and a rapid onset of burnout due to the constant need to reassert their role.

1.1.4.4.2 Practical relevance

By encouraging help-seeking behaviour, ISCGs allow certain situations to be addressed at an earlier stage, before they escalate into more dangerous circumstances. This approach prevents high-impact domestic violence and reduces the number of recurring calls that would otherwise require the mobilisation of scarce police resources (Ministry for Overseas France, 2020).

ISCGs add value to social services by detecting situations that would otherwise have remained unknown, enabling the provision of appropriate social support before matters worsen (Guide de promotion FORS, 2012).

The specific needs of vulnerable victims are not mentioned in the scheme's doctrine, and were mentioned rarely during the interviews. However, insofar as the scheme is designed to provide personalized assistance to the victims handled, ISCGs have the possibility of adapting their support on a case-by-case basis.

The ISCG functions as a "one-stop shop," providing comprehensive support to victims (Biezanek et al., 2008). The scheme facilitates police work by increasing victims' trust in law enforcement and their willingness to contribute to legal proceedings. In many departments, ISCGs relieve police officers of the task of informing victims about the outcome of their cases (Ministry for Overseas France, 2020).

Police officers have a clear interest in participating in the scheme, as they are relieved of social support duties that many consider outside their remit. ISCGs provide officers with a sense of job satisfaction and purpose by delivering appropriate responses to situations that

the police alone would not have been able to address adequately. This reduces the psychological burden on police officers (Biezanek et al., 2008; IGA, 2021).

As an interface, mediator, and buffer between the police and social sectors, the ISCG can facilitate mutual knowledge and understanding, which in turn can foster greater information sharing, conflict avoidance, convergence of views, coordination and collaboration between stakeholders of these sectors. Their work can help to break down inter-institutional, inter-organisational and inter-professional barriers, enabling the stakeholders to work together better and faster. (Biezanek et al., 2008).

Given their presence in the police workplace, ISCGs can raise officers' awareness and provide ongoing training, particularly on how to handle victims' sensitivity and trauma (Ministry for Overseas France, 2020). They can also assist police investigators in working with victims who struggle to discuss the violence they have experienced (Biezanek et al., 2008).

1.1.4.4.3 Evidence and Data

Various audits, particularly the most recent one conducted by the General Inspectorate of Administration in 2021, have highlighted the positive outcomes of the scheme, which has satisfied all the participants surveyed.

All successive national programmes and plans since the institutionalisation of ISCGs in 2006 have aimed to increase their number and geographical coverage.

The relevance of the proposed solutions is reinforced by findings from our empirical studies conducted in Réunion Island in 2019 and 2023, one of the French departments with the highest number of ISCGs (13 currently in service). We interviewed 9 embedded social workers and 29 police officers collaborating closely with them. Additionally, we gathered insights from 26 representatives of victim support NGOs and other key stakeholders through individual interviews with 20 magistrates, 6 healthcare professionals, 10 local government officials, and 5 representatives from local policy centres. Furthermore, focus groups held in 2024 provided additional perspectives, including those of 3 members of the Attorney General's Office, 3 members of the Appeal Court, 10 gendarmerie officers, 3 officials from the university hospital, and 7 members of the local research-action group on domestic violence, along with 5 representatives from victim support associations.

Finally, our findings were validated through the peer review process of an article submitted to a highly regarded and rigorous journals in the field of policing science, Policing. This resulted in the publication of the article: François Bonnet, Thierry Delpeuch, Jarmo Houtsonen, Marianne Mela, “Embedded social workers within police organisations: Comparing domestic violence interventions in France and Finland”, Policing: A Journal of Policy and Practice, Volume 18, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1093/police/paae065>

1.1.4.4.4 Context of the Solution

Police-social work partnership has increasingly become a pivotal aspect of the strategies deployed to enhance the support extended to victims of domestic violence (DV). This form of cooperative engagement traces its origins to the 1920s, mirroring a burgeoning recognition of the challenges police officers routinely encounter in managing individuals, including DV victims, who could benefit from the interventions offered by social services (Linhorst et al., 2022; Patterson and Swann, 2019). It has long been acknowledged that referring such individuals to pertinent social services constitutes an integral component of the police response to DV incidents (Patterson 2022).

Police personnel are often ill-equipped in terms of time, resources, and expertise to deliver the necessary support services to DV victims with multifaceted needs. The occupational culture within police departments tends to lead officers to view tasks associated with social work as outside their purview, consequently preferring to transfer such responsibilities to social workers (Bar-On, 1995). The development of police-social work collaborations gained substantial momentum in the United States during the 1970s, and from the 2000s onwards in Europe.

Today, it has become commonplace for police and social agencies to collaborate on DV issues (Patterson, 2022; Patterson and Swan, 2019). Forming police-social work partnerships is considered advantageous for multiple reasons: victims benefit from better protection and guidance (Messing et al., 2015), they receive a more comprehensive range of support services, with reduced access times (Corcoran et al., 2001; Lane et al., 2004); information and knowledge are better shared between professionals, so that they take more applicable, appropriate and proportionate decisions (Humphreys et al., 2018; Shorrock et al., 2020), which facilitates the achievement of professional goals for both entities. Contributions of embedded social workers to supporting DV victims have been well documented. Among the most significant are training police officers to improve their understanding of domestic

violence; sharing their own information and views to enhance the assessment of a particular case; making the police aware of solutions that can be delivered by the social and health sectors; providing reassurance, advice and guidance to the victims on a short-term basis, in the context of early case-finding interventions; assisting the victims with obtaining emergency resources; helping the police to maintain follow-up with the victims. Embedded social workers bring valuable know-how to the LEAs where they are embedded, such as using a trauma-informed care approach, making referrals to other sectors and agencies, reporting child abuse, offering family mediation and crisis intervention (Patterson, 2022; Alamo and Ornelas, 2021).

Forming partnerships between police forces and social work professionals to assist victims of domestic violence has been deemed advantageous for multiple reasons. These collaborative endeavours are expected to enhance the effectiveness of interventions and provide a more comprehensive support network for victims. While the police are equipped to offer immediate protection and enforce legal measures such as restraining orders to guarantee victim safety, social workers can facilitate access to essential resources including shelters, social assistance, and healthcare. Until recently, the dominant strategy for collaboration relied on making referrals for victims, enabling them to obtain necessary support services at the appropriate time. This method requires minimal joint effort between police officers and social workers, with the primary concern being that social workers are notified about victims identified by the police. Such information allows social workers to reach out to victims and provide them with crisis assistance, counselling, guidance, social care, and further referrals, offering a form of support distinct and separate from that provided by the police. As evidenced by numerous empirical studies, such of cooperation features a clear demarcation of responsibilities, which reduces the potential for conflict.

Various models of collaboration between police forces and social work agencies have been implemented. Some models, known as "police social workers," entail hiring professional social workers within law enforcement agencies themselves, while others involve inter-agency cooperation between local police forces and community-based social services, with each professional operating within their respective organisation. The police-social-work partnerships examined in France – the ISCG - falls into an intermediate model, where social workers, though employed by a social service agency, conduct their duties on police premises, sometimes as part of a police unit or team. This arrangement places them under

the dual authority of both the police force and their home organisation in the social sector. We refer to these professionals as "embedded social workers." Embedded social workers were initially introduced to enhance the efficiency of the referral-based approach in police-social-work partnerships. The rationale behind their development was that closer physical proximity between the two professional groups would facilitate easier transmission of information about victims to social workers and accelerate the provision of care.

In France, over the past decade, an alternative model of police-social work collaboration has been gaining ground, focusing on a more holistic and integrated response to the broad spectrum of victims' needs. This model acknowledges the importance of addressing legal, social, and health issues in a unified manner, rather than in isolation. It requires police officers and social workers to collaborate closely on various tasks essential for the protection, well-being, and recovery of victims and their children, both in the immediate aftermath and over the long term. These collaborative efforts may encompass risk assessment, safety planning, early intervention and prevention, case management, and follow-up activities, all designed to prevent victims from being overlooked or lost within the system. This holistic approach introduces a level of complexity and challenge beyond what is typical in referral-based models of cooperation. Furthermore, social workers who collaborate with the police, mainly ISCG, are expected to transfer valuable knowledge and expertise to police officers. This includes raising their awareness of the solutions that the social and health sectors can provide, employing a trauma-informed approach, and facilitating sensitive interactions with victims. This shift significantly impacts embedded social workers, in particular, due to their direct proximity and interaction with police officers. The challenge for ISCGs has evolved beyond merely working alongside police officers in a complementary role, serving as a bridge to support services outside the legal sector. Increasingly, the expectation is for social workers to function as integral members of a team with police officers.

This expanding victim-centred approach, which places greater emphasis on interdisciplinary teamwork than the referral-based approach, poses more challenges for social workers than for police officers. In both collaborative approaches, the social worker is responsible for the social care of victims, which accounts for the generally positive reception of such partnerships by police officers. However, in the victim-centred approach, social workers are also expected to contribute to police interventions. The parameters of these contributions, though, are primarily determined by the police. This closer involvement presents a significant challenge

for social workers due to their stringent confidentiality and ethical obligations. While their role traditionally emphasises victim support within a framework that prioritises privacy and trust, the necessity of integrating into police processes can create tensions. These tensions arise from the need to balance their professional commitment to confidentiality and ethical practice with the operational demands and objectives of law enforcement, which may prioritise information sharing and procedural requirements differently. This complex interplay demands that social workers navigate their duties in a way that respects their professional standards while contributing effectively to a partnership that operates under police-defined terms.

1.1.4.4.5 Unintended Consequences and Risks

Isolation in the Workplace: ISCG can contribute to widening the gap between sectors instead of bringing them together. As the ISCG takes care of all communication and interface tasks, police and social services professionals no longer need to maintain direct relations. As a result, some partnerships developed before the ISCG's creation may weaken or disappear. Some ISCGs suffer from workplace isolation. Half of ISCGs experience professional isolation due to a lack of contact and support from their employing organisation (as a consequence of being based outside that organisation) and a lack of relationships and support from police officers in their workplace (ANISCG, FORS, 2012). ISCGs experiencing loneliness are particularly exposed to psychosocial risks, as they face victims' distress daily (Ministry for Overseas France, 2020). The solution is to organise mutual support and peer advice groups, and to provide sufficient supervision and training (IGA, 2021).

Ambiguities of Shared Confidentiality: In principle, the ISCG is bound by professional secrecy not to disclose any information to the police that a victim entrusts to them, except under special circumstances. If the ISCG considers that it is in the victim's best interest for the police to be informed, they must seek the victim's consent. The ISCG is not supposed to participate in police investigations of the case. In practice, however, the ISCG often acquires information that is useful for protecting a victim and their children, and it is unclear whether this information falls within the scope of professional secrecy. On the other hand, some police or gendarmerie officers appreciate discussing complex cases with the ISCG to gain different perspectives (Biezanek et al., 2008). Unsure whether or not they have the right to share the information, the ISCG may pass it on informally, but only to a police officer they trust deeply (IS-COM-974-2023-1). The ISCG must learn how to convey such information in a way that

does not make police officers feel that they are attempting to interfere with their work or influence their decisions.

The fact that ISCG professional secrecy is circumstantial and conditional, as well as the provisions for shared confidentiality, are a permanent source of ethical and legal uncertainty and dilemmata for ISCGs. This can have unintended effects, such as the isolation of ISCGs from police officers, or on the contrary, the development of personal informal relationships that may result in the ISCG's participating unofficially in criminal investigations.

A key lesson from the US-based literature is that police officers seem overall more satisfied with police-social work collaborations than social workers (Curtis and Lutkus, 1985; Giacomazzi and Smithey, 2001; Sudderth, 2006), for whom ethical and deontological challenges in working with the police are more salient. Social workers are often concerned that working with police officers carries the risk of giving priority to punitive and security-oriented responses over more preventive and therapeutic ones. A key area in which these concerns play out is the exchange of information.

Too much psychological burden: ISCGs face numerous stressors and challenges at work, primarily due to the psychological burden of continuously dealing with domestic violence cases. Many lack job security as they are employed on temporary contracts and the scheme's funding is unreliable. They are often required to work flexible hours and overtime to handle urgent situations, usually without additional compensation (IGA, 2021; ANISCG, FORS, 2012). The division of labour and responsibilities, which previously helped avoid tensions and conflicts with police officers, is now being challenged by the priority given to victim protection. Under pressure to prevent high-impact domestic violence, police and gendarmerie departments where ISCGs are based seek to hold them jointly accountable in the event of a tragic incident. Today, every tragedy triggers an administrative inquiry to pinpoint the responsible party and identify any mistakes, negligence, or wrongdoing. While this push for greater accountability has the advantage of improving professional skills and service quality, it also significantly increases the psychological burden on ISCGs, leading to higher rates of burnout and turnover.

Solution 2: Judicial Task Forces to Combat Family Violence and Related Innovations

This document examines recent solutions introduced into the French judicial system to combat high-impact domestic violence and improve victim protection. The most significant innovation, which forms the foundation for all others, is the establishment of judicial task forces dedicated to domestic and family violence (FV) within all courts and public prosecutors' offices. These FV Task Forces, along with the innovations they bring, are significantly transforming the philosophy and operational principles of the French judicial system. As their implementation began only in 2019, it is still too early to definitively assess their effectiveness in preventing high-impact domestic violence or protecting victims. However, they are already widely utilised across France, and some of their positive and negative impacts are becoming evident. Within the Reunion Island judicial system and as part of our study on the management of domestic violence cases we have observed and analysed these impacts.

1.1.4.5 Description

1.1.4.5.1 *Background and Aim*

Current focus on combatting high impact domestic violence in France

In France today, efforts to combat domestic violence are primarily centred on the prevention of fatal violence. The imperative to eliminate femicides has emerged as the dominant interpretive framework for addressing domestic violence as a public issue, serving as the main driver for public policy reform and as a top priority for professionals across all sectors involved in intervention. This shift has been catalysed by a series of social, media, and political mobilisations that gained momentum in the late 2010s.

One of the principal causes of public discontent driving this movement was the rising public awareness that a third of femicide victims had filed complaints or reported their situation to the police before their deaths. In response to the criticisms, the Ministry of Justice initiated an audit in June 2019 to examine how judicial actors had handled cases that ultimately resulted in spousal homicide (IGJ, 2019).

The report identified several key issues: insufficient attention to warning signs, inadequate case follow-up, failures in inter-service coordination, and a lack of communication, analysis, and utilisation of information.

Additionally in autumn 2019, a major national conference on combatting domestic violence was held, known as the "Grenelle of domestic violence".

These developments have led to a new concern within the services and structures responsible for supporting victims of domestic violence: the fear of failing to give due attention to a report that could forewarn of an impending homicide. In this context, femicide is seen as a foreseeable crime—one that occurs because the relevant institutions did not take the necessary measures to prevent it.

This approach to understanding domestic violence demands that practitioners continuously search for warning signs, i.e., less severe forms of violence that might precede lethal violence. From this perspective, ignoring, neglecting, or misinterpreting these early signs is equated with organisational failures and professional misconduct. One of the primary duties of practitioners is to address these shortcomings, which requires a rigorous examination of their practices and modes of operation, particularly in relation to the detection of violent situations, the assessment of danger, and the prompt implementation of appropriate protective measures.

The adoption of this new policy framework, which prioritises victim safety within the judicial system, has led to significant transformations in the justice system to meet the imperative of protecting victims.

Key Areas of Reform in Response to the New Priority

The first major area of reform is the enhancement of specialisation within the judicial system. Dedicated interagency collaborations, internal networks, court divisions and case management processes for handling domestic violence cases have been established within prosecutors' offices and courts, all under the governance of a steering board and under the leadership of a coordinating magistrate. The latter is itself supported by a team of specialised collaborators, which is something new in the French judiciary, where magistrates traditionally work more individually than collectively. These new organisational arrangements - referred to as task forces against family violence - are responsible for coordinating the monitoring and processing of cases, improving the organisation of victim support and protection, and developing a comprehensive strategy for the jurisdiction.

Other innovations have been introduced, such as tools and mechanisms for detecting and managing risks, as well as procedures and information systems designed to enhance information sharing. There is also an increased use of social and psychological expertise to assess the vulnerability of victims and the dangerousness of perpetrators.

One of the most significant innovations is the creation of a feedback process for evaluating failures after each domestic homicide, aimed at identifying systemic, organisational and professional shortcomings that contributed to the occurrence of the crime.

Family Violence Task Forces and Coordinators

Decree No. 2023-1077 of 23 November 2023 establishes specialised domestic and family violence task forces within judicial courts and courts of appeal. Technically, this is implemented through the creation of new articles in the Code of Judicial Organisation (COJ) (Art. R. 212-62-1 COJ: Family Violence Task Forces within Judicial Courts; Art. R. 212-62-1 COJ: Family Violence Steering Committee; Art. R. 312-83-1 – FV Task Forces within Courts of Appeal).

According to this framework, Family Violence Task Forces are coordinated by two specially trained magistrates from the judicial court and the public prosecutor's office (Art. R. 212-62-1 COJ). These task forces consist of judiciary personnel—magistrates, clerks, judicial assistant, contractual agents—who are particularly dedicated to handling DV cases.

Under the leadership of a steering committee (Family Violence Steering Committee) co-chaired by the president of the judicial court and the public prosecutor, these task forces are tasked with developing, implementing, and evaluating measures to combat DV and other forms of family violence (DV constitutes the vast majority of family violence cases handled by French courts, which also include violence against children and against ascendants), improving the case management system for these cases, and sharing expertise among justice professionals. They are intended to serve as a forum for information exchange, such as on hearing dates, release from detention, and protective measures implemented for victims, to better coordinate civil and criminal proceedings initiated against violent partners or parents. The task forces are designed to facilitate coordinated and swift action by all actors in the judicial chain, particularly members of the public prosecutor's office, sentence enforcement judges, liberty and custody judges, juvenile judges, family court judges, as well as external partners involved in DV policy, such as representatives of the police and gendarmerie, prison administration, bar associations, victim support associations, and others.

In addition, each court must establish a family violence steering committee that brings together the various relevant judicial actors to enhance information exchange, coordinate the monitoring and handling of cases, and improve support provided to victims.

The fight against domestic violence can be incorporated into a jurisdiction's strategy. This strategy allows the two heads of the local judicial system (the president of the Judicial Court and the chief public prosecutor) to clearly articulate the various policy measures, provide it with external visibility, and ensure its ongoing steering and assessment.

Measures to promote enhanced information sharing

One of the main objectives of FV Task Forces is to improve the sharing of information throughout the judicial process among the various stakeholders involved in combatting DV and FV, namely the public prosecutors' offices, Judicial Court services, probation and integration services (SPIP), penitentiary institutions, victim support associations, associations responsible for socio-educational judicial supervision of perpetrators, and law enforcement agencies.

To this end, the Ministry of Justice undertook the development of the SISPoPP database (Computerised System for Monitoring Priority Criminal Policies) starting in 2022. This IT record tool was established by Decree No. 2023-935 of 10 October 2023. It allows magistrates to access more information when ruling on domestic violence cases.

“By centralising all data related to cases monitored under domestic violence, whether from civil or criminal proceedings, as well as information exchanged within the FV Steering Committees, SISPoPP facilitates collaboration among those involved in combatting domestic violence by providing an up-to-date and multidisciplinary perspective. SISPoPP can be effectively updated by staff assigned to the specialised task forces, with differentiated access modes defined by the heads of jurisdictions, according to the roles of the various users. Equipped with functionalities for managing victim protection measures, automated or customisable alert mechanisms, and indicators for child protection and released convicts, SISPoPP enhances the courts' ability to monitor this priority criminal policy” (Circular of 24 November 2023).

This system is intended to allow for real-time, updated, and contextualised monitoring of the accused in the event of a new incident brought to the attention of the judicial institution. If necessary, automated alerts will be sent to selected recipients for rapid management. This tool is designed to provide access to relevant documents from both criminal and civil proceedings, ensure their preservation, and facilitate the sharing of certain information according to the access level of each partner.

The system's data input and usage are managed at the local level by the FV Task Forces.

Measures to improve risk assessment: recommendation for increased use of social and psychological expertise

FV Task Forces are making increasingly systematic use of "personalised assessments of the victim's situation" procedure (EVVI), as provided for in Article 10-5 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, in accordance with the circular of 9 May 2019 concerning the improvement of the handling of domestic violence cases and the protection of victims. The EVVI objective is to identify risk signals to provide an appropriate response to the complainant's situation and, if necessary, to utilise the "grave danger" emergency phone device (TGD) to protect them.

Creation of an Emergency Track within Jurisdictions

Driven by the governance and management of FV Task Forces, all jurisdictions have, to varying degrees, implemented measures to ensure the prompt consideration of protection orders. This development was accelerated by the law of 28 December 2019, which mandates a six-day period between the scheduling of the hearing and the decision on the protection order (in practice, this allows an eight-day period for making a decision on protection orders). Family court services (JAF) have had to adapt their organisation to meet this procedural deadline.

An emergency track involves supporting victims through victim support offices, close cooperation between victim protection associations and the public prosecutor's office, particularly for the issuance of "grave danger" phones (TGD), responsiveness from court services and lawyers, as well as effective communication between the family court and the public prosecutor's office. In the jurisdictions in Réunion Island that we studied, these conditions were in place, but they created such a workload that it negatively impacted other aspects of judicial activity.

Some jurisdictions have specialised criminal hearings to ensure that domestic violence cases are handled separately and more swiftly compared to other criminal cases. Jurisdictions are increasingly favouring the immediate appearance procedure, which provides less favourable defence conditions for the accused.

Anti-Approach Bracelet (BAR)

A new victim protection tool has been made available to the FV Task Forces: Anti-Approach Bracelet (BAR). Created by Law No. 2019-1480 of 28 December 2019 and implemented by

Decree No. 2020-1161 of 23 September 2020, the BAR is an electronic device designed to ensure compliance with the prohibition imposed on a person from approaching the victim within a certain distance, through geolocation and real-time monitoring. The system includes a mobile unit given to both the victim and the perpetrator, along with an electronic bracelet worn by the latter. An alarm is triggered as soon as the distances set by the court decision are breached.

When the Anti-Approach Bracelet (BAR) is activated due to the wearer entering a pre-alert zone, an operator contacts them to instruct them to change direction. If the perpetrator enters the alert zone despite this warning, the operator contacts them again, instructing them to leave the area. Simultaneously, another operator contacts the victim, advising them to seek safety, and triggers a specific alert to the police, who then decide on the appropriate actions based on the received information.

The BAR can be ordered in both criminal and civil matters. In criminal cases, the measure can be applied to any person accused of an offence punishable by at least three years of imprisonment (Article 132-45-1 of the Penal Code). In civil matters, the BAR can be ordered as part of a protection order (Article 515-11-1 of the Civil Code), but it cannot be imposed on the defendant without the consent of both parties.

The deployment of the BAR across all jurisdictions was completed by the end of 2020. Each year in France, approximately one thousand victims benefit from this.

The creation of a feedback process for evaluating systemic and organisational failures after each domestic homicide

The creation of FV Task Forces has been accompanied by reforms to systematise the evaluation of how judicial and interagency structures and networks handled high-impact cases of domestic and family violence. Each homicide must undergo a thorough review, known as RETEX (“experience feedback”), which examines how the situation was detected and managed by all relevant law enforcement agencies and support services. These RETEX are managed by the head of the appellate court (which is the hierarchical superior of the heads of the local Judicial Courts) and the appellate court district Attorney General (who is the hierarchical superior of local chief public prosecutors).

The RETEX gathers all stakeholders involved in the case management. It does not include the direct actors in the domestic homicide case but involves the heads of the relevant

services. Specific questionnaires for each function are sent to the actors involved and are subsequently analysed and shared among service heads. The results of these reflections are disseminated among stakeholders within the district of the appellate court and are communicated by the Attorney General to the Ministry of Justice.

In principle, the objective of these RETEX is not to assign blame, but to collectively share all relevant information, identify signals that could have prompted protective measures, and learn to collaborate more effectively. But in practice, due to the solemn nature of the RETEX framework and its focus on fatal violence, individuals feel targeted and threatened by the RETEX process.

The Ministry of Justice has produced tools to aid local stakeholders in conducting a RETEX: dedicated questionnaires for each actor, a timeline, and a methodological guide, all disseminated by a circular dated 3 September 2020, instructing the initiation of a RETEX for each domestic homicide. However, there is no overarching reference framework or guidelines.

The FV Task Forces must analyse the results of the RETEX (Return of Experience) and draw the necessary conclusions to improve organisation, procedures, and local coordination.

1.1.4.5.2 Implementation and Practice, as observed in Reunion Island

The central role of judicial assistants in FV Task Forces

The jurisdictions in Reunion Island have opted to recruit specialised judicial assistants for handling domestic and family violence cases (JA VIF) and have entrusted them with a key role in the operation of the FV task forces. The JA VIF are tasked with assisting magistrates in identifying, assessing, and monitoring FV cases that are sensitive in terms of victim safety. They are responsible for improving the circulation and utilisation of information by ensuring the systematic consultation of available records and files. Additionally, they must ensure that critical information reaches the magistrates who need it, by contacting other professionals (institutional or associative) involved in handling the case when necessary. Eventually, the JAs will play a major role in feeding information into SISPoPP, by entering data on Anti-Approach Bracelets (BAR), "grave danger" emergency phones (TGD), and protection orders (OP) to guarantee information sharing within the jurisdictions.

The Saint-Denis Public Prosecutor's Office tasks the JA with conducting the personalised victim situation assessments (EVVI) in collaboration with specialised associations' experts.

When certain elements of a case suggest a potential risk to the victim, the JA consults various judicial records to gather information assessing the perpetrator's dangerousness, such as criminal history, information on previous victims, etc. The JA specifically seeks information about the perpetrator that is not recorded in the TAJ record (judicial history database), such as details about criminal settlements or the perpetrator's attendance in alternative measures to prosecution, such as rehabilitation programmes. The JA also contacts external partners who are familiar with the situation to gather any information useful for risk assessment.

The JA compiles the necessary documents to support protection order requests that the prosecutor's office submits to the family court judge (JAF). They prepare criminal settlement orders and certain requisitions. The JA VIF at the prosecutor's office compensates for the lack of time magistrates have to conduct more in-depth examinations of cases requiring it. The magistrate refers the case to the JA, who checks if the victim is already known and assesses the necessity of a BAR or TGD.

The JA also plays a role in preparing for prison releases and in implementing post-sentence measures by maintaining contact with the victim. For example, they are responsible for informing the victim of a sentence reduction and explaining the protection measures that are being proposed.

How Reunion Island judicial actors use FV Task Forces for accelerating and simplifying case processing

To better ensure victims' safety, the FV Task Forces in Reunion Island have adopted a strategy that prioritises the simplest and quickest procedures. Accelerated processes for handling DV cases have been introduced, relying on a systematic use of a series of procedures that can be carried out rapidly: placing the presumed perpetrator in custody and conducting an in flagrante delicto (crime in progress) investigation, immediate appearance and summary trial, directing cases to single-judge courts, and pre-sentencing judicial control. Mechanisms have been put in place to better identify cases that require greater attention and urgent decisions.

Such rapid criminal procedures provide better protection for the victim than protection orders. It is easier for the prosecutor to establish the plausibility of the alleged violence and the existence of immediate danger. The prosecution has authority over police investigation units. It also has the ability to commission expert assessments from specialised associations, such

as enhanced social investigations into the family situation (EVVI), psychological assessments, and evaluations of the victim's needs and risks.

In contrast, family court judges (JAFs) rely on the evidence provided by the parties, which is often insufficient, even though JAFs tend to be less demanding regarding the quality of the evidence. Their ability to commission expert reports is very limited, especially since they have only about eight days to rule on a protection order request (a timeframe that can be reduced to 24 hours since the adoption of the provisional immediate protection order by Law No. 2024-536 of 13 June 2024). Additionally, JAFs do not have the network of external experts and stakeholders available to the prosecution.

This is why judicial actors in Reunion Island have chosen to prioritise criminal avenues over civil remedies. This strategy has had consequences for the perception of the courts, as the determination of the judiciary to combat domestic violence is often assessed by the number of protection orders issued. The low number of protection orders requested and granted in Reunion Island raises questions and may be seen as problematic.

Moreover, the standardisation of rapid procedures imposes specific organisational constraints. The policy of systematic custody requires prosecutors, particularly FV Task Force coordinators, to devote a significant portion of their work time to managing these cases. As a result, these specialised magistrates are unable to engage as much as they would like in the strategic planning, coordination and implementation of their jurisdiction's DV policy.

1.1.4.5.3 Weaknesses

All these innovations face the obstacle of court congestion. Prioritising domestic violence cases impacts the processing times of other cases, particularly in jurisdictions that have not been granted additional resources.

The cross-disciplinary approach to handling domestic violence cases and the emphasis on partnership work result in a significant number of meetings, which the relevant magistrates do not have the time to attend regularly. As a result, they tend to prioritise those meetings that are more directly related to their specific role, which limits the dialogue between services.

Regarding RETEX, its focus on domestic homicides may seem problematic, as valuable lessons can be drawn from analysing effective interventions that precede acts of violence with less severe consequences. It is at this earlier stage that processes should ideally be halted.

1.1.4.6 Justification

Correspondence with the template's criteria for selecting solutions:

- Most widely employed solution
- Most recently developed or novel solution

1.1.4.6.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

As part of the reforms to improve the management of domestic violence cases, FV Task Forces have been allocated specific human resources, including judicial assistants (assistant judge) and project managers, many of whom have been dedicated to the jurisdiction's DV policy. These staffs dedicated to FV task forces play an active role that magistrates do not always have the time to fulfil. They are able to comprehensively monitor FV-related activities, create links between different court services and with external associations and partners, produce tracking tables for domestic violence cases, and enrich magistrates' files for hearings. In doing so, they facilitate the continuity of case management and the interaction between different actors.

Another factor of successful implementation is the positive feedback loop that links professionalisation and specialisation.

The role of the FV Task Force coordinator requires magistrates to dedicate a larger portion of their work time to handling these types of cases, leading to a form of specialisation. "Even though I had some experience with these kinds of cases before becoming a FV coordinator, I didn't consider myself a specialist. Today, given the time I spend on it, I must admit that I have become one." (FV Coordinator of a public prosecutor's office)

Specialisation is seen as a means to ensure that cases are handled by magistrates who have developed an interest in the field and to exclude those who are not motivated by this type of litigation.

The FV Steering Committees (COFIL VIF) also play a role in providing on-the-job training to magistrates arriving in Reunion Island without specific training in this type of litigation. Many magistrates still lack specialised training, partly because the implementation of such training by the National School for the Judiciary (ENM) is relatively recent.

The work of specialised judicial assistants helps alleviate magistrates' apprehensions about becoming more involved in the fight against domestic violence. The primary obstacle in this regard is the fear of increased workload adding to the already existing overload of work which

is commonplace in the poorly financed French judicial system. Having the support of a specialised JA can encourage some to take on this challenge. As one task force coordinator emphasised, the capacity for action provided by the specialised JAs allows judicial actors to fully invest in the field of combatting domestic violence.

Previously, the dynamics of specialisation and professionalisation were hindered by the significant turnover of magistrates. Magistrate rotations are faster in the Overseas Territories than in mainland France, and there are more vacant positions. Since most magistrates leave Reunion Island after the minimum assignment duration of two years, the services experience rapid staff turnover. This phenomenon is precisely due to the unbearable workload exacerbated by high turnover. This leads to a loss of acquired experience as well as knowledge of the local context and its specificities. Since the JAs tend to remain in place for longer periods, their presence ensures continuity in the practices developed within the task forces and interagency cooperation, and allow for better transmission of skills and organisational memory.

The same applies to specialised training: the JAs attend or organise training programmes and transfer the knowledge gained to the magistrates. "They help us come out of our ivory tower. They are vectors of professionalisation. We encourage them to pursue training as part of a long-term policy" (President of Reunion Island Court of Appeals).

1.1.4.6.2 Practical relevance

The FV Task Forces and steering boards enable the development and implementation of a truly cross-disciplinary approach to handling domestic violence across the jurisdiction, involving all relevant services. They represent a "small revolution," as previously, such policies were led solely by the public prosecutor's office. With the creation of FV Task Forces, both the courts and the prosecutor's office must develop a common strategy and work in partnership.

In dealing with domestic violence cases, jurisdictions have adopted a more comprehensive and cross-disciplinary approach. This approach recognises that situations of violence evolve over time. It is attentive to the complexity of these situations and the challenges of protecting victims and their children. The judicial system is thus moving away from the piecemeal handling of individual cases, evolving towards a more holistic management of situations, focused on risk reduction.

The generalisation of victim's situation assessments, particularly through the EVVI, provides information that allows for more in-depth monitoring and support than previously possible. The same associations that produce the EVVI also offer support to victims and alert the public prosecutor's office to sensitive situations, making the EVVI one of the possible starting points for comprehensive and collaborative care.

Information flows more effectively between the various services, particularly between the public prosecutor's offices and the sentence enforcement judges (JAP) in preparing for prison releases. The objective of this collaboration is to determine whether the victim is still in contact with the perpetrator and whether there is a risk that the perpetrator may return to the victim's home.

According to court officials, the ability to deploy a jurisdiction-wide policy on domestic violence largely depends on the coordination, liaison, management, and monitoring work carried out by the JA VIF. The judicial assistants drive the local initiatives decided by the FV Task Force. Several interviewed magistrates noted that having personnel fully dedicated to the coordination and implementation of a specific jurisdictional policy is a significant innovation. Thanks to the JA VIF, jurisdictions have been able to establish the organisational structures and operational methods that allow them to prioritise and manage DV cases in a truly cross-disciplinary manner.

1.1.4.6.3 Evidence and Data

The positive impacts of FV Task Forces have been assessed in the framework of our IMPROVE empirical research conducted in Réunion Island in 2023 and 2024. All judicial bodies in the region, including the Attorney General's Office, the Appeal Court, and both Judicial Courts and Public Prosecutor Offices, have implemented FV Task Forces. We conducted interviews with 8 prosecutors (including 3 FV Task Force coordinators), 8 judges (among them 3 FV Task Force coordinators), and 2 specialised judicial assistants (JA VIF). Moreover, focus groups held in 2024 offered further insights from 10 gendarmerie officers, 3 officials from the university hospital, 7 members of the local research-action group on domestic violence, and 6 representatives from victim support associations. While the majority expressed positive views on the innovations introduced, several concerns were raised, as outlined in the report.

In France, there has not yet been either a study or an evaluation of the FV Task Forces.

1.1.4.6.4 *Context of the Solution*

The fight against violence against women, declared a major national cause of the presidential term by the President of the Republic on 25 November 2017, gained momentum with the organisation of the Grenelle against domestic violence in November 2019. This Grenelle brought together key public and associative actors. The decisions made following the Grenelle form the current national plan to combat domestic violence.

The solutions implemented within the judicial system after 2019 were largely developed and negotiated with all stakeholders of the DV policy during the Grenelle. This is why they are particularly coherent with other sectors of this policy.

The heads of judicial courts and local prosecutor's offices, divided by the head of the regional appellate courts and the Attorney General, have been assigned a leading role in the inter-sectoral coordination of the fight against domestic violence. They are now responsible for leading victim support efforts within their jurisdiction. In collaboration with subsidised victim support associations, they organise a local victim support strategy. They are also tasked with implementing targeted actions based on partnership protocols to improve care and protection for particularly vulnerable or severely traumatised victims. This leadership role has generated significant engagement within the judicial system to improve the local DV policy.

1.1.4.6.5 *Unintended Consequences and Risks*

Improvement in information sharing that raises concerns regarding the adversarial process

The reforms have facilitated better information flow between various services within the prosecution and judicial offices, as well as between judicial actors and other DV policy stakeholders, such as victim support associations. However, this raises concerns regarding the respect for the adversarial process.

Specialised task forces dealing with FV enable the sharing of information that extends beyond the confines of individual case files. This presents a challenge, particularly for civil judges, especially family court judges (JAF), who issue protection orders and must base their decisions solely on the evidence presented in the case file. At the same time, the priority of protecting victims motivates some judges to seek out additional contextual information necessary for making appropriate decisions. The question of whether a family court judge should conduct their own investigation—similar to a prosecutor—remains a contentious issue

in the courts. As a result, civil proceedings are taking on a more criminal character, even though JAFs do not have the resources to conduct investigations. The information that partner stakeholders might provide "off the record" is more of a hindrance than a help in handling cases, as the adversarial process renders such information unusable, and even potentially dangerous, as it could provide grounds for challenging the validity of the procedures.

"This approach puts civil judges at odds with their duties. The intelligence collected through new mechanisms and partnerships of information sharing on DV should be appropriately introduced into the trial proceedings, which the current process does not allow. Moreover, this information is not insignificant from the perspective of maintaining judicial impartiality, because it is primarily the prosecution that feeds the DV databases." (a FV Task Force coordinating judge)

The close relationship that DV interagency collaborations foster between the judiciary and victim support associations (or those dealing with perpetrators) raises concerns among some JAFs. These associations are often seen as advocating for those they represent, namely the victims, and collaborating with such actors could be perceived as compromising the impartiality required in judicial decision-making.

"I am increasingly being asked to seek out missing information when a protection order request is not sufficiently substantiated. According to the law, this is not my role. I do not have the tools for that. The role of the family court judge is not to conduct investigations, follow-up, or prevention. It is not within the scope of my function to act as a prosecutor, nor to advocate for a cause." (family court judge)

Even though they are reluctant to take on the role of a prosecutor, family court judges are increasingly less hesitant to impose restrictive measures to protect the victim, such as suspending the parental rights of the violent intimate partner.

Specialisation presents several challenges

The idea of specialised FV Task Forces is criticised by some magistrates. Handling a succession of DV cases in quick succession can change the magistrate's perspective on these matters, potentially leading to a diminished perception of the severity of certain incidents. Additionally, in specialised DV hearings, perpetrators are in close proximity in the

courtroom, allowing them to compare themselves with others, which may reinforce the notion that their violent behaviour is normal.

Some magistrates perceive this type of litigation as highly repetitive, with the same profiles of couples and types of situations recurring frequently— the domestic tyrant, the young couple unable to manage conflicts peacefully, etc.

Dealing with this type of litigation is not insignificant for anyone. The more judicial actors are confined to specialised case flow, the greater is the risk of becoming jaded or indifferent. “The all-encompassing focus on DV leads to burnout among actors. We won’t be able to sustain this over the long term.” (FV Task Force coordinator of a public prosecutor’s office). Specialisation would require psychological support mechanisms and specific training to counteract burnout and desensitisation, which are not yet in place.

In addition, establishing a specialised framework creates the expectation of higher quality. This, in turn, prompts magistrates to want to spend more time on cases. This poses a problem for magistrates who must handle a heavy caseload, such as sentence enforcement judges (JAP), who have limited time to examine each case thoroughly and only deal with DV cases as part of their overall workload. These magistrates have limited availability to discuss cases with their colleagues in the task force.

The increased demand for expertise cannot be met

Some magistrates interviewed regret the lack of sufficient psychological expertise, which would be useful in supporting or even informing their decisions. This type of expertise is particularly necessary for understanding sexual violence. The technical opinion of a psychologist is also valuable in determining the appropriate protective measures to implement. In many cases, magistrates must forgo ordering an expert evaluation due to budgetary constraints or the unavailability of experts.

As a result, magistrates tend to reserve psychological evaluations for the rare cases where the only incriminating acts are psychological violence. When a case involves both psychological and physical violence, which is quite common, only the physical violence is often judged to expedite and simplify case processing.

A growing tension between the institutional concern for protecting victims and respecting their freedom of choice

Judicial actors dealing with DV cases feel constantly under institutional, political, media, and social pressure.

"Preventing femicides is a major concern because they make headlines and leave a lasting impact on public consciousness" (PP CA).

The occurrence of femicides is a central criterion for assessing the performance of the courts, as well as the effectiveness of all involved professionals.

Since the creation of the feedback process (RETEX) in 2020, every femicide triggers a thorough interagency audit, focusing on how the case was detected and managed by all relevant law enforcement agencies and support services. RETEX are organised at the level of the appellate court district, under the supervision of the district's public prosecutor. This assessment aims to evaluate the work done by all professionals involved: police and gendarmerie officers, members of the judiciary, social workers, medical professionals, education professionals, etc.

Due to this pressure, some magistrates fear deviating from standard responses, such as imposing a contact ban on the presumed or confirmed perpetrator of violence. The magistrate faces a dilemma when the victim requests the lifting of such a ban. Should such a request always be denied on the grounds that a victim making such a request is inevitably under the coercive control of their violent partner (therefore unable to take an informed and reasonable decision). Or on the contrary should the magistrate consider the victim's wishes and, if appropriate, grant the request after reassessing the intimate partners' situation and weighing the risks (considering that, regardless of the court's decision, the victim will resume relations with the perpetrator if they are determined to do so, for various reasons that belong to them).

This type of decision is seen as a risk, particularly since magistrates generally lack sufficient information and analyses regarding the danger. In addition to concerns for the victim's safety, there is also the fear of being stigmatised and possibly even sanctioned by their institution if things go wrong and a RETEX is initiated.

Magistrates may also feel institutional pressure when faced with cases of isolated violence within a couple, such as during the discovery of an extramarital affair or the announcement of a breakup. It is difficult to determine whether it is an isolated incident, unlikely to recur, or if this initial violence signals the potential for further incidents.

In uncertainty, institutional pressure drives magistrates to take maximum precautions and avoid less coercive solutions such as family mediation. In principle, such a measure is prohibited when violence is repeated or indicates a situation of coercive control, but in cases of doubt, the magistrate may choose not to employ it for handling potentially—but not certainly—isolated violence, even though the measure could be useful (after verifying that the interested parties agree to participate).

Another manifestation of the pressure lies in the way some magistrates use the option to place the perpetrator in a specialised rehabilitation centre. These centres offer anti-recidivism programmes tailored to perpetrators of lower risk who are more likely to amend their behaviour. However, it is sometimes the most deeply entrenched perpetrators of violence who are directed to these centres, not for rehabilitation purposes but to get them under surveillance. Consequently, the chances of success in rehabilitation and reintegration efforts are low. This creates difficulties for the associations that manage these centres, as they are partly funded based on their success rates.

As a precaution, some magistrates prefer to keep a perpetrator in detention when they have doubts about their danger rather than release them with an anti-approach device, such as a restraining bracelet (BAR). These magistrates are then criticised for the low number of BAR they order, as the number of devices assigned to perpetrators is another evaluation criterion.

The systematic use of custody is another way of demonstrating the zeal of the justice system (or rather the pressure it is under). Some of these detentions could be avoided. This policy has led to the abandonment of custody in cases of road traffic offences. Road violence, the other major security issue on the island, is being neglected.

Last but not least, emphasising the responsibility of professionals by prioritising protection encourages them to favour safety over other concerns, needs, and expectations of the victim.

"It is impossible to do nothing when faced with a case of domestic violence, even if the victim refuses to file a complaint and is not ready to accept protective measures." (FV policy coordinating prosecutor)

This trend is exacerbated in the judicial process due to the limited consideration given to the victim's well-being and autonomy in the texts defining the measures and procedures. Well-being is generally reduced to the speed of the procedures.

Victims themselves assess the potential or actual effects of judicial measures on their lives, those of their children, or their relatives. This assessment differs from that of justice professionals, particularly concerning the drawbacks caused by protective measures. The victim does not necessarily wish to prioritise their safety. On the contrary, they may wish to maintain their living environment for various reasons (such as the children's school location, lack of financial resources, social circle, etc.).

For example, some victims do not want to be informed of the release of their violent ex-partner from prison because it causes them anxiety and reminds them of a relationship they want to forget. Major victim support associations advocate respecting this desire for the "right to forget" as they witness the suffering endured by these victims during these times. They recommend informing the victim as late as possible. Recent regulations make this practice impossible: the victim must be informed of all releases, including temporary ones.

One might hypothesise a form of "infantilisation" in the treatment of female victims. It seems, though this needs verification, that the treatment of female victims by the prosecution resembles the practices of the juvenile court, which handles minors at risk. It would be necessary to measure to what extent the prosecution's approach has evolved towards considering "women at risk," or whether it remains focused on dealing with the perpetrators.

Conversely, some magistrates (such as JAFs, who are more independent and less under pressure than prosecutors) claim to be attentive to respecting the victim's free will.

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2.4 Germany

Data from Germany show that levels of intimate partner violence remain high, despite the development of a wide range of services and a broad support network for those affected by violence in recent years and decades. The GREVIO report for Germany⁵¹ makes it clear that there are still a number of gaps (particularly in terms of protection for victims) and that access to the support system is difficult, especially for vulnerable groups (see Country Report Germany T1.3).

The following report presents projects that can be seen as important and innovative approaches to improving support for victims of partner violence in different areas.

Methods

The report is based on several steps taken so far in the IMPROVE project. Findings from expert interviews on 'Factors influencing the effectiveness of frontline response and potential solutions' (D 1.3) have been taken into account. For the collection of new solutions to existing barriers and challenges (T4.1 Report Guide (Inventory Table)), a desk research was carried out primarily using the keyword 'Häusliche Gewalt' ('domestic violence'), or 'Partnergewalt' ('partner violence') AND 'Hilfe und Unterstützung' ('support') AND 'neue Ansätze' ('new development' AND/OR 'innovative approaches') on Google Scholar, as well as a search on the websites relevant actors in domestic violence prevention and intervention.

To describe the selected 'solutions', information from the analysed interviews with experts (T1.3), publications such as professional articles, evaluation reports and information from the projects' websites (self-presentations of the projects, annual reports, etc.) were used. The data used for the description are listed in the respective solution.

Concrete selection

The selected projects concern promising developments in various relevant areas such as the help and support network, health care, police and justice, and civil society (neighbourhood and socio-spatial environment). They aim to build trust, improve access to the support system and fill gaps in the intervention chain.

⁵¹ GREVIO (2022). GREVIO's (Baseline) Evaluation Report on legislative and other measures giving effect to the provisions of the Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence (Istanbul Convention). GERMANY. Baseline Evaluation Report. <https://rm.coe.int/report-on-germany-for-publication/1680a86937>

- They include a proactive approach to provide protection and support quickly and directly to those affected (in health care, the police and the justice system).
- They also include a broad and low-threshold approach to encourage victims to make use of available support (Support Hotline, StoP - neighbourhoods without partner violence).
- Strengthening networking and interdisciplinary cooperation between different professional groups plays an important role in all of the projects mentioned.
- Quality assurance and/or available evaluation are further criteria for the selection of the projects presented.

The following projects are analysed in more detail and presented as solutions:

- **The Violence Against Women Support Hotline** offers 24-hour confidential assistance, emphasising barrier-free access and multilingual support.
- **The Round Table Berlin (RTB)** is dedicated to implementing WHO guidelines for responding to intimate partner violence (IPV) and sexual violence in Berlin's healthcare system, extending its efforts to various vulnerable groups and data-driven approaches.
- **The Marburg Model** represents a proactive and promising approach to addressing DV in Germany, emphasising rapid intervention, collaboration among stakeholders, and support for both victims and suspects. While challenges exist, ongoing efforts to refine and expand this model offer hope for more effective responses to DV across the country.
- **The 'StoP - neighbourhoods without partner violence' project** represents a community approach and shows how supportive the neighbourhood can be as a social network for those affected by domestic violence and what significance the project has for people who use violence.

Some of the projects have already been described in an earlier step (T1.3). In the following, they are presented from a broader and different perspective.

Solution 1: The “Violence Against Women Support Hotline”

1.1.4.7 Description

1.1.4.7.1 Background and Aim

The following report is based on publications (evaluation report, newsletter), information on the support Hotline website (www.hilfetelefon.de) and an interview with a member of the board of the nationwide hotline, carried out as part of the EU project IMPROVE.

Background for the nationwide Support Hotline:

One of the main reasons for setting up the Support Hotline (116 016) was the realisation that many women affected by violence do not make use of the support system. Although there is a high level of DV in Germany - every fourth woman has experienced some form of violence in a relationship – only about 25% find their way into the support network (Schröttle et al. 2004), because of fear, shame or lack of trust. For many, the barriers are high (including language barriers) and they don't know their options. Many simply do not know which contact point is the right one for them.

“The women were also asked what they would like (to receive) in terms of advice and support and many said that we need something low-threshold, where we are not immediately visible on site, but where we can turn to at any time, when it suits us, [and] when we have the courage and where we have the situation, where we can turn to. So those were the triggers or the considerations for setting up the helpline in this way.”
(SIGSoz7)

There was previously a successful experience with the “BIG hotline” in Berlin, only on a local level.

Aim:

With its initial counselling and, if necessary, referral to the local support system, the support Hotline was intended to close a gap in the support network (pilot function).

The aim of the counselling is to provide tailored support and empowerment for women affected by violence. The support Hotline is considered an important “entry point” into the help and support system for women affected by violence and will improve access. The provided Support is multilingual, accessible, and barrier-free and includes a wide range of topics related to domestic violence.

The support Hotline is aimed at

- **Women affected by violence:** it offers psychosocial counselling and crisis intervention, works as a guide to local facilities, if women want so.
- **Anyone wishing to help a women affected by violence:** relatives, friends, acquaintances, or neighbours. The helpline offers information for supporting persons.
- **Professionals (health care workers, social worker, psychotherapists, police, youth welfare, etc.):** support include information on all topics relating to DV, intervention planning dealing with overwhelming emotions, talking about experiences and observations or answering questions about local support services.

1.1.4.7.2 Implementation and Practice

The “Violence Against Women Support Hotline” was launched in March 2013. It is set up as an initial advice and referral service on the basis of the Support Hotline Act, which defines the framework conditions and tasks of the Support Hotline. It is the first nationwide counselling service in Germany that can be reached confidentially and free of charge (24/7 on 365 days).

“The hotline was set up with the Istanbul Convention in mind.” (SIGSoz7)

Various public relations measures such as campaigns, online communication (including the website www.hilfetelefon.de), information and advertising materials, sponsoring, press work and activities have succeeded in publicising the offer of the hotline.

The Support Hotline is available 24 hours a day. The call is free of charge and the number does not appear on the telephone bill. Counselling is confidential and anonymous if desired. In addition to telephone advice, chat and email advice is also available free of charge via the website (www.hilfetelefon.de). The service is multilingual. With the help of interpreters, telephone advice is available in 18 foreign languages; chat advice is only given in German.

Barrier-free access to information and advice is guaranteed. The website is barrier-free and contains sign language videos and information in plain language. Counselling for women with hearing impairments in German sign language is available around the clock.

Counselling

Advice and support is available on all forms of violence against women, in particular: Domestic violence (psychological, physical and sexualised violence within relationships), psychological, physical and sexualised violence outside of relationships, stalking, bullying,

digital violence, forced marriage, violence in the name of 'honour', trafficking of women, violence in the context of prostitution, genital mutilation, sexual harassment in the workplace, sexual harassment in public spaces, special contexts of violence, e.g., in care situations.

The counsellors are qualified specialists, social workers or psychologists, who have experience in counselling women affected by violence. They provide information on all forms of violence against women and inform about the possibilities of the nationwide support system for women affected by violence.

Referral and pilot function

The Support Hotline also has a pilot function and provides information on where and how regional help can be obtained.

1.1.4.7.3 Strengths and Weaknesses

Strengths

Low-threshold

The nationwide "Violence against women support Hotline" with anonymous advice by phone, chat or email is particularly low-threshold. The constant availability, high security standards, multilingual advice and barrier-free access are intended to encourage women affected by violence to contact the support Hotline in confidence and this paves the way for them to find professional services locally (<https://www.hilfetelefon.de/>).

Various contact options

The support Hotline offers various contact and information options: by telephone, chat, e-mail, texts on the homepage. It offers various contact and information options: by telephone, chat, e-mail, texts on the homepage. Users are free to decide what they accept.

Highly qualified and secure counselling

Female counsellors provide initial psychosocial counselling and crisis intervention and, if desired, refer to local support facilities, such as a women's counselling centre or a women's shelter nearby. The counselling is always anonymous, confidential complies with strict data protection requirements. Thanks to special programming, visiting the Support Hotline's website is also highly secure.

Support in many languages

The service is multilingual. With the help of interpreters, telephone advice is available in 18 foreign languages; chat advice is only given in German. Barrier-free access to information and advice is guaranteed (plain language, sign language).

Public relation

The broad-based public relations work of the "Violence Against Women Support Hotline" leads to greater awareness and sensitivity to the issue of domestic violence and encourages those affected.

The Support Hotline and its services are visible in public spaces and easy to find on the Internet.

Challenge (Weaknesses)

Limited resources in the local support system

There are numerous cases in which women affected by violence were encouraged to turn to a local support service as a result of (initial) counselling on the "Violence Against Women Support Hotline", but the possibilities for further referral were limited due to inadequate resources in the local support system. There is a high need for better infrastructure of the local support system (BMFSFJ, 2020).

1.1.4.8 Justification

Most widely and most effective employed solution:

"Our task is to offer initial counselling with these characteristics, i.e., no longer-term counselling processes, we offer initial psychosocial counselling, and we have a pilot function, i.e., we refer people to facilities in the support system if required. We work nationwide, i.e., we have a local address database to refer people to suitable addresses. Our actual counselling mandate is, initial psychosocial counselling, crisis intervention and this pilot function." (SIGSoz7)

The Support Hotline is a well-networked component within the support system.

"This is the only way to ensure that the services offered by the facilities work well together in order to make it easier for women affected by violence to find ways out." (SIGSoz7)

The issue of violence against women has become more prominent in the public eye over the last ten years. The campaigns and publications of the support Hotline as well as the

cooperation with the support system and actors from politics and civil society have also contributed to this.

1.1.4.8.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

Legal Framework

The nationwide “Violence Against Women Support Hotline” has a legal basis that was passed in 2012 (“Act on the Establishment and Operation of a Nationwide “Violence against Women Support Hotline” – *Gesetz zur Einrichtung des bundesweiten Hilfetelefons Gewalt gegen Frauen*). The law regulates the establishment and technical supervision, equipment, target group, requirements for assistance, as well as requirements for public relations work and status reports and evaluation.⁵²

The Support Hotline Act is a significant basis and binding guideline on how the service must be organised in order to make it easier for women to find support. Key features are confidentiality and anonymity as well as round-the-clock availability 365 days a year.

Effective organisational structures

The support Hotline has clear organisational structures.

- **The department heads:** Eight department heads work for the Support Hotline. They are responsible for the supervision of the counsellors, conduct technical discussions and lead service group and case discussions. They are also responsible for specific subject areas and represent the helpline at specialist events. Together with the management, they work on the implementation and further development of the counselling concept, on the design and safeguarding of the service and the framework conditions.
- **The administration department:** The administrative staff provide support in ensuring the infrastructure for the Support Hotline. One important task is shifting planning for the advisors. However, the work area also includes fault and error management, which ensures the smooth operation of the Support Hotline, the dispatch of information material or the creation, further development and ongoing administration of the comprehensive knowledge and address database and the preparation of statistical reports.

⁵² For more details see: <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/hilfetelefon/BjNR044800012.html>

Since 2023, the Support Hotline has had a dual leadership team in charge of personnel and technical operations.

Specialist policy monitoring and support from the advisory board

The advisory board: The Support Hotline Act stipulates that an advisory board is to be set up to provide ongoing political support for the support Hotline. The 15-member advisory board includes academics, senior staff from local authorities and federal states as well as experts from the support system for women affected by violence. The members of the advisory board are appointed for a 3-year term of office by the Federal Ministry for Family Affairs, Senior Citizens, Women and Youth.

Well-equipped with resources

The Support Hotline is relatively well funded and staffed compared to the support structures.

Qualified counsellors

More than 100 counsellors ensure that women affected by violence can find a contact person at the Support Hotline around the clock. All of them are qualified specialists, e.g., social education workers, social workers, or psychologists, who have experience in advising women affected by violence. They work in shifts and advise those seeking advice on all forms of violence against women.

“The challenge for the counsellor is to establish good contact with those seeking advice. To actually create a trusting discussion environment and to convey that it is good that they are getting in touch and that they are in the right place for the time being. We call this empowerment. Actually, encouraging them, giving them courage and reassuring them that there are options and that they can tell their story if they want to, and that it is up to them how much of their story they want to tell.” (SIGSoz7)

Professional counselling on experiences of violence requires a high level of expertise. In order to ensure the quality of the counselling, the counsellors regularly take part in supervisions, further training, specialist and service group meetings.

Evaluation and annual status report

The evaluation after five years and an annual status report are defined by law. The Federal Office for Family Affairs and Civil Society Tasks publishes an annual status report on the use

of the Support Hotline and the services provided.⁵³ The Federal Ministry for Family Affairs, Senior Citizens, Women and Youth evaluate the effectiveness of the Support Hotline (Support Hotline Law) in order to make adjustments and respond to new developments (BMFSFJ, 2020).

The evaluation makes it clear that the professional implementation and needs-based further development of the service, in particular the establishment and maintenance of professionalism, is an ongoing task for the "Violence Against Women Support Hotline", including its public relations work. This also applies to the quality assurance of service providers for implementation, such as the interpreter service (BMFSFJ, 2020).

Public relations

An important component is publicising the counselling and assistance services.

- **Campaigns and activities:** The Support Hotline launches campaigns and various activities to encourage the general public to help publicise the Support Hotline. The aim of the campaigns is to make as many people as possible throughout Germany aware of the advice offered by the Support Hotline. The "join-in campaign" is aimed at local authorities, organisations, associations and companies in order to set an example against violence against women and draw attention to the "Violence Against Women Support Hotline" so that more women find their way to advice and support.
- **Information materials:** A wide range of multilingual information materials and publications from the "Violence against women support Hotline" are available to download and order from the homepage, as well as digital media (campaign and radio spots, other videos).

Cooperation

Strong cooperation partners from business, politics and society make a significant contribution to publicising the "Violence Against Women Support Hotline". A list of all federal states, organisations and companies with which the hotline cooperates can be found on the website⁵⁴.

⁵³ For more details see: <https://www.hilfetelefon.de/das-hilfetelefon/zahlen-und-fakten/jahresbericht.html>

⁵⁴ The website is available here:

<https://www.hilfetelefon.de/das-hilfetelefon/kooperationen.html>

1.1.4.8.2 Practical relevance

Low-threshold and accessible

The Support Hotline is available 24 hours a day. The call is free of charge and the number does not appear on the telephone bill. Counselling is confidential and anonymous if desired.

In addition to telephone advice, chat and email advice is also available free of charge via the website.⁵⁵ The service is multilingual. With the help of interpreters, telephone advice is available in 18 foreign languages; chat advice is only given in German.

Barrier-free access to information and advice is guaranteed. The website is barrier-free and contains sign language videos and information in plain language. Counselling for women with hearing impairments in German sign language is available around the clock.

Working method

Psychosocial Counselling

The counsellors provide initial psychosocial counselling and support in acute situations of violence and crisis and respond to the individual situation of the person seeking advice. If the person seeking help is in a situation of immediate danger, the Support Hotline can forward the call to the appropriate emergency services, in particular the police, or notify them itself. However, the Support Hotline does not offer longer-term support in individual cases. This is where the local professional institutions and specialist advice centres come in.

Guide function

The “Violence Against Women Support Hotline” complements the regional support system for women affected by violence, which includes women’s shelters as well as specialist advice and intervention centres.

If required, the advisors can provide addresses and telephone numbers of local advice centres. An extensive database is available for this purpose. Police emergency control centres are also listed nationwide. In individual cases, the counsellors set up a conference call to connect those seeking help directly with a further point of contact.

Confidential and anonymous

Special precautions are taken to ensure anonymity and confidentiality on the Support Hotline. People seeking advice do not have to give their name. Telephone calls are not recorded.

⁵⁵ The website is available here: www.hilfetelefon.de

Personalised data is not documented or stored. The incoming telephone number is not recognisable to the counsellors and the telephone number of the Support Hotline is not shown in the itemised telephone bill.

Even with online counselling, e-mail addresses or names do not have to be provided. Data transfer is encrypted, and no IP addresses are stored.

The counsellors themselves are bound to confidentiality. Anonymity and confidentiality are crucial for many people to find the courage to seek advice and support.

Individual solutions

Violence and the consequences are experienced very differently by those affected. The counsellors work with each woman individually to find ways out of the violence. Based on the personal life situation of the victim and their needs and possibilities, the counsellors support, encourage and empower them to take the next steps to get out of the violent situation.

Reaching different Target Groups

The Support Hotline addresses specific needs of vulnerable victims: The service is multilingual.

“Obstacles are particularly high for women with a migration or refugee background. The content of counselling will also differ, as the first step is to provide information about the support system and the legal situation in Germany, and there is still a lot that is not known. We notice that again and again. And the barrier to contacting us as a low-threshold service is still very high if the language is not spoken.” (SIGSoz7)

The hotline's newsletters regularly raise awareness of the needs of vulnerable women affected by violence, e.g., what needs to be considered when offering help to older women (Newsletter 9/23) or on the topic of diversity (Newsletter 9/23).

Information on special contact points for men affected by violence are also available. According to its legal mandate, the Support Hotline specialises in advising women affected by violence and forwards men seeking advice to the specialist colleagues at the men's helpline "Männerhilfetelefon" (Help hotline for men).⁵⁶

Cooperation - language mediation as specialist support for other services

⁵⁶ The website is available here: <https://www.hilfetelefon.de/aktuelles/auch-maenner-erleben-gewalt.html>

For example, the police consider it a great support that they can call in the counsellors from the support Hotline if they do not speak the language. They help to explain that accommodation in a women's refuge can contribute to the safety of those affected, if criminal law aspects or legal terminology need to be explained or if police measures such as an eviction order with a ban on entering the premises need to be explained to the person perpetrating the violence. Furthermore, following an immediate police intervention, a connection can be established between the victim and the help hotline in order to initiate immediate psychosocial intervention (BMFSFJ, Evaluation report 2020).

1.1.4.8.3 Evidence and Data

In 2023, the Support Hotline celebrated its tenth anniversary. During this time, it has established itself as an indispensable part of the support system for women affected by violence.

The data on the use of the Support Hotline shows a high demand. Since its launch in March 2013, it has been able to show many women a way out of violence: In total, Support Hotline experts have given advice 446,758 times by phone, email or chat over the nine years. 248,116 people affected by violence have used the low-threshold service and received individual advice. The other target groups of the Support Hotline were also reached: more than 70,512 people from the social environment of those affected and around 18,990 professionals used the service. Domestic violence was a particularly frequent cause of the calls. The advisors referred those seeking advice to local facilities 223,754 times, 82 percent of which were counselling centres and women's shelters.⁵⁷

The 2013 annual report shows: As awareness of the service has increased, the number of counselling sessions has risen continuously over the last 11 years. In all areas, they have at least doubled compared to the first year of operation. There were around 25,000 counselling contacts in 2014 and around 59,000 in 2023, with between 75 and 80 per cent of the contacts over the years being people who had been affected by violence themselves. Between 15 and 20 per cent of those seeking advice were support from their social environment. Consistently, 60 per cent of counselling sessions were about domestic violence. A consistent 40 per cent of enquiries were received between 6 p.m. and 8 a.m., when other facilities are generally

⁵⁷ More details available here:

https://www.hilfetelefon.de/fileadmin/content/04_Materialien/1_Materialien_Bestellen/Infografiken/11_Jahre_Hilfetelefon/Hilfetelefon_Gewalt_gegen_Frauen_Infografik_11_Jahre.pdf

unavailable. The figures in the 2023 annual report show counselling contacts increased by 12 per cent compared to the previous year to around 59,000.⁵⁸

All foreign languages offered were utilised.

With a total of 4,455 cases, an interpreter was consulted in 8 per cent of all counselling contacts. Compared to the previous year (4,044 cases), this represents an increase of 10 per cent. Most of the interpreted counselling sessions (16 per cent) were in Arabic. Interpreters were also frequently consulted in Russian, Farsi/Dari and Turkish. In 863 cases, those seeking advice were given advice in a foreign language spoken by a counsellor herself. At 78 per cent, the majority of foreign language consultations were in English. Farsi followed at a considerable distance, Turkish and Russian (BMFSFJ & BAFzA, 2023).

In the target group of professionals, the police in particular reported almost a quarter of the counselling sessions (490). This was followed by 347 contacts from the healthcare sector and 324 contacts from other counselling institutions. In addition, 223 people came forward from women's support centres. Professionals from schools and daycare centres reported 239 contacts in 11 per cent of cases. (BMFSFJ & BAFzA, 2023)

Public relation

In addition to counselling, public relations work is an important task of the "Violence Against Women Support Hotline. Information and advertising measures are used to make women aware of the free and confidential counselling service.

To mark the International Day against Violence against Women on 25 November, regular "join-in campaigns" are held on social media (under the patronage of the Federal Minister for Women). In 2023, the campaign attracted a lot of attention under the hashtag #BreakingSilence. The social media filter published by the Support Hotline (a free tool for creating selfies, group photos and stories) recorded 9,773 views alone. Well over 500 posts about the day of action were posted on Instagram, Facebook and the platform X (formerly Twitter).

In the partner network, the International Day against Violence against Women was used for various campaigns (e.g. sandwich bags with references to the "Violence Against Women Support Hotline") as well as information stands, events and other high-profile campaigns and

⁵⁸ More details available here: <https://www.hilfetelefon.de/das-hilfetelefon/zahlen-und-fakten/jahresbericht.html>

posters in towns and municipalities. Numerous local authorities, organisations, associations and companies used the Support Hotline's print templates for posters, banners and hoisting flags as part of the campaign day. They can be downloaded free of charge in various formats from the Support Hotline website (BMFSFJ & BAFzA, 2023).

The evaluation report on the support Hotline (2013-2018) published in 2020 confirms

- that the “Violence against women support Hotline, with its low-threshold access and its broad professional profile makes it an important “entry point” into the help and support system for women affected by violence.
- That the “Violence against women support Hotline” is a key addition to the existing help and support system (easier access to the help system).

The evaluation report shows the effectiveness of the "Violence against Women support Hotline, it fulfils the tasks assigned to it under the Support Hotline Act, target groups are reached, and the number of users is rising continuously (BMFSFJ, 2020).

EU-wide hotline number

Since June 2023, the helpline has been available under the number 116 016. The introduction of the Europe-wide standardised short telephone number goes back to an initiative by the German EU Council Presidency in 2020. To date, 15 member states have committed to setting up national helplines for support in cases of violence against women under this number (BMFSFJ & BAFzA, 2023).

1.1.4.8.4 Context of the Solution

Important addition to the help and support system

The Support Hotline is an important addition to the nationwide help and support system and plays a major role in the implementation of the “Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence”.

Support Hotline fulfils pilot function

The "Violence Against Women Support Hotline" is in contact with organisations in the local help and support system in a variety of ways. Overall, the analysis shows a high degree of its integration into the structures of the help and support system for violence against women.

Synergies for the help and support system

According to experts from specialised protection and counselling centres, municipal women and equal opportunities officers as well as experts, the "Violence Against Women Support Hotline" makes an important social contribution to raising awareness of the issue of violence against women (BMFSFJ, 2020).

1.1.4.8.5 Unintended Consequences and Risks

The evaluation report shows that bottlenecks in the local support system limit the potential impact of the "Violence Against Women Support Hotline:

The supply bottlenecks in the local help system and the low-threshold access to the "Violence against women" helpline mean that people seeking advice turn to the helpline with problems that are not covered by the legal mandate.

The "Violence Against Women Support Hotline" cannot close the gaps in care. On the contrary, it is dependent on the local support system being well equipped in order to fulfil its legal mandate to provide referrals. Full realisation of the potential impact requires a needs-based expansion of the local help system (BMFSFJ, Evaluation report 2020).

Competition for funding:

Individual professionals (online survey) reported that municipal funders (e.g. the district) referred to the existing nationwide "Violence against women" helpline when applying for further funding and cited this as a reason for not having to expand the local municipal service (BMFSFJ, Evaluation report 2020).

Solution 2: “Round Table Berlin (RTB) – health care for domestic and sexual violence”

The “RTB – health care for domestic and sexual violence” is a committee of the Berlin Senate Department for Health and Long-Term Care and is chaired by the Berlin Senator for Health. The project is designed, developed, and coordinated by S.I.G.N.A.L. e. V. (head office).

The following report is based on publications by the RTB and S.I.G.N.A.L. e. V. It is supplemented by six recent interviews with RTB members, carried out as part of the EU project IMPROVE.

Code	Profession, discipline	representing
SIGMed1_ZNA	Leader Emergency Room, Surgeon, Physician for clinical emergency and acute medicine, leader of the violence protection team in a hospital,	Association of German Surgeons, Berlin Surgical Society, Working Group Emergency Physician Berlin, German Society for Interdisciplinary Emergency and Acute Medicine (DGINA e.V.)
SIGMed2_HÄ	General practitioner and family doctor/outpatient care They have patients from Berlin but also from rural areas in Brandenburg	Family Physicians Association Berlin-Brandenburg, member of Forum General Practitioner and Medical Association (Ärzttekammer), founder of the working group domestic violence in the Medical Association, member of Round Table Berlin
SIGMed3_Gyn	Gynaecologist	Professional association of gynaecologists (Berufsverband der Frauenärzte), representing the association at (round table Berlin; RTB)
SIGMed4_GF_RT B	Political scientist and health scientist	Coordinator in the head office (organised by SIGNAL e.V.) of the Round Table Berlin under the direction of the Minister for Health (Referentin der Geschäftsstelle des RTB unter der Federführung der Senatorin für Gesundheit Berlin) Member of the advisory board of the nationwide Helpline
SIGMed5_MW	Nurse and midwife	Hospital
SIGMed6_ÖGD	Gynaecologist	Public Health Service (ÖGD), Leader of the Centre for Sexual Health and Family Planning Member of Round Table Berlin and of the Public Health Network

1.1.4.9 Description

1.1.4.9.1 Background and Aim

Opportunities for intervention in healthcare against domestic and sexualised violence have received increasing attention in Germany since the beginning of 2000.

S.I.G.N.A.L. e. V. is a non-profit organisation (provider of three projects financed by the Berlin Senate Department for Health and Long-Term Care) with many years of experiences in implementing measures in healthcare facilities to support patients affected by violence. The first scientifically supported implementation of the SIGNAL intervention program in the emergency department of the Benjamin Franklin University Hospital (now Charité Campus Benjamin Franklin) resulted in the following experiences: In the central emergency department patient survey, 36.6% reported having experienced domestic violence. Those affected showed a high level of acceptance for being asked about domestic violence. Staff found the intervention necessary and the program positive. Intervention is feasible in a central emergency department, but requires a group (on-site group) that creates and maintains the structures for intervention (e.g. provides templates for documentation and telephone numbers for referral) and ensures that further training is offered, that trained professionals are always on duty and that internal consultation is possible with the psychologist or social services. However, despite the important project results, the intervention was hardly taken up in other clinics and practices in Berlin. S.I.G.N.A.L. e. V. realised that the healthcare system needs to be addressed in a targeted, concrete and customised manner. Healthcare professionals, their organisations, medical chambers etc. and health policy must be involved and participate.

Aims:

The Round Table Berlin - Healthcare for Domestic and Sexualised Violence (RTB) is committed to the **implementation of the evidence-based WHO guidelines** 'Dealing with violence in couple relationships and sexual violence against women' and their structural anchoring in hospitals, doctors' surgeries and public health services. The main aims are to improve healthcare and support for those affected by domestic and sexualised violence, to strengthen the confidence of healthcare professionals in dealing with those affected and to promote and expand cross-sectoral, interdisciplinary cooperation. This includes:

First-line support: Asking about intimate partner violence, information and further help (referrals), increasing safety (also for children) and follow-up-care (sexual violence). Documentation and securing evidence should also be implemented.

RTB members develop **specific guidelines** (for different target groups) and **implementation measures** for different sectors of health care, settings and professions (victim protection groups, care processes, cross-sector referral pathways). They also strengthen cooperation with other relevant agencies such as police, child protection and Youth Welfare Office, counselling centres (pro-active approach) and shelters (NGOs).

Training should be offered and integrated into the curricula of healthcare professions and further training programmes (WHO, 2013: recommendations 30-33).

Research and data collection: In order to review the implementation of the guidelines and the impact of measures and to further develop health care services, efforts should be made to improve data collection and research. The needs of all affected target groups/patients requiring care after experiencing DV or sexual violence must be taken into account, for example, as part of the monitoring process.

Public relations work is needed to raise awareness of possible health consequences of DV and sexual violence and of the importance of healthcare for intervention.

1.1.4.9.2 Implementation and Practice

The first step was the implementation of the Round Table Berlin (RTB). The head office at S.I.G.N.A.L. e. V. (financed by the Berlin Senate Department for Health and Long-Term Care since 2018) was crucial for the establishment of the RTB and the acquisition of members. SIGNAL e. V. advises the Berlin Senate Department of Health and Long-Term Care and supports the members of the RTB in the planning and implementation of their activities. This ranges from the development of procedures, measures, and materials, the dissemination of results and public relations work. All meetings of the RTB are organised by the head office in consultation with the Berlin Senate Department for Health and Long-Term Care.

Round Table Berlin (Plenary): The Round Table Berlin is a committee of the Berlin Senate Department for Health and Long-Term Care. It is chaired by the Berlin Senator for Health and Long-Term Care. The RTB is a voluntary association of organisations. The members are not paid for their participation. The 29 members represent medical associations, professional associations for GPs, gynaecologists, emergency and acute physicians, physiotherapists,

chambers (doctors, dentists, pharmacists, psychotherapists), hospital associations, fire brigades, midwives' associations, the public health service, health insurance companies, the Berlin Senate Departments for Health and Care, for Education and for Youth and Family, the specialist department for prevention and health promotion, the network of women's refuges and counselling centres, child protection, the police, equal opportunities officers, etc. There is a cooperation agreement, an annual target and action plan with an evaluation.

Graphic 4: RTB structure

The Round Table Plenary meets twice a year to discuss the current situation, decide on measures to implement the WHO guidelines and review their realisation, formulate work assignments and adopt plans. They agreed on a step-by-step, sector-specific, and practical approach for the implementation of the WHO guidelines. Where possible, the Round Table makes decisions by consensus. Round Table meetings are not open to the public; experts may be invited.

The Round Table can convene **specialised working groups** to deal with issues and problems. They identify the need for action, develop measures and work on their implementation (planning of measures). Individual aspects can also be addressed in greater depth in interdisciplinary specialist or **expert discussions**.

All results are to be published and disseminated so that they can be used by professionals and institutions nationwide. The members of the Round Table use their own networks, professional societies and associations nationwide for this purpose (the snowball-principle).

The implementation of the RTB and the creation of the decision-making and working structures have been completed. The RTB began its work in 2019.⁵⁹

The **implementation of measures in healthcare facilities** has begun in 2020. Victim protection groups and the proactive approach in cooperation with counselling centres are being tested and evaluated in rescue centres. The SIGNAL Coordination and Intervention Centre KIS supports the implementation processes and offers training and counselling for the organisations.

Recommendations for action and standard descriptions for various healthcare areas are available: The implementation of measures in healthcare facilities has begun. The introduction of victim protection groups and the proactive approach in cooperation with counselling centres is being tested in rescue centres. Recommendations for action and standard descriptions for various healthcare areas are available for the following sectors:

Pharmacies, obstetrics, gynaecologists and midwives, general practitioners, pregnancy counselling and central emergency departments. There are also recommendations for the care of patients with children, for medical assistants and for documentation.

Newsletters, the RTB homepage, congresses and meetings, press and specialist publications are used for publication.

1.1.4.9.3 Strengths and Weaknesses

Strengths:

- All the important stakeholder of the health sector and health policy in Berlin are involved and develop measures themselves for the members of their own professional groups (e.g. doctors for doctors). Stakeholders position themselves publicly on the topic of DV.
- The objectives and implementation of the WHO guidelines help to fulfil legal requirements.

⁵⁹ For more details, see: <https://rtb-gesundheit.de/>

- Legal regulations and payment of the documentation promote the anchoring of intervention measures.
- The WHO guidelines that are to be implemented are evidence-based and accepted.
- The head office of RTB coordinates and does all the background work. This is a relief for the members.
- In cooperation with the RTB, the Coordination and Intervention Centre KIS supports hospitals free of charge, to create structures and train staff.
- Responsibility for the development of intervention measures is clarified through victim protection groups.
- Materials, needs-oriented guidelines and the proactive approach facilitate the work and relieve the burden on professionals. The step-by-step working principle is adapted to the capacities of the members and healthcare facilities.
- Analyses and reports make successes visible.
- All patients are reached in healthcare, including the vulnerable ones. There is great potential for the prevention of further violence, as healthcare facilities are interfaces between those affected and other support services (counselling, protection).

Weaknesses:

- Healthcare facilities are commercial enterprises. The lack of payment for intervention (apart from court-proof documentation) makes measures dependent on the commitment of individual professionals, legal obligations and health policy.
- It is unclear how long the RTB will be funded. The scope depends on funding.
- A lack of staff in healthcare facilities can increase work pressure and a lack of time. Perhaps intervention measures will then be forgotten.

“Yes, the biggest challenge is, of course, that we actually implement it, right? That is of course a challenge”. (SIGMed1_ZNA)

1.1.4.10 Justification

A project in the healthcare sector was selected for the following reasons: Many studies show that domestic violence has enormous health consequences. The first priority when seeking help is to contact healthcare facilities. All people are reached by the healthcare system. This is a great opportunity for detecting experiences of violence. Healthcare facilities are regarded as low-threshold care centres. Healthcare professionals are often the first or only

professionals to see injuries caused by DV (Hellbernd et al 2013 p 34). They are in a unique position to offer survivors support and to address their health and psychosocial needs. Healthcare providers are trusted, and the duty of confidentiality enables discussions in a confidential, protected environment.

The healthcare system in Germany is organised on a decentralised basis (each institution is an independent company) and therefore poses a particular challenge for the implementation of measures against DV. A Top-Down-Solution for all healthcare facilities is not possible.

The RTB is the first systematic approach and works on all key points with the healthcare organisations and stakeholders themselves: The measures are aimed both at patients and internally at employees/management (counselling on the implementation of evidence-based WHO guidelines and court-proof documentation, training and acquisition of confidence to act and implementation of target group-specific measures), but also at the general public. This addresses a major challenge that has remained unresolved until now.

1.1.4.10.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

Many different factors were important for the successful implementation of the RTB and the intervention measures in healthcare facilities:

Political support: The Berlin government's coalition agreement (2016-2021) included a commitment to establish the RTB. This was an important step towards funding a **coordination and head office at S.I.G.N.A.L. e. V.** in order to build up RTB and develop a concept.

Legal requirements/laws and evidence-based guidelines: They motivated professionals to participate and implement measures in their health care facilities. There is a legal mandate to intervene.

“And the motivation, I think, for the hospital to implement measures is, of course, the responsibility we have as an emergency hospital, but also the requirements that the legislator places on us as an emergency hospital. The implementation of measures is legally required and mandatory.” (SIGMed1_ZNA)

The important legal principles include

- The publication of the evidence-based WHO guidelines and the WHO “Clinical handbook” in 2013 and the “Council of Europe Convention on preventing and

combating violence against women and domestic violence – Istanbul Convention” (2011, ratified in Germany in 2018) were crucial for the establishment of the RTB. The Istanbul Convention provides an excellent framework for the implementation of the guidelines of WHO: Training, documentation, trauma treatment, protection and cooperation.

- In Germany the Quality Management Directive (QM-Richtlinie) of the Joint Federal Committee 2020 (G-BA, Gemeinsamer Bundesausschuss) requires every medical surgery and clinic to have intervention and prevention measures in place. The instruments mentioned are staff training, presentation of information materials, action plan, care pathways.
- Victims of DV are named as a target group in the Public Health Service Act (Gesundheitsdienst-Gesetz Berlin).
- The Hospital Plan Berlin 2016 (Krankenhausplan) stipulates that hospitals providing emergency care services need to develop concepts for adequate care of adults and children in cases of domestic and/or sexualised violence. The plan explicitly refers and points to the WHO guidelines and to S.I.G.N.A.L. e. V.’s recommendations for documentation of injuries.
- With the legal regulation on the financing of court-proof documentation in cases of domestic violence and confidential forensic evidence, hospitals have the opportunity to be paid for services for the first time.

Stakeholder and Cooperation partners

The RTB **concept** involves all stakeholders and cooperation partners. It works systematically on the implementation of recognised and evidence-based guidelines and data-based measures. Strategic considerations for the establishment of the RTB:

- A high-level round table, chaired by politicians, make clear that this is a health policy concern.
- Health policy stakeholders develop products themselves for the members of their own professional groups (e.g. doctors for doctors). Committed professionals in management positions are role models for their own professional groups. Stakeholders position themselves publicly on the topic.

“It is important to involve healthcare institutions and associations, health care providers, etc. in the development of professional measures against domestic

violence. Results are more likely to be accepted if the various disciplines and organisations are involved in their development. They must be encouraged and enabled to do their public relations work, to find multipliers, to use their professional organisational structures, workshops and congresses, to inform, to create networks and to anchor measures.” (SIGMed4_GF-RTB)

Considering the needs of healthcare professionals

Healthcare professionals and their needs are at the centre of the work. The aim is to create the conditions for structurally anchored intervention. It should be possible to integrate the intervention measures in healthcare facilities into the existing treatment processes. If there are further needs on the part of the patients, they can be referred on. The questions are what helps patients, how can the WHO- guidelines be concretized and what do professionals need to be able to intervene?

“The guideline is increasingly finding its way into surgeries and clinics. The question is what should be done. This is the task of the Round Table to find answers.” (SIGMed4_GF_RTB)

The **cooperation agreement** between the RTB and its members creates a binding relationship. They agreed on a **step-by-step-principle**, sector-specific, results-orientated and practical approach for the implementation of the WHO guidelines. This respects the situation of professionals and healthcare facilities:

- Care areas and settings differ in terms of structural conditions, care mandate and scope for action and therefore require an appropriate approach in each case.
- The sensitisation of healthcare professionals varies.
- None of the member organisations have additional resources available.
- In some cases, structural changes will be required within healthcare facilities, which can only be achieved gradually and over a longer period of time.

Action plan

The RTB's **systematic approach** means an annual plan of objectives, measures and actions. Implementation is regularly reviewed. The action plan will be continued and updated. The head office prepares a report on the achievement of objectives. This makes success visible. The objectives and plans were reviewed by a survey that analysed the needs of professionals in emergency rooms (N=689) (Brzank 2022).

It motivates members when they know that they are on the right track. The development of measures, guidelines and materials follows the **PDCA-Cycle** (Plan-Do-Check-Act).

Active cooperation of all participants

Activating members of the RTB is crucial to achieving results.

“The members of the Round Table Berlin have developed a plan of action with the aim of concretising the guidelines for various healthcare disciplines, professions, and vulnerable victims. It is important to work in a results-orientated way and to anchor intervention measures. One action follows the next or one problem that should be solved follows the next. This keeps the RTB alive and brings individual successes.”
(SIGMed4_GF-RTB)

Working groups and interdisciplinary expert discussions are instruments to address aspects in greater depth. Individual members do not have to deal intensively with all the questions and challenges. For example:

- Working group “Develop practice-orientated care processes and recommendations for various medical disciplines and target groups”
- Working group “Qualification of healthcare professionals”
- Working group “Data collection and research”

“Working groups regularly remind us of the topic.” (SIGMed3_Gyn)

Annual events, social media and the permanent campaign “Stop violence. Strengthen health.” also make success visible. The members of RTB are involved with presentations, social media statements (video clips or quotes), etc. The RTB can only be successful if its members are active. In other words, they must speak at conferences, distribute, and disseminate SOPs and information, etc., in order to remove taboos from the topic.

Intervention measures in healthcare facilities

The key points for implementing the WHO guidelines have been described and agreed by the members. Guideline, specific recommendations, standards and training avoid uncertainty in dealing with victims/survivors of DV.

The violence protection team plays an important role.

“A colleague was a member of a working group of SIGNAL e. V. and brought the concept “Violence Protection Team”. We decided: “Okay, good concept, violence

protection team. We should also implement it." We then approached the clinic management, and they also supported us. That is how we got started."
(SIGMed1_ZNA)

The establishment of a violence protection team to be "ground-breaking for the implementation of measures" against domestic and sexualised violence (SIGMed1_ZNA). The violence protection team ensures that affected patients are recognized and adequately addressed, that documentation of injuries and findings that can be used in court is offered, that the protection of the patient and (co-) affected children is discussed, that information material is handed out on request and that referrals to other support systems (counselling centres or shelters) are made if necessary. The work of the violence protection team is crucial for organising and maintaining intervention measures. They act as mediators for their areas and pass on information. Their tasks are to create infrastructure for the intervention (information material, digital documentation templates, etc.), to take care of the need for further training, and to raise awareness of DV in the hospital.

In cooperation with RTB the S.I.G.N.A.L. Coordination and Intervention-Centre KIS supports the clinic management through cooperation to set up, implement and further develop a violence protection team. It trains the members of the team free of charge on site and advises on questions. S.I.G.N.A.L. - KIS also provides materials for patients and professionals, runs an expert group to share good practice and challenges and supports the team in establishing contact with other support facilities on the topic.

"Well, it's good to have someone there who isn't involved in the hospital operations business, but rather focuses on a timeline and that you stick to it. The external support was of course the training of the members of the violence protection team. We had a one-day in-house training course. And that was great, of course. It was also good for team building to get together on a day like that and for everyone to be on the same page. And of course we still receive regular information from S.I.G.N.A.L."
(SIGMed1_ZNA)

It is considered helpful to have a contact person from S.I.G.N.A.L.- KIS to develop solutions for individual questions and problems.

Measures must be easy and orientated towards the needs of professionals. The benefits must be recognisable (win-situation). It relieves the burden on professionals in

healthcare facilities if new measures can be integrated into the existing structure. Specific recommendations for each professional group, discipline and type of healthcare institution are needed to improve first-line support because the organisations have different structures, tasks and working processes. Acceptance is high if there is a direct benefit and adaptations are not necessary.

“It is good to know what I can do and which help can be recommended and where.”

(SIGMed3_Gyn)

The working group "Develop practice-orientated care processes and recommendations for various medical disciplines and target groups" of the RTB developed several guidelines. The specific recommendations are now available for the rescue service of the fire brigade, obstetrics, midwives and gynaecologists, pregnancy counselling, emergency centres of hospitals, the care of survivors of DV with child(ren) and pharmacists. The recommendations are regularly reviewed, updated, published, and disseminated.

A benefit is also seen in the improvement of interdisciplinary cooperation and the **proactive approach**. It offers the possibility of referring patients to counselling centres that offer further help. This also makes it possible to end the intervention process in a healthcare facility. This creates clarity regarding responsibility.

“It is a measure that does not take much time but takes the pressure off.”

(SIGMed1_ZNA)

The S.I.G.N.A.L.-Coordination and Intervention-Project KIS offers trainings for health care providers. The interviewees considered trainings as very helpful. (SIGMed1_ZNA, SIGMed2_HÄ and SIGMed5_mw).

“And since we have had this, we are much more confident about asking this question.

We feel empowered to ask. We get expertise through training.” (SIGMed5_mw)

1.1.4.10.2 Practical relevance

Practical relevance of implementation strategies

Professionals often recognize the need for intervention measures, but working conditions, lack of time and uncertainty in dealing with victims of domestic or sexual violence mean that evidence-based measures are not applied. This ignores the great potential for prevention. Intervention measures improve ultimately the situation of patients.

The RTB's strategy is to respond precisely to the needs of professionals and their working conditions. Guidelines, materials, documentation templates and measures/processes are developed specifically for different professions and disciplines. The violence protection group is an important tool and contributes to offering patients reliable round-the-clock care. This is achieved by the team introducing these recommendations into their own everyday practice, thereby strengthening the knowledge and skills of employees. The violence protection team is an interdisciplinary and interdepartmental resource within the hospital that clarifies processes, identifies training needs, establishes collaborations and develops the intervention process.

In cooperation with the RTB, the SIGNAL-KIS coordination office offers free advice and information on the implementation of measures and further training in healthcare facilities in order to strengthen confidence in action. As a result, there is an increasing number of emergency rooms that are implementing and anchoring intervention measures.

Practical relevance of intervention measures

Healthcare is the top priority for those affected as a support system. This is why it is so important to adequately identify and intervene in cases of violence. Healthcare plays a major role in secondary prevention and addresses those affected directly. Professionals are often the first and only people to see injuries after domestic or sexual violence. Their reactions are important for the further utilisation and acceptance of help.

In a healthcare facility, patients already receive important messages against domestic and sexual violence and basic information about possible help through posters or emergency cards with telephone numbers.

First aid, documentation and mediation are crucial intervention measures to encourage patients to find solutions, protection and needs-oriented help and to collect evidence.

One advantage of healthcare is that it tends to reach all societal groups. Interventions must therefore take needs of specific vulnerable groups into account.

In its recommendations, the WHO refers to the care of women affected by domestic and sexualized violence and their children. The focus here is on women as, according to international and national studies, they are most frequently affected by these forms of violence. However, based on existing findings and practical experience, the RTB has decided to also consider the specific needs of affected men when implementing the guidelines.

Special attention should also be paid to the situation and perspectives of people with disabilities, people with migration/refugee experience and people with children/young people. In order to clarify whether the WHO recommendations are suitable for the care of the above-mentioned target groups and whether they need to be supplemented, the RTB conducted four expert interviews.⁶⁰

A healthcare facility is an important interface between patients and other support systems (police, counselling centres, protection facilities, youth welfare office). The proactive approach is one of the most important tools for healthcare professionals to refer victims.

“Well, I think that is half of the women who were interviewed in a hospital said that they had not at least visited a counselling centre at that time. And that means that the women can be reached earlier. This approach is also preventive.”
(SIGMed4_GF_RTB)

After a successful test phase and evaluation, the measure has been expanded since July 2022. All of the five Berlin specialised advice/counselling centres have been funded for the pro-active approach in cooperation with hospitals. The number of faxes is now increasing. There are regular exchange and evaluation meetings (emergency centres and counselling services), now coordinated by S.I.G.N.A.L-Coordination and Intervention-Project KIS to expand, anchor and improve the proactive approach.

1.1.4.10.3 Evidence and Data

The prevalence of domestic violence in healthcare facilities:

As part of the scientific monitoring of the S.I.G.N.A.L. intervention project, a prevalence study was carried out to collect data on the medical care requirements and care needs of affected women. A total of 806 women were interviewed in the emergency room of an university hospital in Berlin. 36.6% of women reported physical, sexual or emotional violence after the age of 16 by their partner, former partner or family members. The 12-month prevalence was 4.6%. 56.7% of women who had experienced domestic violence reported health consequences (N=291) (Hellbernd, Brzank, Wieners, Maschwesky-Schneider, 2003).

The importance of healthcare providers:

Healthcare professionals have a special role to play in preventing and intervening in violence against women and their children. Doctors and nurses are often the first and often the only

⁶⁰ For more details, see: <https://rtb-gesundheit.de/unterlagen>

outsiders to see the physical consequences of domestic violence. They therefore have an important role to play in recognizing injuries and complaints caused by violence and to speak to the patient at an early stage about the experienced violence, to offer help and to contribute to reducing the consequences of violence (Hellbernd, Brzank, Wieners, Maschwesky-Schneider, 2003).

Healthcare facilities are the first place to look for help (Schröttle, 2004; FRA, 2014).

Acceptance of the question about experiences of violence:

For “just under seven out of ten women, doctors would be the people to contact if they had experienced violence, but only eight out of 100 have ever been asked about this by doctors and four out of ten women affected by violence would have wished for it. Two-fifths of all women would only report violence experiences if asked directly.” When asked about the characteristics of a potential interviewer, the majority of respondents said ‘understanding’.” Hellbernd, Brzank, Wieners, Maschwesky-Schneider, 2003). 87% of women found routine screening acceptable (FRA, 2014).

Recommendation for implementing intervention measures:

From 2000-2003, the implementation of the SIGNAL - intervention project was tested and scientifically monitored at a university hospital in Berlin. This resulted in a handbook containing the following recommendations for the implementation strategy: Establish a multidisciplinary project group within the hospital, develop intervention program for own facility and quality standards, offer mandatory and ongoing target group-specific training for employees, provide materials for staff and women affected by violence, establish close networking with further counselling centres, ensure a continuous implementation process, project development and evaluation (Hellbernd, Brzank, Wieners, Maschwesky-Schneider, 2003).

WHO describes the minimum requirements for a health sector response to violence against women (WHO 2013, p. 39): Management support, working protocols and procedures related to identification, referral pathways, interdisciplinary cooperation, monitoring and evaluation and support for the carers.

„These guidelines will need to be adapted to specific local and/or national circumstances, taking into account the availability of resources, as well as national policies and procedures.“ (WHO 2013)

A systematic approach is recommended for clinics and practices for the sustainable implementation of an intervention programme. This includes guidelines, process descriptions, regulation of responsibilities, qualifications and networks for the referral of victims. The central role of healthcare in the intervention and prevention of domestic and sexualised violence is not yet sufficiently well known. Targeted specialised public relations work is therefore required (Winterholler & Sautter, 2024).

Intervention: Barriers and needs of healthcare professionals:

Together with Prof. Dr. Petra J. Brzank, Nordhausen University of Applied Sciences, the Round Table Berlin conducted a survey among employees of the Berlin healthcare system on the status and needs in the care of patients after domestic violence. The results and feedback from the survey, in which 659 healthcare professionals took part, are incorporated into the work of the RTB (Brzank, 2022).

71% had contact with victims of partner violence. 96% of respondents feel ready for support. The most frequently cited barriers to a willingness to provide support were: Uncertainty in dealing with those affected (46%), lack of time (41%) and a lack of internal guidelines (40%).

The following were most frequently mentioned as helpful for support: current overview or database of support centres in Berlin (63 %), information material for victims (multilingual) (61%), procedure, standardized approach, case vignettes (56%), cooperation with a counselling centre for victims of domestic violence (53%) and information about services for victims with children (52%). 39% of respondents expressed a specific desire for further training. Almost all respondents (93%) also stated that they felt the support provided was regarded as helpful.

When asked about their confidence in taking action, respondents were more confident in talking to victims about their need for support (52%) and in actively asking about domestic violence (47%). The respondents felt less confident when documenting injuries using a form (30%) and when clarifying an acute risk (32%) or when clarifying the need for support of children (32%).

“The most frequently cited responses provide the RTB with a clear mandate for action, such as the desired database, guidelines for action, more information on various areas, training and also stronger networking with counselling centres.” (Brzank, 2022)

Dissemination of intervention measures in emergency rooms:

The aim of the survey of emergency rooms in Berlin clinics was to map how care is provided to people after violence in intimate relationships and/or sexualized violence and to what extent the implementation of the WHO guidelines and the development of development of concepts provided for in the Berlin Hospital Plan 2016. 28 of 39 Berlin emergency rooms were surveyed (Rasch, Plamp, Tezcan-Güntekin, 2020).

With regard to the care situation in individual emergency rooms, a lack of personnel resources (71%; n = 28) in particular was cited as an obstacle to the care of patients following intimate partner violence and sexualized violence. These include time, space and personnel resources, a lack of training and further education measures, as well as the absence of a "procedural instruction" (Ibid). One third of the clinics have clearly defined responsibilities when domestic violence is detected. (page 56). 11 (39 %; n = 28) emergency rooms did not inform about the care services for patients affected by violence (Rasch, Plamp, Tezcan-Güntekin, 2020).

Three quarters (75 %; n = 28) of emergency departments are prepared to ask female patients with certain symptoms about DV as a possible cause. Men as victims of DV are often not taken into consideration. No emergency room in Berlin had staff that is trained in dealing with LGBTIQ* patients (Rasch, Plamp, Tezcan-Güntekin, 2020).

25% of the responding emergency departments state that they regularly carry out detailed, court-proof documentation (Rasch, Plamp, Tezcan-Güntekin, 2020).

Specifically, it can be seen that decisions about care processes are transferred to the healthcare staff and thus depend on individual knowledge, individual skills and assessments. (Rasch, Plamp, Tezcan-Güntekin, 2020)

Testing the proactive approach:

Between September 2016 and September 2023 there were 126 faxes from emergency centres to counselling services. More than every second woman wanted to receive a follow-up phone call from a counselling service. 49 women could be reached, and 33 women received advice. 63% of these women would not have sought help on their own initiative according to their own or the counsellors' assessment.

“Well, I think that is half of the women who were interviewed in a hospital said that they had not at least visited a counselling centre at that time. And that means that the

women can be reached earlier. This approach is also preventive.”

(SIGMed4_GF_RTB)

After a successful test phase and evaluation, the measure has been expanded since July 2022. All of the five Berlin specialised advice/counselling centres have been funded for the pro-active approach in cooperation with hospitals. The number of faxes is now increasing. There are regular exchange and evaluation meetings (emergency centres and counselling services), now coordinated by S.I.G.N.A.L-Coordination and Intervention-Project KIS to expand, anchor and improve the proactive approach.

1.1.4.10.4 Context of the Solution

The WHO guidelines as well as parts of the Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence - Istanbul Convention are implemented and the requirements of the Quality Management Directive are met.

All objectives and strategies were agreed and published.⁶¹ All key stakeholders and healthcare policy and administration have been involved, and the needs of healthcare professionals and healthcare facilities have been surveyed and incorporated. Professional and facility-specific modifications are possible.

⁶¹ For more details, see: <https://rtb-gesundheit.de/unterlagen>

Solution 3: “Marburg Model”

This report presents the Marburg Model as a solution for law enforcement. Under the title “Marburg without partner violence – recognizing, preventing and ending violence in relationships in our city” this project started its two-year period in October 2019.

The Marburg Model represents a proactive and promising approach to addressing DV in Germany, emphasising rapid intervention, collaboration among stakeholders, and support for both victims and suspects. While challenges exist, ongoing efforts to refine and expand this model offer hope for more effective responses to DV across the country.

The following report is based on publications and one interview with a member of the Hessian Ministry of Justice (PJ5).

1.1.4.11 Description

1.1.4.11.1 Background and Aim

Background

Reservations and scepticism towards the police often result in DV incidents going unreported by victims, leading to a low rate of formal reports to the police and the subsequent involvement of the legal system. This reluctance stems from a deep-seated distrust in law enforcement and the belief that seeking their help would be futile. Negative past experiences, where victims felt wronged or misunderstood by the police, contribute to this hesitancy. The fear of potential retribution or further harm at the hands of the authorities also plays a role, creating a prevailing sentiment among victims that avoiding any involvement with the police is the safest course of action. As noted in the T1.3 interim report on training for legal professionals, limited resources at the police contribute to difficulties in enforcing protection orders, potentially leaving victims at risk. Also, court processes contribute to stress and secondary victimisation, highlighting the need for improved interviewing procedures and increased support from law enforcement. Gender-based stereotypes complicate matters further with e.g., men refraining from reporting, and blaming victims, especially in cases of sexual violence. However, a lot of information, including on domestic violence, is not systematically included in criminal proceedings.

Police and prosecutors often experience in cases of DV that the victim withdraws the criminal complaint filed shortly after the incident. Since, in many cases, there are no other intervention options without a criminal complaint, and the accused do not face immediate consequences,

experience shows that this can lead to further cases of DV. The Marburg Model aims to prevent this.

In implementing coordinated intervention in cases of domestic violence, it has not yet been possible to involve law enforcement to the same extent as the police. Domestic violence is rarely sanctioned by the public prosecutor's office. There is a significant correlation between the injured party's decision to co-operate in criminal proceedings and the outcome of the proceedings. (BMFSFJ, 2010)

Aim:

The main focus of the Marburg Model in cases of DV is the acceleration of proceedings through rapid and intensive networking of all actors and support systems involved in domestic violence. The police, public prosecutor's office and court are in close communication with each other, as well as with independent organisations conducting offender intervention programs and counselling centres for victims and witnesses of crimes. The role of court assistance, which becomes active within five days of the incident, is innovative about the Marburg Model. It adopts an outreach approach by engaging with the family in which the violent incident occurred. Court assistants do not have the right to refuse to testify and are part of the law enforcement authority.

DV is, therefore, not treated as a private matter. Instead, it signals to the victim that the state is taking action for their protection and to the perpetrator that violence will not be tolerated. Positive effects on any children in the family are also expected since they quickly receive support through the assistance system. They witness that the perpetrator faces consequences for their violent actions and that the victims are not left alone.

Court assistance does not only represent the prosecution side. Due to their social work and educational counselling competencies, they also provide assistance, convey information, and collaboratively develop solutions with the affected parties.

1.1.4.11.2 Implementation and Practice

The Marburg Model has been practiced in the city of Marburg since 2011. When the governing fractions of the state of Hessen decided in their coalition agreement in 2019 to "continue to focus on innovative prosecutorial work for the 'combat against domestic violence,' for example, with the Marburg Model (acceleration of proceedings through networking of all actors involved in domestic violence protection)," the political framework for

widespread implementation was established. Since 2020, eight new positions for the court assistance provided for in the Marburg Model have been established in the state of Hessen.

In accordance with these standards, the police, in consultation with the prosecutor's office, have a catalogue of offenses that should be directly reported to the court assistance. Controversial cases are then sent to the prosecutor's offices with a request for a decision on the use of court assistance. Additionally, cooperation and networking are defined to foster a respectful, trusting, and targeted collaboration. According to the work standards, regular meetings and effective networking should take place. The participation of court assistants in the roundtables against DV organised by the districts and independent cities is bindingly regulated in the work standards. However, the organisation and frequency of the regularly held discussions with various cooperation partners, especially with local specialist counselling services, the police, and the officials of the prosecutor's office, can be tailored to the local context.

The procedure under the Marburg Model is as follows: After an incident of DV, the police promptly inform the court assistance by transmitting a protocol containing the personal data of the injured parties and suspects. After conducting an individual case review, the court assistance decides on the further course of action.

Work with the victims:

The court assistance typically conducts a home visit to the victims, which may be announced in writing beforehand. However, discussions can also take place at the police station, for example, if the suspects and victims live in the same residence, the police advise against home visits, or the victims prefer discussions at the station.

In the initial personal meeting, the victims receive a comprehensive briefing on the voluntary nature of their cooperation and their procedural rights. Subsequently, the victims have the opportunity to report on their current family and domestic situation, the course of the relationship, and the financial situation. The court assistance, in this and possibly additional counselling sessions, works empathetically and sensitively to identify the individual needs and issues of the victims who are still under the impact of the incident. They collaboratively develop support options and clarify necessary assistance. Ideally, the victims are informed by the court assistance, particularly about the specialised victim counselling centres existing in each regional court district, and are referred to them. In addition to psychological trauma counselling, information can also be provided on other specialised counselling services,

marriage and family counselling, or debt counselling. A contingency plan can be developed together, and, if there is a willingness to testify, assistance can be offered for accompanying them to the police interrogation. However, victim counselling, in terms of extended, longer-term support, and emotional stabilisation, is not part of the responsibilities of court assistance within the framework of the Marburg Model.

Work with the suspects:

The suspects are also contacted by the court assistance. They are given the opportunity to present the incident from their perspective. An important goal here is that the suspects engage with the act, reflect on their own actions, and work together with the court assistance to develop strategies for responding in future acute situations. These strategies can be further developed in training programs.

If necessary, a joint discussion with the affected parties can be conducted at the court assistance centre. This is particularly appropriate when the partners are still interested in continuing to live together. However, this discussion offer does not replace specialised relationship counselling or couple therapy. Instead, the court assistance assesses the willingness for further referral and informs about the relevant contact points.

Reporting to the Prosecutor's Office:

Subsequently, the court assistance reports the discussion contents of the parties involved to the prosecutor's office and provides a case-specific opinion on a suitable sanction for the suspects from their perspective. This should necessarily include the consequences for the victim, as this can be relevant to the question of sentencing. In particular, they inform the prosecutor's office about whether the suspects are willing to participate in a training program for perpetrators of DV according to the standards for perpetrator work of the Federal Working Group "Perpetrator Work Domestic Violence", or whether other approaches such as couples counselling, addiction and substance abuse therapy, or psychotherapeutic counselling are recommended as a judicial order.

The court assistance receives knowledge about the course of the proceedings from the prosecutor's office or the court. After three months, a follow-up support takes place. The court assistance writes to the parties involved again and inquires whether there have been changes in the situation or if there is a need for further discussion. If so, the court assistance can provide additional information about suitable counselling services. It becomes evident that the court assistance must have a good overview and comprehensive knowledge of

counselling and therapy offerings in their working environment to provide necessary help. Therefore, discussions with various cooperation partners, in addition to coordination with the police and officials of the prosecutor's office, are crucial at regular intervals.

1.1.4.11.3 Strengths and Weaknesses

Strength:

A political framework exists and working standards are described. The Hessian Ministry of Justice has defined minimum standards. Cooperation and interdisciplinary and interagency networking is promoted. Access to help is simplified and offered systematically (proactive approach).

The proactive approach of the Marburg Model addresses individuals who may have lost interest in pursuing the legal process or would not engage in counselling without the support of court assistance. Court assistance is an important interface to other help systems. The proactive approach and outreach counselling lower the threshold to the help system and improve the chances of those affected choosing the form of counselling or protection that meets their needs, their vulnerability and their life situation.

It is only through proactive or outreach counselling that many of those affected receive the information they need to make informed decisions about their future. Target groups can be reached who would not have found access to help themselves at the present time (BMFSFJ, 2010).

The core of the Marburg Model lies in the speed of the intervention.

The solution was developed with the intention of reaching all victims of DV equally. Vulnerable groups are therefore also the focus of the measure, although they are not explicitly addressed. In some aspects, such as a language barrier, court assistance must have a sufficient network to be able to provide comprehensive help. This individualised approach in particular is one of the strengths of the solution. If the use of an interpreter is necessary, the costs are to be covered by the prosecutor's office on whose behalf court assistance is engaged in the investigative process.

The intervention is aimed at both victims and defendants. The message is twofold: they experience that the suspects bear responsibility for their violent actions and that the victims are not left alone. These are important findings for breaking through structures of domestic violence.

Intervention increases protection through the establishment of support, civil protection orders and offender programmes.

After three months, a follow-up support takes place. This is particularly important for ambivalent victims, because the need for help may only arise later.

In the initial personal meeting with the court assistance service, the victims are fully informed about the voluntary nature of their participation and their procedural rights. Personal protection is an important issue. Both meet the requirements of the EU Victims' Rights Directive.

The effects for the criminal proceedings are positive, as the victim report provides information about the willingness to testify and about the victim's interests and makes it possible to take these into account when structuring the proceedings and determining possible conditions for discontinuation or sentencing. Contact with court assistance thus contributes to improved cooperation and therefore potentially more successful prosecution. It is essential for the success of this instrument that an internal judicial authority provides the information. The victim report from court assistance is part of the investigation file.

Weaknesses:

In order for the police and judiciary to deal appropriately with victims of domestic violence, professionals must be sufficiently trained to recognize the dynamics of domestic violence, the resulting stresses for victims and the consequences of traumatisation. While such training has been a standard requirement for police officers since the implementation of the Protection against violence act, there is no mandatory training for public prosecutors and judges who deal with such cases (Kotlenga, Nägele, Nowak, 2016).

Court assistants have no right to refuse to testify and are part of the prosecuting authority. Victims must be informed about this in a clear and understandable way.

1.1.4.12 Justification

A project for law enforcement was selected for the following reasons:

It is an intervention project that fills a gap in the intervention chain. By actively acting or remaining inactive, the police and public prosecutor's office represent the attitude of the state towards domestic violence. Both institutions are actively involved in co-operation alliances in many places. In many cases, state intervention still ends at the interface with criminal

prosecution. Domestic violence is rarely sanctioned by the public prosecutor's office. (BMFSFJ, 2010)

For a long time, it was difficult to involve law enforcement in (state) intervention processes in cases of domestic violence. (BMFSFJ 2010, page 17). This is why the Marburg Model is groundbreaking for cooperation between the police, prosecution, court assistance, victim counselling centres, protection facilities, perpetrator programmes, victims and suspects in order to end domestic violence.

1.1.4.12.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

Political support: The governing parties wrote the model into their 2019 coalition agreement and committed to its expansion. With this support, the Hessian justice system has been able to create 8 new workplaces for court assistance to date. Resources are important for implementation.

The Hessian Ministry of Justice has defined minimum standards. According to these standards, networking is established with regular meetings. The court assistants take part in the local round tables against domestic violence.

The organisation of regular personal meetings for all participants in the Marburg Model is crucial for the exchange, cooperation, planning, reflection and further development of the model.

Many agreements were reached between ministries, NGOs for victim support and offender work, intervention centres, court assistance and public prosecutors' offices and responsibilities were clarified.

The roles of court assistance and counselling centres are clarified. Although court assistance also acts as a social worker in proceedings, it does not replace the work of the counselling centres (NGOs). Court assistance is an important interface to further assistance.

According to the accompanying scientific research on intervention projects, successful implementation can be assumed because it is possible (BMFSFJ, 2010):

- to combine top-down strategies with bottom-up strategies,
- to link structures and activities at state level with regional structures and activities,
- to firmly anchor work results in institutional structures,
- to establish binding and needs-based cooperation,

- to maintain innovative capacity in the cooperation alliance.

The proactive approach of court assistance is embedded in a support system and network. The proactive approach and outreach counselling lower the threshold to the help system.

1.1.4.12.2 Practical relevance

The success and positive effects of the Marburg model lie in the early intervention of court assistance. As a rule, this should take place five days after the incident. Experience has shown that both the victim and the suspects accept counselling shortly after the offence. The victim is willing to testify, and the suspect is more motivated to undergo a training programme or accept other offers of help. This window of opportunity usually closes very quickly.

Victims and perpetrators are both addressed. The fact that they are visited quickly after an offence by the court assistance service signals to the victims that the state is doing something to protect them. The suspects are made aware that their actions will not be tolerated, and that domestic violence is not a private matter. This approach also has a positive impact on child protection.

Ending domestic violence is a process. Many victims are initially ambivalent about help or change. The effects of perpetrator programmes also take time. A follow-up support is important in order to be able to address changes and to see how it works and if further help is needed.

Offenders who participate in an offender programme on the basis of a court order or requirement complete it significantly more often than participants without a judicial background. A court order can apparently increase the motivation to complete an offender programme. Men who have become violent towards their partners rarely contact a facility that offers behavioural modification measures for this target group. External pressure is often necessary to start a perpetrator programme (BMFSFJ, 2010).

Protective measures, offender programmes and professional support can increase the protection of the victim.

Evaluations of the proactive approach show positive effects on victims: the proactive approach empowers those affected, expands their options for action and decision-making, increases their self-efficacy and gives them back control over their own lives (BMFSFJ, 2010).

In order to ensure consistent prosecution, the Marburg Model precisely records the victim's entire situation and incorporates this into the proceedings. Witnesses can be motivated, and their concerns addressed through personal contact with court assistance. If victims do not want to testify because they are afraid of the perpetrator and are under pressure, this now becomes visible and protective measures can be established.

Court assistance also provides information about victims' rights and procedures.

1.1.4.12.3 Evidence and Data

Access to help and protection measures

Evaluations of the proactive approach show positive effects on victims: the proactive approach empowers those affected, expands their options for action and decision-making, increases their self-efficacy and gives them back control over their own lives (BMFSFJ, 2010).

The interviews reveal the overall importance of the various support options with regard to coping with the consequences of the offence, but also with regard to dealing with criminal proceedings (Kotlenga, Nägele, Nowak, Goergen, 2016).

The importance of the court assistance

One useful instrument to ensure that victims are informed about proceedings and possibilities for support has proven to be the public prosecutor assigning the court assistance service to work in a proactive way (Kotlenga et al., 2016).

However, if victims do not attend the hearing, the case is usually closed. The court assistance service can help to establish personal contact with the victim (Kotlenga et al., 2016).

Contact with court assistance contributes to improved co-operation and thus potentially more successful prosecution. It is essential for the success of this instrument that an internal judicial body provides the information. The victim report is part of the investigation file (Kotlenga et al., 2016).

Networking

Experts from the area of the judiciary and victim protection state that good cooperation and networks are helpful in making the differentiated help network available to victims, but also in some circumstances for case-related cooperation as well. The round tables on domestic violence are described as helpful in offering insight into the activities of other professions. Especially the judiciary has to rely on a network in taking into account the needs of victims,

as it otherwise has little contact to victims or knowledge about their needs (Kotlenga et al., 2016).

Motivation to testify and cooperate - importance of rapid intervention

All the experts as well as the victims surveyed themselves draw attention to the close connection between subjective feelings of security and protection against repeat victimisation and revenge on the one hand and the willingness to cooperate in criminal proceedings on the other (Kotlenga et al., 2016).

The victim report provides information on the willingness to testify, gives advice on how to take victims' needs into account when organising proceedings and determining the sentence, and often contributes to increased cooperation and improved prosecution by taking victims' needs into account. Commissioning court assistance appears to be crucial for the success of this instrument (Kotlenga et al., 2016).

Victims are less willing to testify if it takes too long until they are questioned (Kotlenga et al., 2016). Therefore, judicial support that monitors the proceedings can help to increase the number of victims who testify.

Importance of criminal prosecution for victims

Sentences, the type of punishment and degree of penalty or dropping of charges (with and without requirements being attached) are in the view of victims highly relevant to subsequent coping (gaining more control or helplessness), to practical aspects of violence (e.g. to achieve enforcement of civil law regulations and claims to compensation of victims) and especially their future security (setting effective borders for perpetrators) (Kotlenga et al., 2016).

Offenders who participate in an offender programme on the basis of a court order or requirement complete it significantly more often than participants without a judicial background. A court order can apparently increase the motivation to complete an offender programme. Studies have shown that almost two thirds of men who start a programme also complete it (BMFSFJ, 2010).

1.1.4.12.4 Context of the Solution

With its objectives, structures and measures, the Marburg Model implements provisions of the "Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence" and the *EU Victim Protection Directive 2012/29/EU* of the European

Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 establishing minimum standards on the rights, support and protection of victims of crime.

Solution 4: “StoP - neighbourhoods without partner violence”

This part of the report presents the project „**StoP – Stadtteile ohne Partnergewalt (Neighbourhoods without Partner Violence)**“. The project’s initiator, Sabine Stövesand (Hamburg University of Applied Sciences), developed the original concept in 2006, and the first pilot project was launched in 2010 in Hamburg (Stövesand, 2007). The StoP concept was extended to Austria in 2019, where it is now being implemented at 28 locations.

“StoP - Neighbourhoods without Partner Violence“ stands for a community-oriented concept for prevention and intervention in the area of partner violence and for a network of district projects in various cities that are active under this name.

The presentation of the project is based on the following: Internet research on innovative developments in intervention against partner violence (“Solution”), various articles on the project (especially by the concept developer Stövesand), the project website and scientific reports and evaluations.

1.1.4.13 Description

1.1.4.13.1 Background and Aim

The starting points of StoP are the persistently high level of violence against women in the social environment and the still strong taboo surrounding domestic violence. The project will close the gap between being affected by violence and seeking help and enable faster support (see Stövesand, 2024).

„In recent decades, many measures have been taken to support victims of violence and change the situation: women's shelters, public campaigns, training courses, men's projects, work with perpetrators, federal action plans, amendments to laws. The measures are usually aimed either at victims, perpetrators, experts from various fields or the general public. One crucial factor has been neglected so far: the social and spatial environment of victims and perpetrators. (...) Action strategies must increasingly start where the violence takes place, i.e. directly in people's immediate lives.“ (Stövesand, 2015, cf.)⁶²

In connection with the implementation of the “Violence Protection Act” the project started to create the promotion of sustainable support structures in the social environment.

Aim:

⁶² For more details, see: <https://stop-partnergewalt.org/warum-braucht-es-stop/>)

The StoP project aims to strengthen those affected by violence and social networks in urban areas so that partner violence is no longer endured, kept secret, ignored or tolerated.

The "StoP" project has a dual objective: 1. to systematically develop and expand the willingness of people affected by violence and perpetrators of violence to come forward, and 2. to systematically develop and expand the willingness to intervene and the civil courage of a local community. In addition to removing the taboos surrounding partner violence and direct forms of support and intervention, willingness to intervene also means the willingness and ability of district residents to engage with the issue in a wider social and socio-political context and to develop collective forms of action (Stövesand, 2024).

1.1.4.13.2 Implementation and Practice

The StoP concept comprises eight methodological steps that build on each other, sometimes run in parallel and should be seen as a circle rather than a ladder:

1. "An institution or sponsor makes the decision to take up the topic and provide staff, premises and funding for it: Prepare decision-making processes, analyse and possibly expand resources and competencies.
2. The community is explored in its various dimensions and activated at the same time: social space analysis, network analysis, action research, activating surveys, community organising.
3. Neighbourhood action groups are established: Differentiated public relations work, everyday-oriented adult education and biography and remembrance work in the group.
4. The development of neighbourhood networks and change work on cultural guiding principles, concepts of identity and criteria of the residents in the community is broadened: exhibitions, artistic interventions in public space, public information tables, film evenings, creating low-threshold places of communication and useful relationships (e.g. exchange rings), initiation of processes of social self-understanding and promotion of the ability to act through e.g. school projects, dialogical learning, future workshops, forum and statue theatre.
5. Initiation and expansion of networking and cooperation at district level: establishment of district working groups, pooling of resources, mutual qualification.
6. Individual support and person-centred networking are offered: Legal and social counselling, establishing contacts with other institutions or entering into cooperations with them, person-centred networking.

7. Establishment of continuous, small-scale relationship and organising work (see under 3. and 4.)

8. Developing political alliances and enforcing political demands: developing strategies and applying targeted tactics, political networking.” (Stövesand, 2007; cited in: Stövesand, 2024)

The StoP approach aims to build or stabilise social contacts and networks and supports them in giving the victims support so that they can exercise their rights. An approach is needed that makes flight unnecessary in the long term because those affected feel safe on site. Those who are not directly involved often have important options for action open to them; they can help prevent escalations or stop the violence (Stövesand, 2024).

1.1.4.13.3 Strengths and Weaknesses

Strengths

Filling a gap:

The StoP project sees itself as a complement to existing policies. The project aims to fill a missing link between the living environment of those affected by domestic violence and the professional support system.

StoP strengthens the networks in the neighbourhood.

StoP's approach is based on the development of a scientifically sound action plan:

It is based on proven community approaches and the concept of action research.

StoP is a community project that offers participation for civil society:

Community projects enable civil society to play a constructive role in an urgent social problem. Participants experience themselves as helpful and effective (bottom-up approach). They can learn new things for themselves and experience meaningful activity in their living environment. Social cohesion is also strengthened.

Including men:

StoP is not just aimed at women. Men are an important target group when it comes to changing traditional role models and preventing violence.

People who use violence:

Through community projects, men (and women) who use violence also learn that their immediate social environment no longer looks the other way, but is on the side of those affected by violence.

Weaknesses

The project requires resources:

Project framework: sufficient time, sufficient intensity, sufficient financial resources. Funding must be secured for the project set-up for at least two years (Stövesand, 2024).

There is a **risk of instrumentalisation** with projects in the context of civil society involvement. They can be used as a cost-cutting model to negate or insufficiently fund professional support or to play them off against other public services (Stövesand, 2020).

Challenges:

Fluctuation of group members, especially at the beginning. This may be an indication that it is difficult to bear when the topic is actualised through the discussions and experiences or comes very close.

Stereotypes (cultural attributions), barriers due to certain norms, myths and cultural models and self-images (Stövesand, 2024).

1.1.4.14 Justification

The project "StoP - Neighbourhoods without Partner Violence" is the most widespread offer in Germany in the field of community mobilisation for the prevention of violence against women. It has been working continuously and successfully since 2010. StoP is active in various major cities in Germany and their surrounding areas. The approach has also been disseminated throughout Austria (in nine cities or regions with 25 projects). There is a total of 40 local projects in Germany and Austria.

Women (and men) affected by violence experience active, appropriate support through community projects, be it through listening, asking questions, providing information and support or through accompaniment, e.g. when going to a professional help centre. Through community projects, women (and men) affected by violence experience that their immediate social environment does not look the other way, that they are not left alone or even have to feel guilty due to the reactions of their environment.

The StoP community project closes a gap between victims of domestic violence and the professional support network.

StoP addresses new target groups:

- Men are important when it comes to changing traditional role models and preventing violence.
- The project is aimed at men (and women) who perpetrate violence. They learn that violence is not tolerated, that their immediate social environment is on the side of those affected by violence.

The StoP project brings the issue of domestic violence into the heart of the community, into the mainstream of social debates, organisations, actions and measures. Stövesand, 2024).

The approach has proven successful in Germany and Austria, where it has already reached thousands of people – women and men from young to old – in their neighbourhoods.

1.1.4.14.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

The initiators of StoP consider the following requirements to be important for organisations that want to work successfully with the StoP concept:

- The reference to the social space is recognised as a working principle,
- it has district expertise, i.e. the supporting organisation has been active in the district for more than three years, is known there and is well established,
- it is supported as an institution, not just through projects, and is expected to continue for at least the next three years,
- it works across generations and origins, has access to different population groups (people of colour, adults, young people...),
- it has a low-threshold approach: i.e. it (also) offers open programmes, e.g. in the context of leisure and cultural work, it has premises that can be entered and used without prior appointment and without stating specific problems,
- it has demonstrable experience in working with (resident) groups, public relations work and event organisation
- has demonstrable experience in gender- and diversity-sensitive social work (concept, projects)

- a team trained in the StoP approach (e.g. a permanent employee plus a freelancer) is available or is willing to set up such a team.

The following aspects are important measures for implementing the StoP project in a neighbourhood.

Action plan and training:

Training in the StoP approach is a prerequisite for using the copyrighted concept and an important building block for quality assurance during implementation. It is offered by the concept developer, usually in cooperation with the further education centre of the Hamburg University of Applied Sciences. The action plan for "StoP - Neighbourhoods without Partner Violence" according to Stövesand (2007) is taught as part of a training course, which also provides access to relevant supporting materials (e.g. for public relations work) (Stövesand, 2024).

'Activating survey' Method:

The example of StoP neighbourhoods without partner violence uses the 'activating survey' to illustrate how a project can get to know the local community in depth, activate it and make itself known. Project staff interview key people from different stakeholder groups such as religious communities, civil society groups, social and educational institutions and volunteers about the neighbourhood and the issue of violence. In this way, the project receives information, can introduce its own theme, initiates discussion and reflection, and gets to know other interested and active people through a snowball effect (Gloor/Meier, 2022).

"Table meetings":

The establishment of regular meeting points for active community members to exchange, train and get involved as neighbourhood groups is an important component, often the heart, of community projects. In the "StoP projects" in Germany, the so-called "kitchen tables" fulfil this function; the term "table" refers to the low-threshold nature of the get-together.

At the table meetings in Germany and Austria, the aim is to exchange information about one's own community, experiences, violence against women and in partnerships, civil courage and options for action (Gloor/Meier, 2022).

Leadership:

The StoP project requires a trained, professional and reliable facilitator and group leader who is capable of community work as well as being interculturally and gender competent, especially with regard to gender-based violence.

Financial resources:

Funding must be secured for the project set-up for at least two years, with the prospect of subsequent consolidation through inclusion in regular funding. At least two (half) staff positions or one position plus fee costs for an additional employee, funds for group and public relations work and for training in the StoP approach are required (Stövesand, 2024).

1.1.4.14.2 Practical relevance

The StoP project has initiated an important process in the different project areas. Over the course of the project, domestic violence prevention has increasingly evolved from an individual problem to a neighbourhood development issue and a matter of public interest. It has succeeded in raising awareness of domestic violence in the neighbourhoods, providing knowledge, initiating the involvement of civil society and embedding it in local structures (Stövesand, 2024).

In the neighbourhoods in which they run, StoP projects seek to contribute to prevention and support and to help break down the taboo surrounding intimate partner violence by encouraging community members to talk about it. Neighbours of those affected, as well as acquaintances, relatives and colleagues hear, know or have suspicions about intimate partner violence. However, fear, uncertainty and ignorance are prevalent, and due to such qualms, often nothing is done, and no intervention is made. This is what StoP wants to change. StoP projects aim to show how victims and members of their social environment can set in motion positive changes to end domestic violence in their neighbourhood or district. They seek to enable victims to talk about the violence and take appropriate steps, and to increase local communities' civil courage and willingness to act. Victims of violence and social networks in neighbourhoods are empowered so that they no longer tolerate, conceal or ignore intimate partner violence and the violence ultimately stops." (Gloor/Meier, 2022)

Development of political networking:

Community work is characterised by the combination of individual support measures with social-structural development processes. A core element is the participation of people, the promotion of activation and self-organisation, self-organisation in the sense of empowerment, which includes educational and awareness processes as well as collective capacity to act.

The creating relationships between different local actors and promoting and utilising the promoting and utilising the potential of social networks is another central point.

Example of neighbourhood support:

The low-threshold neighbourhood work proved to be particularly valuable when all counselling centres were closed due to Covid.

"The women were often at home and the situations of control and surveillance by violent partners became more intense. StoP employees were out and about in the neighbourhood, going into houses, bringing information material or food donations while keeping their distance and wearing masks. They also wrote the number of the nationwide help hotline in chalk on streets and courtyards and painted encouraging messages. There were information stands in front of the supermarket, information flyers on trees in the neighbourhood and later meetings and talks outside. The vast majority of people of all genders are interested in loving, equal relationships and are therefore potential allies for our goals."⁶³

Active neighbours ring doorbells in the event of loud arguments or shouting, officially to borrow something (e.g. flour or mobile phone cables), unofficially to interrupt acts of violence. Removing taboos, seeking help, support, getting involved, raising awareness and cohesion are important processes that have emerged over the course of the project and promote change from below (Stövesand, 2020).

1.1.4.14.3 Evidence and Data

Two evaluations are available on the StoP projects, which carry out community-based prevention work against intimate partner violence in Germany and Austria. One focuses on work in Hamburg (2020), while the other focuses Vienna (2022). The reports indicate that the community approach has been successfully implemented in both countries. At "Kitchen Tables" and "Men's Tables", active project participants come together to talk. These have proven to be useful tools for activation, reflection and training. They are valued and used regularly, and they are an important starting point for activities in the area. Further evaluations, e.g. on the outcomes and impact of neighbourhood projects tackling intimate partner violence, are not yet available (Gloor/Meier, 2022).

⁶³ For more details, see: <https://www.haw-hamburg.de/detail/news/news/show/partnergewalt-stoppen-das-projekt-stop-macht-es-vor/>

Principles of StoP works⁶⁴:

- Integrating the issue of domestic violence and partner violence into the community
- Working with local people, regardless of gender and ethnicity, using the local language and local symbols
- Community empowerment and ownership
- Participation: involving a growing community network in the activities
- Using creative methods to develop campaigns that people enjoy participating in over the long term

Importance of Community work:

StoP - is community work. Community work is a classic, professionally well-founded concept of action in social work. StoP was the first time that this approach was systematically applied to a new field of action, namely work against intimate partner violence (Stövesand, 2014).

A study by Christopher Browning (2002) has shown that an enlightened and good neighbourhood has a life-saving and violence-reducing effect. For example, cases of fatal relationship violence and serious partner violence were significantly lower in neighbourhoods where residents had attitudes that supported third-party intervention in cases of domestic violence. Tapping into the potential of neighbourhood resources and professionally promoting these conditions for civil society involvement is one of the core tasks of community work.

A Metastudy on the Significance of Civil Society Engagement and Local Communities for Preventing Domestic Violence (“Violence against Women and Providing Low-Threshold Support for People Affected”) was published in 2022. The study was funded by the German Federal Ministry for Family Affairs, Senior Citizens, Women and Youth (BMFSFJ) as part of the Federal Innovation Programme Gemeinsam gegen Gewalt an Frauen (Tackling Violence against Women Together). StoP is one of the successful community projects described (Gloor/Meier, 2022).

Evaluation of the StoP men's work:

The StoP project in Austria is currently being scientifically monitored with regard to the opportunities and challenges of men's work (survey of participants at the men's tables, participatory observation of meetings by the project team). An initial interim report (2023) on the results of interviews with three coordinators of men's work shows: StoP activities received

⁶⁴ For more details, see: <https://www.stop-partnergewalt.at/stop-in-der-eu/>

a lot of positive feedback from neighbours in all three districts, the project was generally welcomed, and public relations work is a focus of the activities. Due to the high media presence of StoP, the project has achieved a high level of awareness, which makes it easier to approach interested parties (Haller & Hasenauer, 2023).

Continuous growth of the StoP action approach:

The StoP concept was extended to Austria in 2019, where it is now being implemented at 28 locations.

Since 2023, the project team StoP has further expanded to France, Belgium, the Czech Republic and Romania. The AÖF, Association of Autonomous Austrian Women's Shelters, is leading the EU project StoP - Community Matters for two years from March 2023. Together with the project team, a StoP toolbox and a StoP curriculum will be developed for international use and expansion to the European Union. As part of the project, the foundations will be prepared and local actors will be trained in order to be able to implement StoP in selected EU partner countries in the future (**EU Funding (101095737 – PROJECT StoP – CERV-2022-DAPHNE)**).

1.1.4.14.4 Context of the Solution

StoP - Neighbourhoods without Partner Violence is an important addition to the professional support structure in cases of domestic violence. The StoP concept is based on the idea that communities have the potential to bring about change within themselves. It promotes the idea of civil courage and shows that domestic violence is not a private matter. The aim of StoP is to build and strengthen community networks so that partner violence is no longer tolerated, concealed or ignored.

Political alliances:

StoP has established contacts with experts at various levels, including the borough, local politics, the social department, social space management, the youth welfare office; at Hamburg level, cooperation in the "Round Table against Domestic Male Violence" and a discussion group in the responsible state authority; at federal level: presentation at the networking meeting of the intervention centres, important conferences (German Prevention Day) and meetings (nationwide women's shelter meeting) and political support (federal Ministry for Family Affairs). This has contributed to the consolidation of StoP in the region Hamburg Steilshoop and the creation of new StoP projects in other neighbourhoods (Stövelsand, 2020; Stövesand, 2024).

Both the willingness to disclose and the willingness to intervene are not purely personal dispositions, but are shaped by interlinked structural, cultural and individual factors, in particular they are determined by 1. the social situation and resources, 2. the prevailing norms and cultural models and self-images, 3. the visibility of violence, 4. the interest in the neighbourhood and the existence of trusting relationships and 5. individual motivations, fears, insecurities and competencies (cf. Stövesand, 2007). All of these factors must be taken into account and addressed, and this can only be done in a network of actors ranging from social urban development to educational institutions, social work and committed residents (Stövesand, 2024).

Through the StoP work, a process was set in motion in the respective project areas in the course of which the prevention of domestic violence was increasingly transformed from an individual problem into an issue of neighbourhood development and a matter of public interest. It has succeeded in sensitising larger social contexts to this problem, imparting knowledge, initiating civil society involvement and anchoring it in local structures (Stövesand, 2024).

1.1.4.14.5 Unintended Consequences and Risks

The following problems have been identified for the continuation of the project. In Germany, there is no federal funding to date. The 13 StoP projects in eight German cities are supported by a mixture of state and municipal funds and donations as well as a great deal of civil society involvement. Hamburg is leading the way with six projects. However, the projects in Austria only receive start-up funding for one year through the federal programme. In Germany, on the other hand, funding is provided for at least two years. It aims to change attitudes in the population as part of violence prevention and active protection for affected women*, i.e. civil courage, which takes time. While there is a nationwide coordination centre for StoP work in Austria, this is still lacking in Germany (Stövesand, 2021).

The project needs sufficient space and attention to ensure that joint agency can be developed. It requires a locally anchored commitment, and only a joint agency can bring about the necessary mobilisation push for an initiative. To summarise, experience shows that active community members and facilitators need to be found, formed and supported. Otherwise, there is a risk of actionism, which is unlikely to lead to success (Gloor & Meier, 2022).

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2.5 Spain

The Spanish report includes 4 different solutions and slightly deviates from the other report, as it includes the research findings of a research institution, i.e., DEUSTO, as well as a stakeholder in the field of combatting DV, i.e., PLV.

The first solution presents the specialised training in gender-based violence, that underpins the work of professionals from various fields to comprehensively address gender-based violence. The second solution details the Women's Shelter and their feminist approach to combating gender-based violence. The third solution included is the Gipuzkoa's Provincial Council Social Services' Attention Model, guidelines set forth by a regional board for regional services. The fourth and final solution is the specialised GAMA (Abuse Care Group) of the Valencia local police. This solution combines specialised police officers and tools to offer close and personalised support to victims of DV. The first three solutions are presented by University of DEUSTO and thus follows closely the above-mentioned method of desk-research and secondary use of previous IMPROVE research. The final report has been provided by PLV and represents not just the expertise of a stakeholder, but the provider of the solution presented.

Solution 1: Specialised training in gender-based violence for professionals

1.1.4.15 Description

1.1.4.15.1 Background and Aim

Spain has a solid legislative and public policy framework for the elimination of gender-based violence, which implies the obligation of public authorities to provide specialised and quality trainings for professionals. Training in gender-based violence needs to be of high quality and based on the knowledge provided by the experts in the field. In Spain, there are many courses and trainings, and many professionals are involved in them. The contents of these courses need to be addressed from an intersectional and feminist perspective to highlight and keep the professionals aware of the different barriers and situations that women suffer. As reported by Hausnarbide, a space for reflection on sexist violence of the Provincial Government of Gipuzkoa (Basque Country), 'only by guaranteeing quality training for professionals to deal with it from an anti-patriarchal model and a feminist approach will it be possible to address violence as a structural problem' (Sortzen Consultoría, 2022).

The aim of this solution is to provide qualified training to professionals from various disciplines, including the legal, social, health, education and communication sector, to

intervene, in a coordinated and multidisciplinary manner, in the field of violence against women, providing them with the necessary skills to design, plan, manage, implement and assess support, psychosocial, educational, socio-sanitary and/or legal interventions, from a holistic view of the intervention which considers the multiple factors that affect the needs of women and their context.

1.1.4.15.2 Implementation and Practice

Specialised training in gender-based violence for professionals has been implemented mainly through university postgraduate programs and ongoing training programs offered by public and private institutions and professional associations. In addition, vocational education includes the prevention of gender-based violence in the training plan of the vocational degree of Higher Technician in Promotion of Gender Equality, and there is a strategy to introduce specific content on gender-based violence in some courses of undergraduate programs at universities.

This specialised training is often offered on a general basis. However, universities frequently present in their research topics for final undergraduate and master's degree dissertations, topics related to the detection, intervention and reparation of gender-based violence victims-survivors in situations of special vulnerability such as elder women, migrant women, women living in rural environments, or women with physical and mental health problems. Some of the ongoing training programs for professionals also offer specialised courses in the assistance of these groups.

University training

Specific training for professionals is led, in the case of the courses offered in the universities, by researchers specialised in gender-based violence with the capacity to organise their own teaching proposal, always according to the curricula approved by ANECA, the National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation of Spain.

Postgraduate Professional Training

Specific training in gender-based violence is usually offered in postgraduate programs on gender studies or oriented to the training of Gender Equality Agents. The Spanish public university system is composed of 50 universities, 28 of them offer official postgraduate programs specialised in feminism, equality policies, gender relations and/or gender-based violence, and 18 have their own postgraduate programs on these topics (Universidad de Cantabria, 2021). There are 10 postgraduate programs in the specific field of gender-based

violence or violence against women in the following universities: Universidad de Jaén, Universidad Pablo Olavide, both in Andalusia, Universitat de les Illes Balears, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Universidad de Salamanca, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, the latter two in the Community of Madrid, Universidad de La Rioja, Universitat de València and Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, the Spanish university for distance education.

Gender Innovation Projects in University Teaching

The research and innovation projects carried out in the last decade on the integration of the gender dimension in university teaching are contributing to innovative and quality teaching practices, including gender-based violence training. These initiatives have been developed within the framework of European and state inter-university projects, academic networks and training proposals from universities and teaching staff to guarantee gender training in bachelor and master degree programs (García Lastra & Romero Gutiérrez, 2022). The commitment to introduce gender content in innovation and research is present in all areas of knowledge. The Catalan association Xarxa Vives d'Universitats has published the collection Guides for mainstreaming gender in university teaching (Xarxa Vives d'Universitats, 2022), which currently has a large volume of specific guides corresponding to 21 different disciplines from the five areas of scientific knowledge. These guides are available in Catalan, Spanish and English and have been increasing their thematic spectrum over the years reaching a significant variety.

Ongoing Professional Training

The specific training of professionals throughout their careers is carried out through programs and courses specialised in gender-based violence, often offered by state, regional and sometimes local public institutions, private entities, consulting companies or NGOs specialised in gender issues, and professional associations. These courses are usually offered specifically by the professional sector or on an interdisciplinary basis. They are usually designed by the entities and are given by professionals specialised in the field.

1.1.4.15.3 Strengths and Weaknesses

The Spanish academic and legal context, with more than 50 years of academic feminism (Ballarín Domingo et al., 1995) and 20 years of legislation for the elimination of violence against women are the main strengths of this solution. Violence against women has been a priority in the research, teaching and knowledge transfer work developed by academic

feminism over the past 50 years. Likewise, state and regional laws for the elimination of violence against women have been passed, during the first two decades of the 21st century, which have legitimised the implementation of this expert knowledge in public policies, in general, and in the training of professionals, in particular.

Regarding formal education, postgraduate degrees were presented as the most feasible specific teaching with which to respond to the professional profiles. These profiles resulted from the legislation on equality between women and men approved during the first decade of the twentieth century in Spain. However, this training has also encountered obstacles in a period of austerity policies. Furthermore, autonomous and state governments that have not always prioritised the financing of equality policy (Paleo and Alonso, 2015). The absence of professional opportunities perceived by those who studied these degrees (Ballarín Domingo, 2017) until the end of the last decade also presented problems. Since then, there has been an increase in the demand for specific training on gender equality and GBV as a result of the gender awareness-raising that entailed the massive mobilisations around the feminist strikes and against sexual violence that took place at the end of the last decade.

In regard to specialised training in vocational education, the integration of an advanced technical training for the promotion of gender equality into the Spanish vocational education in 2013 broadened the specialised training in GBV for professionals. However, the teaching staff that impart these vocational training programs do not have specific training in gender equality, but rather in the more general fields (García Lastra & Romero Gutiérrez, 2022). In addition, the number of High Schools that offer this course remains low.

With respect to the legislation, laws usually focus on the training of professionals working in specific gender-based violence services. They largely do not cover professionals working in non-specific services in the legal, social and medical fields who also support victims-survivors of gender-based violence. The report by Hausnarbide, a space for reflection on sexist violence of the Provincial Government of Gipuzkoa (Basque Country), emphasises these normative weaknesses. The State Pact against Gender-Based Violence does not pay attention to the training of Social Services professionals. Regarding Law enforcement, specific legal training is mandatory only for the holders of the Courts of Violence against Women, and the training of judges in violence against women is so scarce that it has not even been achieved that every professional working in the Courts of Violence against Women is an expert in this area. The State Pact does not contemplate either the training of

magistrates from other courts. Furthermore, the professionals who work in public defender's offices have little training in GBV, as they only take a 20-hour course that does not enable them to understand a problem as complex as violence against women (Sortzen Consultoría, 2022).

1.1.4.16 Justification

Specialised training in gender-based violence for professionals has been selected because of the extension and establishment of this solution across the different stakeholder groups and the Spanish territory. As mentioned above, many Spanish public universities offer postgraduate programs specialized in feminism, equality policies and gender relations that usually include training in gender-based violence (28 official postgraduate program and 18 non-official postgraduate programs). There are 10 postgraduate programs in the specific field of gender-based violence or violence against women distributed throughout the Spanish territory, including universities at the autonomous communities of Andalusia, Balearic Islands, Catalonia, Castile and Leon, Community of Madrid, La Rioja and Valencian Community, as well as the national university for distance education established in every region. According to the Autonomous Community Resources Statistics on Violence Against Women, in 2020, there were 1.277 training programs in gender-based violence for professionals, including 37.140 trained professional, covering the fields of medical, pharmaceutical, educational, police, judicial, social services, journalism and public sector (Delegación del Gobierno contra la Violencia de Género, 2020).

1.1.4.16.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

One decisive factor for the successful implementation of the specialised training in GBV for professionals has been the favourable academic context provided by academic feminism with more than 50 years of tradition in Spanish universities. Other factors included comprehensive legislation on Gender-Based Violence and Equality between Women and Men, the support of national and regional governments and the promotion of postgraduate programs on relevant topics by women's institutes, as well as ongoing training programs and the cooperation between academia, women's organisations, and the government. Regarding the later, it was respective governmental units aiming to promote equality between women and men.

Especially relevant as a facilitator is the Spanish legislation, a result of the impulse of social, academic and institutional feminism. Spanish legislation has legitimised the role of

universities in training professionals in gender equality in several laws, and training in gender-based violence is one of the priority areas in gender equality training. The first to do so was the Organic Law 1/2004 on Comprehensive Protection Measures against Gender-Based Violence, which states that universities will include and promote training, teaching and research in gender equality and non-discrimination in all academic areas in a cross-sectional way (article 4.7.). Among all the areas of institutional action, this law focuses on the socialisation process and the role of education (Venegas, 2010), incorporating training in gender equality and non-violence at all levels of the educational system, in addition to establishing the obligation of the educational administrations to ensure the initial and ongoing training of teachers. The second was the Organic Law 3/2007 for the Effective Equality of Women and Men, which explicitly states the inclusion of knowledge on equality between women and men in the curricula and the creation of specific postgraduate courses (article 25). Subsequently, Law 14/2011 on Science, Technology and Innovation incorporated the implementation of the gender perspective in the Spanish scientific system and, specifically, the promotion of gender and women's studies (thirteenth additional provision). Furthermore, during the transition to the European Higher Education Area (EHEA), the Royal Decree 1393/2007, which established the organisation of official university education, also ordered the introduction of this knowledge in the reorganisation of university programs. Recently, the Organic Law 2/2023 on the University System also includes the introduction of the gender perspective in all university activities and functions through the Equality Offices (Article 43).

The *State Pact against Gender-Based Violence* approved in December 2017, a historic milestone in Spain to eliminate violence against women, includes the promotion of specific training for professionals as one of the ten axes of this pact. The Axis 5: *Promoting the training of the different agents to guarantee the best assistance response* states the following:

“In order to offer victims of gender-based violence the best possible assistance, it is necessary to expand the specialised training of all professionals involved in prevention, protection and psychosocial assistance to victims. It is therefore unavoidable to continue promoting the training of all professionals involved: judges, prosecutors, psychosocial teams, forensic doctors, law enforcement agencies, health personnel and teachers, among others. Training must include both the techniques and procedures of their profession, as well as the characteristics, causes, effects and consequences of violence against women. The commitment lies in the training

contents being mandatory, approved by specialised organisations and accessible for all operators.” (State Pact against Gender-Based Violence, 2017)

Training for professionals is also part of Axis 1 on *Awareness and Prevention*, referring to teacher training, initial training in universities (measures 12, 13 and 16) and ongoing training (15), training of media and advertising professionals (47 and 52) and training of health professionals (60 and 61). Axis 3 on *Improving Assistance, Help and Protection for Victims* also includes training for legal professionals (139, 140, 150) and law enforcement officers (152).

1.1.4.16.2 Practical relevance

This solution is relevant because it provides professionals with needed knowledge and skills for supporting gender-based victims and survivors, as well as for raising public awareness among those participating in the academic and ongoing training programs. The study on Gender-Based Violence in University Education by Ferrer Pérez et al. (2010) concludes that those who best predict gender-based violence are those who have studied gender-related subjects.

1.1.4.16.3 Evidence and Data

As mentioned above, one of the main strengths of specialized training for professionals who support victims-survivors of gender-based violence is the law mandate, with more than two decades in Spain. The *Organic Law 1/2004 on Comprehensive Protection Measures against Gender Violence* has been an unprecedented step forward in this regard and has contributed to the promotion of GBV-specialised training in other educational, scientific and social laws. As reflected in the words of a judge interviewed on the occasion of the fieldwork conducted on work package 1, the 1/2004 Law had a significant effect on the obligation of this training in some professional sectors:

“In the case of judges, training is mandatory, so by law, to be working in a Court for Violence Against Women, you must take specific training in the matter. This is something that, well, was also very demanded, and that in one of the legal reforms was agreed upon (...) I started my career in 2002 and the Integral Law against Gender Violence was not approved. So, no, in my career, nothing, zero, absolutely zero. When I was in the opposition, yes (...) I did my career from 2002 to 2007 and precisely, well, we entered the opposition and the law was approved and all the legislative change,

which is very, very important, took place. So, already in the opposition, yes” (Judge of a Court for Violence Against Women).

1.1.4.16.4 Context of the Solution

This solution aligns with the Spanish legislation on Gender-Based Violence and Equality between Women and Men. However, it has been successful due to the strength of academic feminism in Spanish universities. By the end of the first decade of the 21st Century, every public university in Spain had instituted a women’s and gender studies institute, research centre, chair, or seminar (Ortiz Gómez, 2005), around which the promotion of gender studies in university research and teaching is organised. Academic feminists have been the main promoters of training in gender-based violence in universities, often on a voluntary basis.

1.1.4.16.5 Unintended Consequences and Risks

Anti-gender movements and politics, which emerged in the second decade of the 21st Century with the rise of the far right in Europe (Graff and Korolczuk, 2022), are today one of the main risks facing this specialised training in gender-based violence. The consolidation of this specialised training runs the risk of being neutralised or diverge from the scientific knowledge about gender-based violence, domestic violence and intimate partner violence, elaborated within the framework of academic feminism. As the consolidation is regulated in the Spanish laws and promoted by institutional feminism from different national, regional and local public bodies each of which can alter the original content. As gathered during the interviews with professionals conducted in work package 1, some of the training courses offered to professionals included contents that did not correspond to the scientific knowledge elaborated in the framework of gender studies. This was the case for content offered at gender equality public institutions in autonomous communities where the far right is in the government.

“Training that is being given in the field of [gender] equality by governments of this political colour [far right] in which they are giving training that is contrary to [gender] equality (...) I remember the case of the person who gave training on [gender] equality and who did not... let's say, who talked about everything but [gender] equality.”
(Psychologist).

Another risk of the specialised training for professionals is the cost of the postgraduates or the courses, which can lead to the non-engagement of professionals in these trainings, with

the consequent drop in enrolment and the ending of the degrees. The interviews conducted in the framework of work package 1 show differences between the training offered among sectors, being often free for the judiciary sector, but not in other cases as the social sector, in which professionals are often in a more precarious situation. Training involves an economic cost that not all professionals can afford.

“I took the course on gender-based violence at the professional association [of social workers] because the [Autonomous Community where she works] requires 200 hours to be able to work (...) in [GBV] specific resources. So, well, since it was something that interested me and I wanted to do it, it was a course that was quite good, but it cost me 600 euros for 200 hours, which is not 1000 [hours] either, and it was because I was a member [of the professional association], the course was [in fact] 1200 euros (...) We already belong to a precarious enough sector, the few economic resources we have left to pay the rent and so on... to allocate 600 euros to train me to intervene better...” (NGO Social Worker).

Solution 2: The Women's Houses and the feminist movement as a gateway to Services

1.1.4.17 Description

1.1.4.17.1 Background and Aim

After the fall of the Franco regime, the feminist movement in Spain emerged, challenging the public-private dichotomy concerning women and coining the slogan, "the personal is political." This movement sought to assert women's control over their own bodies, identifying sexuality and reproduction as primary systems of oppression (Osborne, 2009). Feminists of that era recognized violence as a crucial factor in women's subordination to men. Consequently, the movement's primary goal was to equip women with resources and tools to combat this violence.

One of these resources involved the creation of the Women's Houses whose objectives are as follows:

- Promote Feminist Awareness: Enhance feminist consciousness among women.
- Develop Feminist Actions: Implement initiatives aimed at empowering women.
- Increase Understanding of Gender-Based Violence: Provide deeper insights into gender-based violence.
- Offer Specific Guidance: Supply information and support to help women overcome gender-based violence situations.
- Encourage Socio-Political Participation: Foster active participation of women in socio-political spheres.
- Promote Gender Equality: Advance the principles of gender equality.
- Create Open Meeting Spaces: Establish inclusive spaces for individuals, groups, and associations advocating for equality.

The first initiative was launched in the municipality of Ermua in 2003 and became a reference point in the following years. This was followed by the establishment of similar initiatives in Arrasate in the same year, Eibar in 2004, Ondarroa in 2007, Balmaseda in 2008, Durango in 2009, Donostia in 2010, Azpeitia in 2011, Basauri in 2012, Vitoria-Gasteiz in 2017, and Errenteria in 2019. In 2020, processes were initiated in various municipalities in Gipuzkoa such as Zarautz, Zumaia, Hernani, Tolosa, and the Urola Garaia Consortium, as well as in Portugaleta in Bizkaia.

1.1.4.17.2 Implementation and Practice

The Women's Houses emerge from the collaboration between public institutions and citizens (Picaza, 2017:159). There are two distinct processes through which these houses are created. In some instances, the feminist movement has actively advocated for the establishment of a Women's House and spearheaded the efforts to bring it into existence. In other cases, the initiative has stemmed from policies or projects developed by the relevant equality department, always in partnership with equality councils and local women's groups.

Therefore, the Women's Houses have been established and developed at the municipal or county level through locally driven participatory processes, tailored to the specific needs and characteristics of each municipality. Unlike other municipal facilities, citizens have been actively involved in defining all aspects of these projects, including the objectives, values, principles, characteristics, and management models of the Houses. This approach has fostered future collaborations and set a clear precedent for implementing public policies effectively.

The creation process of Women's Houses is crucial, as it is closely tied to the unique characteristics of each municipality and the strength of the feminist movement and women's groups within it.

1.1.4.17.3 Strengths and Weaknesses

Strengths

The Women's Houses serve as a long-term protective network.

When women who have suffered violence receive assistance from the protection system (such as social services, shelters, etc.), they begin the process of empowerment. However, this empowerment process, is usually a long-term process and extends beyond the initial support provided by the system. At this critical juncture—when women no longer have any other support network—the Women's Houses play a fundamental role.

The Women's Houses provide special attention in a non-institutionalised space.

Due to their structure, the Women's Houses are perceived as a non-official or non-institutionalized space, thus making it easier for women who have suffered violence or those who want to ask about it to approach them. In this sense, the Houses are valued as a more private, quiet, comfortable, warm, and safe space than other municipal services.

"I think it is a privileged space, it is a gateway for all the women that come here"
(Equality Technician in a Women's House).

The Women's Houses serve as important complements to the protection system.

The Houses are important complements to the protection system for several reasons. They provide initial support from the beginning, before women receive assistance from other specialised services; they facilitate long-term recovery processes, and welcome women who do not qualify for the formal protection system. Additionally, they offer a space for women to clarify questions before taking more formal steps and, in some cases, host support groups for women who have suffered violence. Their status outside the formal protection system adds significant value to the services they provide.

The Women's Houses reflect accessibility and variety.

They cater to various types and profiles of women, encompassing a wide range of origins and ages. Gender-based violence is approached from a broad perspective, allowing the Houses to provide initial protection to women who fall outside the formal system. They also reach women who, despite suffering from gender-based violence, may not be aware of their situation or recognise it as such, and who have not yet engaged with the protection system.

Some women who come to the Women's Houses may not initially perceive the violence they are experiencing. Through the activities offered, they come to realise and acknowledge their situation. Importantly, no specific event is required for a woman to receive help from the Women's Houses. Their proximity to women and the special attention they provide facilitate quicker identification of needs and more accessible support.

The Women's Houses operate from a feminist point of view.

Feminism is integral to their essence, with most of these Houses originating from feminist movements or demands. This foundational essence has been preserved over time, maintaining a critical perspective and advocating for systemic transformation. Consequently, the work and services provided by the Women's Houses are structured through a feminist lens.

"We must remember that the Women's Houses are a project driven by feminist organisations. What we, as professionals in these Houses, offer to the women who come here is not only the chance to build a social network but also the opportunity to

transition from being victims of gender-based violence to becoming activists." (Equality Technician in a Women's House).

The Women's Houses serve as a reference point for addressing gender-based violence.

They interact daily with various stakeholders, including women's associations or groups, social workers, the media, political representatives, schools, local associations, and users. These stakeholders consistently recognise and highly value the work performed by the Women's Houses.

Fluid communication with the public administration.

Permanent dialogue between political staff, the association, and technical staff is essential. In co-managed Women's Houses, efforts are made to build effective communication and coordination, balancing autonomy with oversight and project monitoring. Strong partnerships are fundamental to the project's success, fostering collaboration between associations and those working in the equality service. Trust and cooperation must be continuously developed. Both technical and political staff need to demonstrate openness and flexibility, keeping the ultimate goal of the project—collective and individual empowerment of women—at the forefront.

Weaknesses

Lack of specialised services.

Some Women's Houses lack specialised services such as psychological and legal support. While these services are considered highly beneficial, their inclusion needs clear definition to avoid potential misinterpretations or misunderstandings about the scope of the Houses' responsibilities.

Intuitively articulating the gaps in the protection system.

Although the Houses are not responsible for the shortcomings of the protection system, currently they are responsible for covering those shortcomings. Especially in two cases:

- When the deadlines for receiving care services (psychological and legal) from the Provincial Council are very long. In response to this, some houses attend to the woman using the resources of the house while in other cases, they may pay for private psychological and legal care, until the women are attended to in the services of the

Provincial Council. The houses are clear that this is not a function that corresponds to them, but in the absence of an adequate response, they prefer to take on this task.

- When women need "accompaniment". One of the most notable deficiencies in the current protection system is the "accompaniment" of women who suffer gender-based violence. This being so, the Houses offer coverage to the system, offering help to women in specific situations: to go to court, to go to the police station, to the shelters, etc. It is not clear how to articulate this help and from where it should be offered, whether from the social services or from the Houses. It is noted that the Houses have the potential to carry out this work, since the women in the Houses are particularly supportive. It is also believed that the Houses should have a special service to channel this help, with an adequately trained person.

Need to create places for the construction of networks among the Women's Houses.

It is necessary to create a network among the Women's Houses, that is, a space for reflection. Until now, each house looked at its own reality, but it is convenient to represent a common path with the rest of the houses and to respond in a coordinated manner to the challenges they face today. Working together can guarantee a shared and broad view on different topics. In addition, it offers the possibility of sharing experiences, learning how others do it and offering mutual help. In other words, working together and strengthening each other.

Need to improve the systematisation of data collection.

All the houses have taken steps to improve data collection and processing but see the need for improved systematisation. Not only to collect the profile of the women who pass through the houses, but also to measure the dimension of the work the houses do and to carry out a continuous evaluation of the work. This systematisation will also make it possible to carry out an adequate transfer to the newly created houses. To this end, it will be convenient to define the data to be collected, the criteria for data collection and the data collection itself, to be clear about the reason for collecting data, etc. It may be convenient to share the data collection criteria among all the houses.

Difficulty of access for migrant women.

There are difficulties for migrant women to participate in the Women's Houses, and this aspect is a challenge to be met by all of the Houses. To achieve this, it would be necessary to strengthen ties with migrant women through activities focused on working on the relevant

aspects of their daily lives, the discrimination they experience in their daily lives; it is also essential to involve the women who participate in the house, as they are a fundamental pillar for creating the network of women in the locality. In this sense, the importance of networking with the rest of the municipal areas (migration, social services, Basque language, education, sports, etc.) is highlighted, in order to be able to carry out a transversal approach to the actions contemplated in the equality policies.

Difficulties when it comes to coordination with professionals.

In order to offer real comprehensive care, it is necessary to develop an optimal coordination and articulation between the different agents working in the field of gender-based violence. Currently, this relationship differs depending on the case.

A better articulation would improve the referral process. Currently, it seems that social services do not always refer women who suffer violence to the Houses (because there is no habit, because the potential of the shelters is not understood, etc.), even though women who could potentially suffer violence are identified in these spaces. Furthermore, when a referral is made, in some Houses it is not easy to attend the woman (because there are workshops underway, because there is no adequate supply, etc.).

In the opposite direction -when the shelters refer women who have suffered gender-based violence to social services- difficulties also arise, since sometimes social services do not attend to these women: because the criteria of the Houses and those of the social services do not always coincide in defining what gender-based violence is; because it is difficult for the social services to attend to certain specific profiles of women; because of access criteria, etc. At the same time, it may be beneficial to define a common model of care for all the agents in the care system; to agree on the type of care to be offered. Working with other agents in the care system can lead to the development of a model of care based on a feminist point of view; the houses can share a work model with different agents and promote a feminist perspective in the care system.

Tensions among public-community collaboration.

Public-community collaboration often generates tensions due to unclear roles and conflicting work styles between public institutions and citizens. These tensions highlight the need to clearly define the responsibilities of each party. One of the future challenges may be to find a balance between the public and community spheres. To enhance public-community cooperation, it will be important to build relationships based on mutual knowledge and trust.

This involves working on establishing conditions that foster strong, trusting partnerships and providing the necessary resources and support to strengthen the activities of the Women's Houses.

Lack of knowledge.

Among the women who do not participate in the Women's House, a sense of distance is noticeable. Despite the fact that most women claim to know about it [the House], those who are more distant do not perceive the most distinctive features of the Women's Houses, such as the weaving of networks and empowerment.

Lack of women's adherence to the project.

Despite being in favour of the actions and activities carried out by the Women's Houses, some people are not inclined to participate in them and express their solidarity from a second plane. In this sense, ideas associated with this adherence are made explicit, such as the lack of role models and the willingness of some women to "stay in the background" (interpreting it as a desire to avoid prominence or public exposure).

1.1.4.18 Justification

1.1.4.18.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

The Women's Houses have been established and developed at the municipal or county level through locally driven participatory processes, tailored to the specific needs and characteristics of each community. Unlike other municipal facilities, these Houses have involved citizens in defining every aspect of the project—including objectives, values, principles, characteristics, and management models. This participatory approach has fostered future collaborations and established a concrete method for implementing public policies.

1.1.4.18.2 Practical relevance

The Women's Houses emerge from the collaboration between public institutions and citizens, emphasizing a cooperative approach. The Women's Houses are built on two key pillars: feminist agents and women's associations, who play a crucial role in promoting and driving the activities of the Houses. At the same time, municipalities have embraced this need and provided a formal channel for it. As a result, the Women's Houses represent a convergence of both the public and community spheres.

In this context, the establishment processes are crucial. To date, the Women's Houses have been designed and created at the municipal or county level. All aspects of each House—such as objectives, characteristics, and activities—have been developed through participatory processes tailored to the specific needs and characteristics of each municipality. This approach not only fosters collaboration between institutions and citizens during the creation phase but also sets the stage for ongoing cooperation in the future. These bottom-up processes enhance mutual recognition and trust, establishing an innovative approach to public policy development.

1.1.4.18.3 Evidence and Data

Currently, in the territory of Gipuzkoa, there are 14 Women's Houses. This section presents the data collected from the Women's House of Donostia - San Sebastián, as it is the capital of the Gipuzkoa Territory.

The latest data provided by the Women's House of Donostia - San Sebastián indicates that during the first half of 2021, a total of 6,091 visits were received, averaging 1,015 visits per month and 56 daily visits. Also, during the 2020-2021 academic year, a total of 19 workshops and 17 empowerment groups were offered, with 729 registrations. As for the services, 987 appointments were recorded. Participation in the services offered by the Women's House is broken down as follows:

- Legal Advice and Social Intervention Services: 144 interventions were carried out; 26 related to gender-based violence, 15 in its criminal aspect and 11 in the civil aspect. Regarding questions about divorce and family proceedings, there were 56 interventions. The areas of regularisation and immigration were in high demand, with 36 interventions, additionally questions about asylum were addressed.
- Social Counselling Service: Women attended directly: 84, Follow-up and accompaniment: 125
- Legal Advisory Service: 154 women were recorded; of these, 20 disclosed being victims of gender-based violence and/or sexual assault. In consultations about separation or divorce, it is noted that there is often a history of abuse that some women either do not want to address or do not wish to initiate any criminal action against their partners.

- Psychological Support Service: 175 sessions were held from September 2020 to July 2021. Many women arrive after having gone through the entire available resource circuit and feel they still need support in their recovery.

In sum, it can be highlighted that women typically exhibit strong support for this project. This is partly because the institutions are addressing a need or demand identified by women's associations and the feminist movement. Additionally, women are involved from the outset in shaping the details of the project, which fosters a sense of ownership and connection to these spaces.

1.1.4.18.4 Context of the Solution

The Women's Shelters, in addition to being key spaces in the municipalities of the Basque Autonomous Community, have become a link for solidarity, sisterhood, and both collective and individual empowerment for women in these municipalities. This highlights the strategic importance of these spaces in the fight against gender-based violence, the transformation of societal values, and the empowerment of women.

These empowerment, wisdom, and supportive shelters for women have been a historical demand from feminist movements and women's groups. The establishment of these projects aimed to include the voices of diverse women from each municipality and to develop working processes to gather the opinions of Women's Councils, feminist groups, organisations focused on gender equality, and social entities from each municipality. Through these processes of building spaces for citizens, public equality policies have been put at the service of women's groups in towns and cities, not without complications in some cases, which involved resolving disagreements to reach consensuses that could bring these projects to fruition.

1.1.4.18.5 Unintended Consequences and Risks

Lack of human and material resources.

It is crucial to identify the required resources from the outset, including both material (space and internal resources) and human (necessary personnel) needs. Inadequate space or resources can hinder the growth and effectiveness of the Women's Houses, potentially stalling their ability to provide adequate services. Similarly, insufficient, or poorly managed staffing can undermine the quality of service and contradict the administration's commitments to equality policies. Jobs in the Women's Houses should be filled by qualified professionals

under optimal conditions, with positions either secured through civil service or, in the case of co-management, guaranteed to meet good working standards.

Lack of social awareness of the Women's Houses.

There may be a lack of understanding about the role and benefits of Women's Houses among both professionals and the general public. Questions such as, "What is this space for? Is it only for women?" may arise. To address this, it is important to promote the Women's Houses as essential and valuable services. Internal efforts within City Councils should focus on recognizing the significance of the Women's Houses and integrating them effectively into municipal policies.

Solution 3: Gipuzkoa's Provincial Council Social Services' Attention Model for Gender-Based Violence

1.1.4.19 Description

1.1.4.19.1 Background and Aim

The Provincial Councils of the Basque Country—Bizkaia, Araba, and Gipuzkoa—are administrative boards coordinated by the autonomous Basque Government and operate under the Statutes of Gernika. In this framework, social services and the promotion of social welfare are competencies transferred to both City and Provincial Councils. This structure supports proximity, personalisation of care, and the decentralisation of resources and services.

According to Law 12/2008, of December 5, 2008, on Social Services, care is divided into Primary Care Services (Basic Social Services), managed by local councils, and Secondary Care Services (Specific Social Services), managed by Provincial Councils. Social services are accessible to the general public, while specialised services require prior diagnosis or intervention, coordinated by Provincial Councils.

Over the past few years, the Gipuzkoa Provincial Council has promoted various initiatives aimed at improving the response to gender-based violence against women. In this context, in 2019, the latest multidimensional evaluation process was conducted in collaboration between the Gender Equality Body and the Department of Social Policies. This evaluation allowed for the identification of areas for improvement and the design of plans to enhance the quality of the response to the violence faced by women.

In this regard, one of the improvements worth noting refers to the creation of a working group (named AMUUM) led by the Social Inclusion and Attention to Women Victims of Gender-Based Violence Service. This group includes representatives from the various regional service providers that assist victims of gender-based violence. During 2021, AMUUM, supported by EDE Fundazioa, took on the challenge of considering and reflecting on how the intervention model should be. This process involved reviewing their own practices as well as those of other services. Thus, as a result of this process and subsequent systematisation of the generated knowledge, practical recommendations emerge that lead to the development of this attention model.

These recommendations, consistent with a gender-perspective intervention model, stem from an initial reflection on the fundamental principles outlined in various normative frameworks and international, national, regional, and local recommendations, both in the area of gender-based violence against women and in the fields of social inclusion and social services. Ultimately, this work aims to ensure that the different services provided by the Gipuzkoa Provincial Council to victims of gender-based violence offer a response that is aligned and coherent with the same principles and values, thereby contributing to the adoption of common quality standards.

This is why this work provides concrete guidelines to help translate the fundamental principles into practices, thus facilitating the direction of improvements and changes in services (micro level). Additionally, it aims to guide services towards excellence by highlighting the elements where intervention may be most beneficial.

1.1.4.19.2 Implementation and Practice

The importance of outlining these guidelines ultimately lies in their contribution to removing meso-level obstacles that may hinder the implementation of the recommendations for micro-level support. This intervention model establishes a framework for professional actions across various care services, ensuring they adhere to agreed-upon criteria. By aligning with regulatory frameworks in both gender equality and social services, the model aims to provide a consistent and effective response to male violence against women.

Key aspects of the intervention model:

Homogeneous Criteria.

The model provides a uniform approach for professional interventions, ensuring that all services operate under the same guidelines. This consistency is crucial for achieving coherent and effective results across different care services.

Regulatory Alignment.

The intervention model is designed to be in line with existing regulatory frameworks, including the previous Aurre! Plan, the 3rd Provincial Plan for the Equality of Women and Men of Gipuzkoa, and Law 1/2022. This alignment ensures that the response to gender-based violence is both legally compliant and reflective of established best practices.

Focus on 'How'.

Emphasizing the methods of intervention is key to the effectiveness of the response. The model outlines specific guidelines on how services should be delivered to achieve sustainable, effective, and high-quality outcomes.

Sustainable and Effective Response.

By defining the main characteristics of the intervention, the model aims to offer a response that is not only effective but also sustainable in the long term.

Objectives of the Aurre! Plan.

The Aurre! Plan's general objective was to ensure that women facing sexist violence receive adequate attention. This involves enabling them to exit these situations in an empowering manner, promoting social recognition, and addressing the restitution of their violated rights.

In summary, the intervention model serves as a comprehensive guide for professional practice, ensuring that responses to gender-based violence are effective, consistent, and aligned with regulatory standards. It builds on established plans and laws to create a robust framework for supporting victims and addressing male violence against women.

*1.1.4.19.3 Strengths and Weaknesses***Strengths****The flexibility of the Legislative Framework.**

The adaptable nature of the legislation enables intervention processes that better align with women's lived experiences. Notably, the absence of mandatory reporting for accessing resources facilitates more responsive and effective interventions.

Coordinated and Decentralised Intervention.

The model emphasizes a coordinated approach to social services that is also decentralised, allowing for localized and contextually relevant support.

Coordination between Associations and Public Institutions.

There is a strong focus on collaboration between various associations and public entities, enhancing the overall effectiveness of the support network.

Intersectoral Perspective.

The model adopts an intersectoral approach, breaking from traditional single-sector models to address GBV comprehensively.

Reparation and Healing as Transformation.

The framework includes a focus on reparation and healing, viewing these processes as crucial for transformative change for survivors.

Autonomy and Social Agency.

The model supports working from a place of autonomy and emphasises the social agency of women, empowering them in their recovery and activism.

Incorporation of the Feminist Approach.

A feminist perspective is integral to the model, guiding its principles and practices.

Community Perspective.

The model leverages a community-based approach, recognising the importance of collective involvement and support in addressing GBV.

Consideration of Minors as Victims.

The model acknowledges the impact of GBV on minors, ensuring that their needs are considered and addressed.

Strategies and Guidelines Against Re-Victimisation.

The framework includes specific strategies and guidelines designed to prevent re-victimisation and ensure a supportive and respectful process for survivors.

Weaknesses

Limited Role in Judicial Proceedings.

Social services often have limited influence or recognition in the judicial system, affecting their ability to contribute their expertise and perspectives in legal proceedings.

Insufficient Resources for Comprehensive Support.

Social workers frequently face a lack of resources, which hinders their ability to provide the full spectrum of support needed for effective intervention and care.

Gap Between Judicial and Social Intervention

There is a noticeable disconnect between the judicial system and social services, creating challenges in coordinating efforts and ensuring a unified approach to addressing GBV.

Lack of Judicial Training.

There is a deficit in training within the judicial sphere regarding gender-based violence, which impacts the effectiveness of legal responses and support for survivors.

Partial Integration of Reparation.

While reparation is a component of the model, it has been only partially integrated, limiting its impact on transformative healing and recovery for survivors.

1.1.4.20 Justification

1.1.4.20.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

In 2022, the Provincial Council of Gipuzkoa, guided by the III Plan for the Equality of Women and Men and Law 1/2022, developed a pioneering care model for women experiencing GBV in the territory. This model emphasises a feminist perspective and gender approach, recognising GBV as a violation of human rights and necessitating non-discriminatory, victim-centred services.

Key Principles of the model's implementation:

Feminist and Gender Perspective.

The intervention model is grounded in feminist principles, ensuring that the care provided addresses the complex factors influencing GBV and respects the victims' rights to dignity, autonomy, security, privacy, and social inclusion.

Empowerment and Intersectionality.

Empowerment is central to the approach, aiming to help women recognize and challenge the normalisation of violence. An intersectional perspective is essential to address the diverse needs and additional inequalities faced by victims based on various factors like age, social class, ethnicity, and disability.

Intervention Strategies.

Effective strategies include person-centred planning, avoiding re-victimisation, encouraging participation, ensuring comprehensiveness, fostering a community model, promoting sisterhood, and enhancing resilience.

Quality and Accountability.

The model advocates for continuous improvement, accountability, and a focus on quality of life. It emphasizes the need for ethical practices and results measurement to ensure effective support and service delivery.

The comprehensive care model proposed by the Provincial Council of Gipuzkoa aims to align all services with these principles, ensuring a consistent, high-quality response to GBV and guiding improvements and excellence in service provision.

Practical relevance.

The Gipuzkoa Provincial Council is firmly committed to tackling gender-based violence that severely impacts our society. In this regard, work is being carried out through various initiatives with agents and institutions, within the framework of collaboration as a hallmark of good governance. At the same time, the Gipuzkoa Agenda 20 > 30, in its axis 9, anticipates the development of a transition agenda that, through collective efforts to position social policies as a lever for the future, provides pathways to transform care and support models in Gipuzkoa. Specifically, this involves Action 29, which outlines the deployment of a new comprehensive model for supporting victims of gender-based violence.

1.1.4.20.2 Evidence and Data

According to the latest data published in the Macro Survey on Violence Against Women by the Spanish Ministry of Equality, in 2019, 31.4% of women over the age of 16 in the Basque Country had experienced some form of violence (physical, psychological, control, fear, economic, etc.) from their partners or ex-partners at some point in their lives (extrapolating this figure to the Basque Country's population in 2022, this amounts to 353,588 affected women), with 7.6% experiencing it in the last year (about 85,574 women). Additionally, 16.6% had suffered physical violence (186,992 women), and 8.6% had experienced sexual violence outside that context at some point (92,360 women).

The rates in the Basque Country are not significantly different from those recorded at the national level. The same source indicates that 32.4% of women aged 16 or older residing in Spain have suffered at least one type of violence from their partner or ex-partner at some point in their lives (physical, sexual, psychological, etc.), and 10.8% have experienced it in the last year. Additionally, 13.4% have suffered physical violence, and 6.5% have experienced sexual violence outside that context at some point in their lives. Data from the

European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights in the study "Violence Against Women: An EU-wide Survey" for the year 2012 indicates that one in three women in the European Union (33%) has experienced physical and/or sexual violence since the age of 15, including from partners or ex-partners and others, with 8% having suffered this violence in the last year.

Gender Based Violence (GBV) targeting Women								
	Autonomous Community of the Basque Country				Spain		Europe	
	2011		2019		2019		2012	
	Lifetime	last year	Lifetime	last year	Lifetime	last year	Lifetime	last year
Any form of GBV inside and outside of current and former Relationships	12,5	2	-	-	-	-	33	8
Any form of GBV inside of current and former relationships	7,5	1,2	31,4	7,6	32,4	10,8	22	4
Physical GBV outside of a relationship	-	-	16,6	-	13,4	0,9	-	-
Sexual GBV outside of a relationship	2,7	0,2	8,6	-	6,5	0,5	11	2
Any form of GBV, including acts attempted or carried out	-	18,2	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 1: Gender-based Violence (Based on Data from: EMAKUNDE, 2023)

Regarding the Social Services’ Attention Model and based on the data obtained from the Gipuzkoa’s Provincial Council Report, in 2023, 162 women were assisted in immediate and medium-stay shelters, 1,113 women received psychological care, and 199 women were provided with socio-legal assistance.

- The immediate - stay shelters, understood as short-term facilities accessible 24 hours a day, provide refuge to women who are victims of domestic abuse, along with their dependents, whether they are children, minors or not, or dependent adults. These shelters offer immediate care and support for the time needed to assess their needs before referring them to the most suitable resource. In 2023, there was an availability of 19 places in the immediate - stay shelters. The occupancy rate as of December 31st

was 79%, and the annual turnover rate (people assisted per year/number of available places) was 6%.

- Medium-stay shelters, understood as facilities designed for women who are victims of domestic violence and their dependents, providing them with a safe space for an extended period. These shelters offer support during the recovery process, focusing on social reintegration and helping women regain autonomy. In 2023, there was an availability of 26 places in the medium-stay shelters. As of December 31st, the occupancy rate was 104%, and the turnover rate (people per place) was 2.08%.
- Socio-legal and psychosocial support service for victims of abuse or acts against sexual freedom. This service provides specialized assistance to women who have experienced domestic violence or sexual violence, offering support in both legal and psychological aspects. It aims to help victims navigate the legal system, access necessary resources, and receive psychological counselling to aid in their recovery. From this service, the following interventions are carried out:
 - Psychological assistance for victims of gender-based violence: 585 new cases were assessed. The total number of cases attended to throughout the year was 1,319.
 - Socio-legal support: 126 new cases were assessed, and a total of 206 people were assisted, including 106 new cases.

1.1.4.20.3 Context of the Solution

The nature and complexity of gender-based violence necessitates a specific intervention model grounded in a feminist perspective and a gender-based approach. This approach ensures that all factors contributing to and complicating the issue are addressed comprehensively. The current regulatory framework recognizes violence against women as a human rights violation, particularly the right to live free from fear and violence. This recognition requires a commitment to providing services that prioritize the safety and well-being of victims in a non-discriminatory manner.

All system agents must uphold the rights involved in cases of violence against women and their children, including the right to dignity, autonomy and self-determination, security, privacy, the best interests of the child, social inclusion, and reparation. This approach also emphasizes two critical elements: empowerment and intersectionality. Empowerment is both

a means and an end—it involves supporting women to help themselves, seek assistance, and challenge the normalisation or minimisation of the violence they experience. While gender-based violence can affect all women, its impact may vary based on factors such as age, social class, origin, ethnicity, disability, residency status, and health. Thus, an intersectional approach is essential to address these additional inequalities and discrimination.

To support the recovery of victims, several key intervention strategies are essential, including:

- Person-Centred Planning, tailoring support to the individual needs of each victim.
- Non-Revictimisation, ensuring that victims are not subjected to further harm or trauma during the intervention process.
- Participation, involving victims in decisions affecting their recovery and support.
- Comprehensiveness, providing holistic and all-encompassing care.
- Community Model, leveraging community resources and support networks.
- Sisterhood, fostering solidarity and mutual support among women.
- Resilience, promoting the ability of victims to recover and rebuild their lives.

In line with these principles, the social services system of the Provincial Council of Gipuzkoa implements a comprehensive care model involving both Basic Social Services and Specialized Social Services.

1.1.4.20.4 Unintended Consequences and Risks

Challenges and/or risks in the Social Services System of the Provincial Council of Gipuzkoa regarding GBV are as follows:

Lack of Budget for Professional Training.

There are no allocated funds for the training of professionals, which impacts the quality and effectiveness of the intervention and support provided.

Limited Intersectional Perspective in Other Areas.

While the Provincial Council's model incorporates an intersectional perspective, other areas involved in victim support, such as health and judicial services, do not consistently apply a diversity-focused approach.

Harmful Impact of Foreigners' Law.

The current legislation on foreigners negatively affects the reparation processes for victims, complicating their recovery and access to support services.

Institutional Violence in Administrative Requirements.

Administrative processes and requirements may contribute to institutional violence, creating additional barriers and challenges for victims seeking assistance.

Urgency of Work and Case Management.

The urgent nature of cases and workload may lead to rushed decisions and insufficient attention to the complex needs of victims, affecting the overall quality of support and care provided.

Solution 4: GAMA (Abuse Care Group) of the Valencia Local Police (PLV)

1.1.4.21 Description

1.1.4.21.1 Background and Aim

The GAMA group was created in 2003 as a pioneering group in Spain to act specifically in the protection of victims of gender and domestic violence.

In October 2016, it was established as a group with exclusive dedication to this problem, which means that the agents who are part of it are dedicated to protection work for victims of gender violence, domestic violence and sexual assaults 100% of their working day. This change marked a turning point, both in terms of the quantitative results of the work carried out by the team, as well as a qualitative leap that has led to a substantial improvement in the quality, effectiveness and efficiency of the service provided to victims under protection which will be shown in detail below.

In 2018, legislative changes have been made to devolve responsibility in DV and GBV back to city councils. This change aimed to reinforce the role of local administrations and local police forces, recognising that their proximity to citizens enables them to offer more tailored services, especially when it comes to combat GBV. Law 6/2018, dated July 3, on the General State Budget, allocated specific funds for local entities to support the implementation of the State Pact against Gender Violence. Consequently, Valencia now receives funding for this purpose. These changes in the law have led the Valencia Local Police to develop the Abuse Care Group (GAMA) to tackle DV and GBV.

Over the years, GAMA has developed into a specialised unit dedicated to offering comprehensive assistance to victims. Operating within a collaborative network of support services, the unit works closely with various organisations and institutions. This ensures that victims are provided with timely and effective support.

In 2019, there were 300 arrests related to gender and DV in Valencia, making it the second cause for arrests after road safety offences - an area exclusively managed by the local police. GBV and DV represent the most significant public safety issue in Valencia. 1,300 victims were under police protection. GBV was reported at rates of only 20 to 25 per cent, suggesting

that a significant proportion of such violence remains hidden. By February 2024, GAMA has 36 police officers dedicated to its mission.

1.1.4.21.2 Implementation and Practice

GAMA adopts a multidisciplinary approach to guarantee that victims receive personalised support tailored to their unique needs. Through providing a diverse array of services and partnering with various organisations, GAMA ensures comprehensive assistance for victims. This holistic support is offered irrespective of the victims' background or abilities.

GAMA utilises the Comprehensive Monitoring System for Victims of Gender Violence (VIOGEN) to effectively monitor victims. This system was launched on March 13, 2014, following an agreement between the Ministry of Interior and the City of Valencia. VIOGEN enables a nationwide network connecting state, regional, and local security forces and bodies through respective agreements.

The process of registering victims' personal data within the VIOGEN police database is meticulously handled to ensure that specialised agents from GAMA units are consistently up to date with the victim's information. During the collection of this information, several critical aspects are prioritised:

- Creating a safe environment throughout the information-gathering phase. The PLV's has specifically designed GAMA offices located in each of the 7 Proximity Police Stations across the city, facilitating a proper environment for these discussions.
- Informed consent. This approach underscores the importance of transparency and respect for the individual's rights and preferences in the data collection process.
- Empathy and respect: Active listening and demonstrating empathy towards individuals are crucial.
- Open-ended approach: GAMA professionals employ open-ended and non-suggestive questions to encourage individuals to share their experiences in their own words.
- Avoid unnecessary repetition: Repetitive questioning is avoided because it forces individuals to relive their trauma.
- Emotional support: GAMA professionals provide emotional support throughout the information-gathering phase.

- Ensure confidentiality.

The professionals in charge of collecting information have adequate training in handling cases of violence or trauma, as well as in the technique of victim-centred interviewing, to avoid re-victimisation, which is why at PLV this part of care is always carried out by individuals with appropriate training, who have achieved their position through a selection process.

Additionally, GAMA employs an internal computer system that facilitates the entry of criminological profile data for enhanced monitoring. Since 2006, this system not only improves the tracking of victims but also allows for the generation of reports. These reports provide insights into the profiles of victims and perpetrators in Valencia, aiming to better evaluate public policies directed at addressing the needs of those affected by this severe issue.

This internal information system is particularly valuable for maintaining stringent control and monitoring of protection orders related to domestic and sexual violence. Unlike those already integrated into VIOGEN, these specific orders are managed exclusively by GAMA within the Local Police, thus ensuring focused and specialised protection for DV victims.

1.1.4.21.3 Strengths and Weaknesses

Strengths

- The team consists of specialised and trained personnel committed to supporting victims of DV and GBV.
- A comprehensive suite of services is available, encompassing legal, social, and psychological support to address various needs.
- Strong partnerships with a range of organisations and institutions ensure victims receive coordinated support.
- The approach is tailored to meet the unique backgrounds and needs of each victim, ensuring personalised support.
- Integration of innovative technological solutions.

Weaknesses

- Limited resources and capacity constraints can impede service provision.

- Difficulties in accessing marginalised or isolated communities may leave some without support.
- Coordination among different agencies and services sometimes presents gaps, potentially leading to fragmented care.

1.1.4.22 Justification

1.1.4.22.1 Conditions and factors for the successful implementation

The most important condition for initiating police actions in GAMA was legislative development. On December 28, 2004, the Spanish government approved Organic Law 1/2004 on Comprehensive Protection Measures against Gender Violence, which promoted comprehensive prevention strategies and legal, assistance and protection measures for victims of violence against women and domestic violence. In addition, the Spanish Criminal Code has undergone numerous reforms to typify the new crimes of gender violence, increasing the penalties and establishing precautionary measures of protection.

GAMA functions under the auspices of the Valencia Local Police and engages in collaboration with various public institutions and agencies. Adhering to established protocols and procedures, the Unit maintains flexibility, allowing it to respond effectively to changing needs and circumstances.

On the other hand, training of police officers is indispensable to carry out specialized care. This training is conducted both by GAMA's own experienced staff, who have been delivering training for over a decade, and with external support, through the "tutor agents" program. The goal is to extend this regulated and supervised program to an increasing number of institutions.

1.1.4.22.2 Practical relevance

Victims of GBV face compounded challenges due to fear, shame, and social isolation. Lack of awareness about available resources, difficulties in overcoming linguistic and cultural barriers, emotional or economic dependence on abusers, and insufficient social and family support significantly heighten their vulnerability.

GAMA teams counter these complex challenges by offering specialised training to law enforcement officers and ensuring that services are accessible and culturally sensitive.

Despite these measures, many women remain uninformed about community resources or are reluctant to seek assistance due to fears of retaliation or mistrust towards support services. Economic barriers also hinder access to support services, with some women unable to afford necessary expenses like transportation or legal consultation.

Additionally, the fragmented nature of local services presents a barrier to comprehensive care. Without effective coordination, victims struggle to access the diverse support measures they require, including legal, housing, medical, and emotional assistance. Cultural and social norms may also deter women from seeking municipal care services, leading to feelings of embarrassment or guilt. For this reason, the introduction of specialized agents can contribute to the meshing of the system, facilitating communication between the different specialties of victim care.

1.1.4.22.3 Evidence and Data

In the XVI Annual Report of the State Observatory of Violence against Women, published by the Ministry of Equality,⁶⁵ for the period 2010-2022, the number of cases of women with a police response decreases every year until 2016, when there is a slight upturn, which is accentuated in the following years. However, there is a major difference in the evolution of cases with no perceived risk and those requiring police protection: while the former decreased from 2011 to 2018, the latter increased steadily from 2013 to 2018. In 2022, the number of cases requiring police protection was higher than the number of cases with no perceived risk.

During the year 2023, the GAMA group made more than 18,500 follow-up calls to victims of gender violence, 4,164 Police Risk Assessments, 462 accompaniments to health centres, assistance or judicial headquarters, among other tasks aimed at the proper monitoring of the Protection Orders in force in that year.

1.1.4.22.4 Context of the Solution

All monitoring tasks performed by GAMA are carried out in compliance with the protocols established by the Ministry of the Interior and the Ministry of Equality, such as the Protocol

⁶⁵ For more information, see:

<https://violenciagenero.igualdad.gob.es/violenciaEnCifras/observatorio/informesAnuales/home.htm>

for collaboration and coordination between state security forces and local police forces for the protection of victims of domestic and gender violence, the Protocol for police risk assessment of intimate partner violence against women in Spain, or the “Zero Protocol” for the initial police contact with victims of gender violence who are in need of protection.

In Valencia we work with a national database, the Comprehensive Monitoring System for Victims of Gender Violence, (VIOGEN) implemented on March 13, 2014 through a membership agreement signed between the Ministry of the Interior and the Valencia City Council.

This system allows networking with all the State, Autonomous and Local Security Forces and Bodies adhered by the corresponding agreements.

1.1.4.22.5 Unintended Consequences and Risks

Risks

- Staff faces the risk of burnout and stress, attributed to the high demands of their services.
- Victims may remain vulnerable to continued abuse and the possibility of re-victimisation.
- Dependence on external factors, such as political support, can influence the stability and effectiveness of services.
- Deep-rooted societal attitudes and beliefs may continue to enable DV and GBV.
- Resource variability could disrupt the continuity of services.
- External crises or emergencies, like the COVID-19 crisis, pose challenges to maintaining effective service delivery.

Despite this, our experience leads us to propose some suggestions for improvement, such as:

- Expanding partnerships and collaborations with community organisations to widen the network of support and resources available to victims.
- Continuing to focus on training and capacity-building initiatives to enhance the ability to respond to the evolving needs of victims effectively.

- Increasing the number of specialised professionals to provide targeted support and counselling tailored to the specific circumstances of each victim.
- Allocating more social and economic resources to ensure comprehensive support covering legal, psychological, and financial assistance.
- Ensuring quick access to information for individuals seeking help, streamlining the process of reporting and accessing necessary resources efficiently.

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